

THE SYLLABLE STRUCTURE OF THE ANAANG LANGUAGE

BY

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ABSTRACT

In recent phonological theories, the syllable is regarded as a very important constituent and a domain of a number of phonological processes. However, few studies that had been carried out on the phonology of the Anaang language did not pay adequate attention to its syllable. A research in an important descriptive issue in Anaang phonology, such as the syllable, was this imperative. This study, therefore, investigated the syllable structure of Anaang, a Lower Cross language, spoken in Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria, with a view to identifying, classifying, and discussing the internal structure of its syllable. It explored the basic building blocks of Anaang phonology including segments and syllables.

The study employed a descriptive design and adopted the onset-Rhyme model of the non-linear phonology framework. Data were collected through a combination of oral interview and structured questionnaire methods. Twelve Anaang native speakers, above 30 years, were purposefully selected. Songs, stories, and narratives in Anaang were collected through oral performances using a tape recorder. The twelve subjects were asked to pronounce the 700 English words. Respondents provided the Anaang equivalents of the English words and read them into a tape recorder. Lexical items were elucidated from the data and described using the non-linear framework.

The internal structure of Anaang syllable comprised simple onset, simple or complex nuclei and simple coda. Onset and coda were optional, whereas the nucleus element was obligatory. Consonant at the coda were transitional and subjected to synchronic and historical sound change. This was evident in processes like consonant deletion, glide formation and resyllabification. Other processes that resulted in coda shift involved voicing assimilation and consonant weakening. The voiceless stops / p t k/ manifested as voiced and subsequently weakened to their homorganic continuants or tap / β r R / respectively in the environment of a following vowel at word boundary. Generally, different types of syllable structure violation are handled by different general strategies. Segments that do not fit into the syllable were labeled extrasyllabic. Such segments got deleted or were resyllabified by epenthesis. Whereas segments which violated feature combinations in syllable positions were subjected to a feature changing process in conformity with Anaang phonotactics. These were mirrored by repair strategies applied in the modification of Anaang loan-words and in even other language enrichments processes like affixation, reduplication and compounding, including sentence constructions.

This work is a contribution to current phonological theories in general and syllable structure theories in particular. It equally contributes to a better understanding of the Anaang phonology. Phonological processes of the Anaang language is better characterized through the dynamics of phonological representation in a phonological hierarchy which has the syllable as its domain. Many phenomena relevant to the phonology of Anaang can, therefore, be properly understood when the representation is enriched within the syllable.

Word count: 461

Key words: Anaang, syllable, internal structure, phonotactics, clusters.

DEDICATION

Mmesana nwet em uno fien

PROFESOR ENO-ABASI ESSIEN URUA

Afo ade Eti Eka Unwana

Mme utuenitan ifiok

Uwana fo inyiehe mbeen
Ajaajamma

Afo ade Eti Eka Unwana
Ka iso jamma!!!!

TRANSLATION

This work is dedicated to you

PROFESSOR ENO-ABASI ESSIEN URUA

You are the MOTHER of LIGHT

And the PILLAR of KNOWLEDGE

Your BRIGTNES has no boundary

It shines continuously

You are the MOTHER of LIGHT
Continue shining!!!!

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CERTIFICATION BY SUPERVISOR

I certify that this work was carried out by Itoro Anietie Michael, in the Department of Linguistics and African Languages, University of Ibadan, Ibadan.

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ABBREVIATIONS AND KEY TO SYMBOLS

C	Consonant
V	Vowel
N	Nasal
L	Liquid
G	Glide
SGP	Standard Generative Phonology
AP	Autosegmental phonology
L	Low Tone
H	High Tone
LH	Low-High Tone
O	Onset
N	Nucleus
C	Coda
R	Rhyme
TBU	Tone Bearing Unit
+	Morpheme Boundary
#	Word Boundary
#-	Word initial position
-#	word final position
~	Nasalization
V-V	Intervocalic
C-C	Interconsonantal
N	Syllabic nasal
.	Syllabic
//	Phonemic brackets
[]	Phonetic brackets
[˥]	High tone
[˩]	low tone
[!]	Downsteeped High Tone
[˩˥]	Low-High Contour
[˥˩]	High- low Contour
[:]	Length
[ˈ]	Stress
σ	Syllable
→	Becomes
/	Environment
~	Free Variation
˩	Syllabic sign
-	Syllabic division
*	Asterisks
˩	Mora

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background Information

Anaang is a language spoken in the north – western region of Akwa Ibom state of Nigeria. The language is named after the speakers “ANAANG” who constituted the former Abak and Ikot – Ekpene provinces of Eastern Nigeria. Today, speakers of Anaang spread across Abak, Ika, Ikot-Ekpene, Etim Ekpo, Essien Udim, Obot- Akara, Oruk – Anam and Ukanafun Local Government Areas (LGAs) of Akwa Ibom State. They number 1.6 million following the 1991 census result and occupy a total area of 2.73sq kilometers (Umoren 1997). Anaang has four broad varieties viz: Abak, Ika, Ikot Ekpene and Ukanafun with a high rate of mutual intelligibility.

This classification is based on the geographical locations. Abak dialect is spoken in Abak, Essien Udim, and Etim Ekpo Local Government Areas. They occupy the central part of Anaang. Ika is spoken in Ika local Government only. They are located at the central region of Anaang. Speakers of Ikot Ekpene dialect spread across Ikot-Ekpene, and Obot- Akara Local Government Areas. Ukanafun speakers are located at Oruk Anam and Ukanafun Local Governments. They constitute Southern Anaang. A geographical sketch of Anaang is presented in a diagram in (1).

Genetically, Anaang is classified as a Lower – Cross Language, of the new Benue – Congo sub-family of the Niger–Congo family of languages (Greenberg 1963). Cook (1985), Connell (1991, 1995), Williamson (1989), Williamson & Blench (2000), Crozier and Blench (1992) and Udoh (1998), classify Anaang as a Lower Cross Language after Greenberg’s classification. Faraclaus (1989) proposes a central name “Cross River”, since this language alongside Ibibio, Efik and Ukwu are spoken in the Cross River region. This shows that Efik, Ibibio, Anaang, and Ukwu are closely related. Essien (1987) and Urua (1996b) group these languages under the Central Cross group of the Niger Congo family of languages. For the purpose of this study, Anaang is considered a Central Lower-Cross Language alongside Efik and Ibibio after Connell (1991). This is illustrated in a tree diagram below.

LINGUISTIC ATLAS OF ANAANG LANGUAGE (LAA1)

SCALE 1:50,000

KEY	
Local Town Boundary	
Northern Anaang	
Central Anaang	
Southern Anaang	

1 Tree diagram showing the genetic relationship of the Anaang language

Adapted from Connell (1991).

On the level of development, Anaang is the least developed among the Efik, Ibibio, Anaang group. The first written work on Anaang was in (1954) by Koelle 'Anaang in Polyglotta Africana'. Koelle presented Anaang as a language spoken in Ikot Ekpene province of Eastern Nigeria. In his discussion, he tried to present some sounds as they are produced in certain lexical items. Other scholarly research, include: (Utip 1985, Udondatta 1993, 2000, Idem 1994, Udoh 1998 and Udom 1999). The area of focus on these research works are on comparative / contrastive studies which lead to transfer effects, developmental as well as language universal problems militating against second language learning with particular reference to English. For instance, Utip (1985), provided a

comparative description on the vowels of Anaang, Efik and Ibibio and concluded that these languages do not have the same vowel inventory even though they are closely related. Udondatta (1993), focused on a contrastive analyses of the English and Anaang phonological systems and showed that errors are bound to occur in the production of the English lexical items by the Anaang speakers, since the two languages have unrelated phonological inventory. Udondatta (2000) presented a description of the Anaang structural pattern, and established a basis for the description of the Anaang words. Idem (1994) researched on the transfer effects created by the Anaang learners of the English liquid and stop segments which of course, militates against second language learning. Udoh (1999) focused on the effects of duration on the Anaang learners of English and presented the transferred errors militating against second language learning. However, Michael (2000) shifted focus from contrastive to a descriptive study. Her area of interest was on assimilation processes as they affect the structure of Anaang.

The present study is a descriptive work on the structure of Anaang, with emphasis on the internal structure of the syllable and their constraints. Our analysis is based on the non-linear theoretical framework with particular reference to the CV-tier model (Clements and Keyser 1983) and the Onset-Rhyme theory (Ewen and Hulst 2001).

1.2 The Sound System of Anaang

Our concentration here is on the consonants, vowels, tones and the syllable structure.

1.2.1 Anaang Consonants

Anaang has twenty eight phonetic consonants comprising stops, fricatives, affricates, tap, lateral, approximants, and syllabic nasals. At the same time, the language has an inventory of twenty-one consonant phonemes as presented in tables 1 and 11 respectively.

Table 1 Anaag phonetic consonant chart
Place of articulation

Manner of articulation	Bilabial	Labiodental	Dental	Alveolar	Alveo palatal	Palatal	Velar	Labio velar	Labialized velar	uvular
Oral stops	p b		t̪ d̪	t d			k	kp	kw	
Nasal stops	m	ɱ		n		ɲ	ŋ		ŋ ^w	
Tap				r						
Trill										R
Lateral				l						
Fricatives	β	f		s	ʃ					ʁ
Affricates					tʃ dʒ					
Approximants							j		w	
Syllabic nasal		ɱ								

Table II Anaang phonemic consonant chart
Place of articulation

Manner of articulation	Bilabial	Labiodental	Alveolar	Alveo palatal	Palatal	Velar	Labio velar	Labialized velar	uvular
Oral stops	p b		t - d			ʔ	kp	ɕ ^w	
Nasal stops	m	ɱ	n		ɲ	ŋ		ŋ ^w	
Tap			r						
Lateral			l						
Fricatives	β	f	s						χ
Affricates				tʃ dʒ					
Approximants						j		w	

1.2.1.1 Consonant Distribution in Anaang

The following provides illustration of the phonemic consonants as they occur in Anaang.

1.

/p/ /dʒùppɔ́ / flog
/étáp / saliva

/b/ /bó / say
/ébá / breast

/t/ /tá / chew
/ltá/ three
/bót/ mould

/d/ /dáídʒá/ sleep

	/bòt/	mould
/d/	/dàidzà/	sleep
	/ndáp/	dream
/k/	/kúnó/	wrap
	/ŋkɔ̄/	u-like shape
	/ákák /	game played in the sand
/g ^w /	/g ^w òt/	kill
	/ig ^w uò/	head
/kp/	/kpá/	cut
	/ikpá/	cane
/m/	/mèk/	chose
	/mímàn/	mild
	/iném/	sweet
/n/	/nèk/	dance
	/únèk/	dance (noun)
	/mèn/	swallow
/ŋ /	/ŋké/	proverbs
	/sàŋá/	walk
	/ibɔ̄ŋ/	kola nut
/ŋ ^w /	/ŋ ^w éék/	breathe
	/iŋ ^w éék/	breath
/ɲ/	/ɲímmé/	accept
	/á ɲɔ̄ŋ/	up

/f/	/fidé/	forget
	/míḽḽu/	frog
/s/	/sḽḽḽ/	squat
	/nsim/	tail
/tʃ/	/tʃin/	reject
	/itʃin/	waist
/dʒ/	/dʒit/	lock
	/ádʒòp/	oil palm tree
/r/	/úbàrà/	blood
/l/	/úlúk/	pity
/j/	/ájàṅ/	broom
/ʋ/	/ bóʋó/	be close
/w/	/wéré/	roll
	/àwàwà/	green

1.2.1.2 Differences

/ʋ/ and /R/ are in complementary distribution. /R/ occurs before a front vowel, while /ʋ/ occurs before a non front vowel as in example (2).

2.

/f ḽḽḽ/	'be sad'
/n ḽḽḽ/	'bend'
/m ḽḽḽ/	'be short'
/méRè /	'be familiar'

/n̄sɛRɛ/ 'premature'

In Abak dialect, /s/ and /ʃ/ are in free variation as the following example shows.

3.

/ʊsɔ̄/	~	/ʊʃɔ̄/	'your father'
/n̄sijà/	~	/n̄ʃijà/	'intestine'
/n̄sikpàrikpà/	~	/n̄ʃikpàrikpà	'tadpole'
/siné/	~	/ʃiné/	'wear'
/sùùk/	~	/ʃùùk/	'lower'
/sijòŋ/	~	/ʃijòŋ/	'abuse'

In all the dialects but Ikot Ekpene, /w/ and /b/ are used interchangeably in a few lexical forms. This occurs in words exemplified in (4).

4.

/bip/	~	/wip/	'ask'
/ébót/	~	/éwót/	'goat'
/éba/	~	/éwá/	'breast'
/bó/	~	/wó/	'say'

It should, however, be noted that this process occurs in only restricted items. Ikot Ekpene speakers maintain /b/ in all contexts.

/d~r~/ are in free variation in some instances. They occur in few lexical items as follows.

5.

/ùtèdè/	~	/ùtèrè/	~	/ùtèlè/	'vulture'
/ùdádà/	~	/ùdàrà/	~	/ùdálà/	'a kind of fruit'
/ùdúk/	~	/ùrúk/	~	/ùlúk	'rope'
/ùdùà/	~	/ùrùà/	~	/ùlùà/	'market'
/ìbɔ̀ɔ̀dɔ̀/	~	/ìbɔ̀ɔ̀rɔ̀/	~	/ìbɔ̀ɔ̀lɔ̀/	'answer'
/tùdó/	~	/tùró/	~	/tuló/	'stop'

Note however that each of /d r l / can equally occur as a separate phoneme as represented in example (section 1.1.2.1) above.

The phoneme /kp/ is absent in Ikot Ekpene dialect of Anaang. This is replaced with /p/ so that we have words such as

6.

/kpèèné/	/pèèné/	'delay'
/kpón/	/pón/	'become big'
/ákpàn	/ápàn/	'big basket'
/ékpémmé	/épémmé/	'bottle'

The phoneme /p/ does not occur word initially except in Ikot Ekpene dialect. It however occurs as geminate word medially. Other segments that occur as geminates include /t k m n ŋ/. Examples follow.

7.

/sɔ̃ppɔ̃/	'be fast'
/mbɛttɔ̃/	'rotten substance'
/kpékké/	'cut'
/ákpámmá/	'broken bottles'
/kánná/	'turn'
/tàŋŋà/	'quarrel'

The voiceless stops / p t k / are unreleased word finally. Orthographically, /t/ is represented as 'd' word finally. This however led to the analysis of these segments as voiced by Udoh (1998) and Udondatta (2000). It should however be noted that the voiced stop segments in Anaang do not occur word finally. At the same time, voiced stops are barred from syllable final position by Anaang phonotactics. Therefore in a situation where these segments occur word finally, it implies that they can automatically occur at the coda or syllable final position thereby violating Anaang phonotactic constraints. Secondly, Anaang phonotactics do not allow segments that cannot be geminated to occur as the coda element. Voiced oral stops cannot occur as geminates and as a result are barred from word final position in Anaang.

1.2.1.3 Syllabic Nasals

The following nasals are syllabic in Anaang [m n ŋ] Example follows.

8

[m-kpáná]	'bed'
[m-bòppò]	'young lady'
[ñ-ḶḶḶḶ]	'cassava'
[ñ-támmá]	'act of jumping'
[ŋ-kùwáunèn]	'eggs'
[ŋ-kùdikù]	'owl'

Syllabic nasals are homorganic with a following segment. This shows that the place feature specification of a syllabic nasal is always determined by the place feature characteristic of a following segment as presented in the example in (9).

9

(i)	[ń tán]	'sand'
(ii)	[ń dòm]	'white clay'
(iii)	[m' bà]	'wing'
(iv)	[m' kpá]	'death'
(v)	[ŋ kà]	'charcoal'
(vi)	[ŋ g'èt]	'book'
(vii)	[ŋfēm]	'cockroach'

In some other instances, the syllabic nasals may not share the same place feature with a following consonant. Let us consider the following data.

10.

(i)	/nd ₃ én/	[ń d ₃ én]	'a tiny object'
(ii)	/ntfáát/	[ntfáát]	'dried object'
(iii)	/ń ɲ â/	[ń ɲâ]	'garden egg'
(iv)	/ń ɲ â ŋ/	[ń ɲ âŋ]	'sharp rope from raffia '

Note that the nasal /n/ is prefixed to the items in (10 i-iv). It does not share the same place feature with a following segment. This leads to the justification of assessing the alveolar nasal /n/ as the generic form of the nasal. This analysis is supported by the fact that in such cases, there are only two possible phonetic realization of the syllabic nasal in the prefix: either as /n/ or as a nasal, which is homorganic with a following consonant. The phonetic distribution of syllabic nasals in Anaang is illustrated in (11) as follows.

11.

Apart from word initial position, there are restricted number of words where syllabic nasals are seen word medially as represented in example (12)

12.

[m̀ bùk m̀ bùk]	N-CVC-N-CVC	'interestingly'
[ǹ dáp ǹ dáp]	N-CVC-N-CVC	'wonderfully'
[m̀ bà ǹ sán]	N-CV-N-CVC	'groundnut'
[m̀ kpá ǹ tük]	N-CV-N-CVC	'sweet fruit'

Syllabic nasals in Anaang are used to mark persons, numbers, nouns, adjectives etc. as presented in example (13).

13. Personal marker

first person

- (i) m̀-ɓ̀k áféré
I – cook soup 'I am cooking'
- (ii) n̂-súk n̂-dí
I-pres I – come 'I am coming'
- (iii) n̂-dà di
i-shall come 'I shall come'
- (iv) ḡ-ḡ^wɓ̀ ḡ ḡ^wɓ̀^w
I-drink water 'I am drinking water'

Syllabic nasals here mark first person singular.

14. Plural marker

singular		Plural
/éti/	'good'	[níti]
/á!bɓ̀ɓ̀ ^w /	'chief'	[m̂!bɓ̀ɓ̀ ^w]
/ètòk/	'small'	[ntòk]

The plural markers are [m, n] respectively.

They also act as derivational prefix in deriving nouns, adjectives, adverbs from verbs.

15 verbs		nouns	
(i) /ɗ̀/	'marry'	/n̂-ɗ̀/	'marriage'
(ii) /biòm/	'carry (load)'	/m̂-biòm /	'load'
(iii) /g ^w èt/	'write'	/ḡ-g ^w èt /	'book'
(iv) /má/	'love'	/m̂-má /	'mother'
(v) /ḡ ^w ɓ̀ ^w /	'drink'	/ḡ-ḡ ^w ɓ̀ ^w /	'water'
(vi) /kpá/	'die'	/m̂kpá/	'death'

16. Verbs		adjectives
(i) /bóóró/	'be complete'	/m̀- bóóró/ 'round'
(ii) /bàk/	'be early'	/m̀- báák/ 'broken things'
(iii) /fín/	'be good'	/m̀- fín/ 'good things'

17. Verbs		adverbs
(iv) /fín /	'be good'	/ m̀- fín m̀- fín / 'orderly'
(v) /kpá/	'die'	/ m̀- kpá m̀kpá / 'deadly'

Equally, the syllabic nasals are used as loanword prefix¹ to some noun forms as presented in example (18).

18.	
/mmótó /	'motor'
/mmédi /	'Mary'
/ndzín/	'engine'

Apart from grammatical contrast, syllabic nasals are used to mark lexical contrast. A substitution of a vowel with a syllabic nasal will result in a meaning difference of the following words in (19a & b)

19. a		b	
(i) /èkà/	'mother'	/ŋ̀- kà/	'age grade'
(ii) /iták/	'stand'	/ǹ- ták/	'reason'
(iii) /ákpǎ/	'bone'	/m̀- kpǎ/	'something'
(iv) /ákpá/	'first'	/m̀- kpá/	'death'
(v) /úbǎk/	'hand'	/m̀- bǎk/	'wrestling'
(vi) /ádžén/	'child'	/ǹ- džen/	'tiny thing'
(vii) /ábót/	'hill'	/m̀- bót/	'boil'
(viii) /ibát/	'fish'	/m̀- bát/	'dirt'

Generally, the syllabic nasal bears tones just like vowels, it is classified as [+cons] [+syl].

1.2.2 Anaang Vowels

Anaang has sixteen phonetic vowels. These are made up of seven short vowels and seven long vowels / a, a:, e, e:, i, i:, o, o:, ɔ, ɔ:, u, u:, ʉ, ʉ:, ə, ə: /. However, the language has a total number of seven phonemic vowels. The description is presented in tables III and IV respectively.

Table III Anaang phonetic vowel chart.

Table IV Anaang phonemic vowel chart

1.2.2.1 Vowel Distribution in Anaang

There is a restriction of occurrence of vowels at word initial position. Out of the seven vowels, / o ʉ ɔ / cannot occur word initially. The analysis of our data reveals that, non-high rounded vowels are barred from word initial position, they can occur elsewhere. Only / a e i u / are possible vowel initial segments in Anaang. However, all the vowels can occur word medially and word finally as illustrated in (20a).

20a. Distribution of Anaang phonemic vowels.

/a/	/áfò /	you
	/ifāŋ/	how many?
	/ikpá/	cane
/e/	/èkpè/	lion
	/èkpèk/	chin
	/ikpè/	pit
/i/	/ikpá/	skin
	/tím /	pound
	/étí/	good
/o /	/tóp/	throw
	/èkpó/	masquerade
/ɔ/	/kɔp/	hang
	/nɔ /	give
/u/	/úkót/	leg
	/úsúŋ/	road
	/èg ^w ù /	termite

/t̩/	/m̩t̩m/	catch
	/áǵ ^w t̩/	dust

Anaang vowels equally attest length phenomenon where all the vowels can be lengthened as presented in example (20b) as follows.

20b.

/a:/	/kááp/	carve
/e/	/kpéép/	teach
/i:/	/jiin/	soak
/o:/	/ákóóp/	drinking cup (with long curved mouth)
/ɔ:/	/k ɔ́ɔk/	pile up
/u:/	/úkuút/	distress
/t̩:/	/im̩t̩t̩m/	a dumb person

Vowel lengthening is very restricted in Anaang. It does not occur in an environment other than intercosonantal position. There is a contrast between pure vowels and their lengthened counterpart. Detailed analysis on vowel lengthening is postponed to chapter three.

1.3 Anaang Tones

The concept of tone in African languages has received quite a lot of attention (Welmers 1973, Newman 1995, Kenstowicz 1994, Cook 1985, Williamson 2003, Clements 2000, Urua 2000 and Yip 2002, 2007). Perhaps, the most outstanding characteristic of tone in African languages is its autonomy with respect to its segmental slot. The independent characteristic constitutes the centre of focus in autosegmental phonology (Goldsmith 1976, 1990). The basic autonomous feature of tone according to Goldsmith, is that tones are represented on a separate tier and are anchored to tone bearing units such as syllabic segments by means of association lines.

Two types of tone languages have been identified in the literature. These are: register and contour tone languages (Clements 1990). Anaang is a register tone language with two level tones; High (H) and Low (L). Anaang also has downstepped

high tone (D), low-high (L-H) and high-low (H-L) sequence in addition to the high and low level tones. The low-high and high-low tones sometimes occur as a result of a cluster of the high-low tone sequences or low-high tone sequences as the case may be. The contour tones occur only in a restricted environment in Anaang, therefore cannot be treated as phonemic even though they equally contrast with the level low tones in such a restricted environment. In *Ibibio*, a Lower Cross language, Essien (1990) regards the low-high and high-low tones as phonemic, whereas Urua (1987, 1990, 2007) analyse them as phonetic manifestations of high-low or low-high tonal sequences which of course occur in a restricted environment just like the downstepped high tone. The level high and low tones are phonemic in Anaang.

The following symbols are used to indicate tones

21.

H	[ˈ]	High
L	[ˌ]	Low
D	[!]	Downstepped
LH	[ˈˌ]	Low-High
HL	[ˌˈ]	High-Low

1.3.1 Anaang Lexical Tones

Previous work on Anaang lexical tones (Udoh 1998, Idem 1998), show that the two level tones (L,H), contrast in all the environments, while the contrast involving downstepped high tone, low-high or high-low tones is restrictive as represented in examples (22-31).

The following lexical tones are present in Anaang.

22. H

/dà/	'stand'
/mín/	'frown'

L

/dà/	'friend'
/mín/	'press'

23. H H

/tàngà/	'gather in bits'
/tímmé /	'stay back'
/tákkɔ́/	'uncover'

L L

/tàngà/	'quarrel'
/tímmè/	'try'
/tákkɔ́/	'conceal'

24. L L L L H H H H
- | | | | |
|-------------|-------------|----------|-----------|
| /ntɔ̀ɔ̀dɔ̀/ | 'foofoo' | ŋkánáfǎŋ | 'lamp' |
| /inèmèsit/ | 'happiness' | úkáridém | 'matchet' |
| /ìbèdèdèm/ | 'supporter' | úkárákpá | 'python' |
| /idòrèjèn/ | 'hope' | | |
-
25. H L L H
- | | | | |
|----------|----------|---------|-------------|
| /úfɔ̀ k/ | 'house' | /úfɔ̀k/ | 'side' |
| /úmàn/ | 'female' | /ùmán/ | 'a nursing' |
| /ákɛ́/ | 'priest' | /ákɛ́/ | 'circle' |
-
26. mixed tones
- | | | |
|------------|------|------------|
| /údɔ̀ɔ̀ɔ̀/ | LHH | 'sickness' |
| /úbàrà/ | HLL | 'blood' |
| /itòòró/ | HLLH | 'praises' |

The examples in (22-26) show that all the syllables in a word be associated with the same level tones or mixed level tones. The number of tones in the above data determines the number of syllables per word. Each syllable is assigned at least one tone. Example (24) has four syllables each with four tones.

The above presentation simply illustrates simple tones in Anaang. The level tones can occur syllable initially, medially and finally. At the same time, lexical contrast on level tones is not restricted to a specific environment. Let us consider the following contrastive pairs.

27. Anaang contrastive lexical tones at different environments.

(i) syllable initial position'

L		H	
/ákpá/	'first'	/ákpá/	'water surface'
/ìkpè/	'pit'	/ìkpé/	'judgment'

(ii) syllable medial position

H		L	
/m'kpáná/	'bed'	/m'kpànà/	'material for building'
/àkpákpâ/	'death something'	/àkpákpà/	'corn'

(iii) syllable final position

H		L	
/má/	like	/mà/	finish
/àbá/	den	/àbà/	forty
/élɔ̃ŋ/	sheep	/élɔ̃ŋ/	knee

Apart from the level tones, L-H pattern equally occurs in Anaang within a syllable but only in restricted lexical items as presented in (28).

28.

/tié/	'sit'
/náá/	'lie down'
/kàá/	'go'
/dùɔ̃/	'fall'

Lexically, this tone is restricted to only the final syllable.

Lexically, LH, HL tonal patterns are restricted to word final syllable and occur more frequently in open syllable. Generally, LH contour can occur as lexical contrast in disyllabic words.

This is presented in (29)

29.

/àkpò/	L- H	'male goat'	/àkpô/	H-LH	'non-initiates'
/ùkpò/	L- L	'terrific'	/ùkpô/	L-LH	'a kind of tree'
/ìkpɔ̃/	H-L	'sweat'	/ìkpô/	H-LH	'rope used in climbing a tall tree'

Grammatically, contour tones (cf 1.3.2.3) contrast in certain contexts.

Example follows.

30

- | | | |
|-------|----------|----------------------------|
| (i) | àtà ébót | 'you are eating goat meat' |
| (ii) | ǎtà ébót | 'you ate goat meat' |
| (iii) | tá | 'chew' |
| (iv) | tâ | 'you may chew it' |

Another tonal structure involves downstepped high tone represented with the exclamation mark [!].

31.

- | | | | | |
|-------|----------|----------|---------|--------------------|
| (i) | /á!bɔ́ŋ/ | 'chief' | /ábɔ́ŋ/ | 'mosquito' |
| (ii) | /m!bɔ́k/ | 'please' | /mɔ́k/ | 'wrestling' |
| (iii) | /á!bɔ́ŋ/ | 'chief' | /ábɔ́ŋ/ | 'pimples' |
| (iv) | /ú!ké/ | 'where' | /úkè/ | 'a specie of bird' |

Example (31 i-ii) presents a lexical contrast between downstepped high tone and a level high tone. (31 iii-iv) illustrates a contrast with a low tone.

An earlier analysis (Urua 2007:160-165) shows that downstepped high tone is always preceded by a high tone. Secondly, this tone occurs only on the second syllable. Therefore, the occurrence of downstepped high tone is very restricted in Anaang. Even though the downstepped high tone contributes to lexical contrast in example (31), it should however be noted that the contrast does not occur syllable initially and cannot combine freely with other tones except in the environment of a H H tonal sequence. Therefore, downstepped high tone is a phonetic modification of a high tone.

1.3.2 Grammatical Tones in Anaang

Tone is an important grammatical feature in Anaang. A change of a tone in a syllable can mark grammatical functions in question, aspect and person.

1.3.2.1 Person

32 (a) á tò ùlké? 'Where do you come from?'

2nd per sg. come from where?

(b) á tò ùlké? 'Where does he come from?'

3rd per sg. come from where?

The syllabic prefix /a/ is a personal marker. A substitution of a low tone with a high tone in the initial syllable results in a grammatical contrast of second and third person singular in the sentence.

1.3.2.2 Question

33. (a) á dèmmé he is awake.

3rd person wake up

(b) á dèmmé? is he awake?

3rd person wake up

There is an alteration of the tone on the first syllable of the verb. This alteration marks the contrast between statement and question in (33) above.

1.3.2.3 Aspect

34. (a) à tàmmà òtámmá (progressive)
you progress jump jump (n) you are jumping

(b) ǎ támmá òtámmá (completive)
you past jump jump(n) you jumped

1.3.3 Anaang Tonal Features

Tones usually affect each other phonetically when juxtaposed in certain environments. Juxtaposition of tonal sequences in a word results in what Goldsmith (1990), Crystal (1997), call tonal sandhi. Tonal sandhi is a situation where tones sometimes affect each other phonetically so that pitches of voice change continuously throughout the derivation of sounds, leading to downstepping, and tonal raising among other tonal features.

1.3.3.1 Tonal Downstepping

Tonal downstepping is a common phenomenon in Nigerian languages such as Igbo, Hausa Yoruba, Ibibio etc. Synchronic evidence reveals that a high tone is downstepped following a lost or a floating low tone. There is a perturbation of the second high tone in the sequence leading to downstepping. In other words, the second high tone becomes downstepped owing to the intervention of a floating low tone. This has been demonstrated in (Urua 2007) for Ibibio, from certain syntactic constructions as presented in example (35).

(35) agentive construction in Ibibio

àkpɔ́kɔ́ + èkɔ́t → àkpɔ́kélkɔ́t 'one who has a bald occipod'

The downstepping effect on the final syllable is created by the preceding low tone even though no vowel is deleted. Let us consider data from Anaang, repeated here as example (36).

36

- (i) /á!bɔ́k/ 'chief'
 (iii) /m!bɔ́k/ 'please'

Downstepped high tone in Anaang is significant since it contrasts with the level high tones as the example in (37) demonstrates.

- | | | | | |
|-------|----------|----------|---------|-------------------|
| 37. | | | | |
| (i) | /á!bɔ́k/ | 'chief' | /ábɔ́k/ | 'mosquito' |
| (ii) | /m!bɔ́k/ | 'please' | /máb k/ | 'wrestling' |
| (ii) | /á!bɔ́k/ | 'chief' | /ábɔ́k/ | 'pimples' |
| (iii) | /i!nèm/ | sweet' | /inèm/ | 'a kind of leave' |

The historical account on the derivation of these words has been lost. Therefore, the presence of a floating low tone in this example cannot be traced. However, evidence abound in various grammatical constructions to show that downstepping occur as a result of a preceding floating low tone. Example follows.

38 adverbial construction

úkàŋ	+	mí	→	ú!mí	'this side'
side		here			
úkàŋ	+	dé	→	ú!dé	'that side'
side		there			
úkàŋ	+	kó	→	ú!kó	'yonder'
side		there			
úkàŋ		ké	→	ú!ké	'where?'
side		at			

There is an underlying floating low tone after the deletion of the second syllable in the (8). This floating low tone, however, leads to the downstepping of a following high tone as demonstrated in (39).

(39)

1.3.3.2 Tonal Replacement

Tonal replacement occurs as a result of some grammatical constructions as presented in (40).

(40) noun-noun construction

(i)	/úkót/ # /ŋwèt/	HHLL	[úkótŋwèt]	HHHL	'foot note'
	leg	book			
(ii)	/úbɔ́k/ # /èlèm/	HHLL	[úbɔ́kèlèm]	HHHL	'bribe'
	hand	back			
(iii)	/éwá/ # /ùlò/	HHLL	[éwáùlò]	HHHL	'dragon fly'
	dog	water pit			

The low tone on the initial syllable of the second word is replaced with a high tone in the penultimate syllable at the surface structure. Whereas, the data in (41) involves the replacement of the high tone with the low tone at the final syllable as follows.

41.

- (i) /ikpá/ + /itʃin/ HH HH → /ikpájʃin/ HHL 'belt'
 skin waist
- (ii) /ákpǎ/ + /úsún/ HHHH → /ákpáúsún/ HHHL 'road'
 bone road
- (iii) /èkpàt/ + /úbók/ LLHH → /èkpàrúbók/ LLHL 'hand bag'
 bag hand

In Anaang, compounds carry a final low tone and a high tone on the penultimate syllable irrespective of the tonal structure of the underlying construct. This shows that certain grammatical constructions have a fixed tonal pattern irrespective of the tonal pattern of the derived word. This process is equally applicable to a language like Shona. In the Shona language, if a noun begins with H tones, those H's become L when preceded by one of the prefixes né- sé- and ché as demonstrated by (Odden 2005:308). The prefixes are represented as follows;

- ne- 'with a noun'
 se- 'like a noun'
 che- 'of a noun'

Example

42. N

mbwá	né-mbwà	'dog'	(with N)
hóvé	sé-hòvè	'fish'	(like N)
hákátà	ché-hákàtá	'fool'	(of N)

Odden (2005:308) regards this tone lowering process as 'across-the-board tone change'.

Tone is said to be a property of the syllable in the sense that no syllable can exist without at least one tone as illustrated above. Even though tone is a property of the syllable, it can exist independent of the syllable. This is illustrated in vowel deletion and tonal reassociation processes. The deletion of a vowel (tone bearing segment), in most instances typically leads to desyllabification. The tone that was anchored to the deleted syllable cannot delete, it lingers on and gets reassociated with an adjacent surviving syllable because tone is autonomous or exists independently as formalized in (43).

43.

/èté # àfò/ → /è té à fò/ → [è té:fò] 'your father'
 V CV V CV V CV V CV V CV CV

(Refer to 4.2 for detailed illustration).

The discussion on Anaang tones and their characteristics is not exhaustive here. Tone is a vast phenomenon in Anaang phonetics and phonology. A more detailed descriptive account of Anaang tones can successfully be carried out as an independent research, where phonetic and phonological details can be logically presented.

1.4 Anaang Syllable structure

The basic syllables of the Lower Cross languages, to which Anaang belongs, are [CV, CVC, V, N]. Other syllables augmented from these basic structures give room to the divergent structures. We present a cross linguistic variation of the Lower Cross syllable, specifically Anaang, Efik and Ibibio in table V.

Table V Cross linguistic variation of the Lower Cross syllable

	Anaang	Efik	Ibibio
V	+	+	+
CV	+	+	+
CVV	+	+	+
CVC	+	+	+
CVVC	+	+	+
CGV	-	+	+
CVG	-	+	+
C ₁ C ₂ V	-	+	+
N	+	+	+

In Efik and Ibibio C₂ may be any of / r, y, w/.

Actual data on the Cross linguistic variation of the Lower Cross syllable are presented in (44 -54).

44. Efik/ Ibibio syllables

V	à-kpá	first
CV	dí	come
CVV	káá	go
CVC	tém	cook
CVVC	féén	forgive
CGV	tjě	sit
CVG	wâj	tear
C ₁ C ₂ V	brě	play

From the representation in (table IV), we can deduce that Anaang has a total number of six possible syllable structures as the following data illustrate

i. N Shape.

This is usually a syllabic nasal, which is homorganic with a following consonant. The generic form of the syllabic nasal is /n/. It bears tone just like vowels as in the following examples.

45.

/n̄-fín/	'today'
/n̄-dáp/	'dream'
/n̄-nàn /	'blind person'
/m̄-múùm/	'darkness'
/ŋ̄-ŋ̄ ^w ɔ́ŋ̄/	'water'
/ŋ̄-kàŋ	'ribs'

ii V Shape.

The /V/ syllable is a very wide spread structure in Anaang. This syllable consists of a vowel which is restricted to /a e i u/. It should, however, be emphasized that other vowels like /o ɔ ʉ/ cannot occur in this syllable. It is the minimum syllable type in the language. It cannot occur independently as a phonological word. It occurs initially in a word or as a prefix in some word classes

like nouns, nominals, adjectives, adverbs, as well as pronouns (refer to 3.6 for detailed illustrations).

46.

/à- kàm /	'prayer'
/à-fò/	'you'
/é- tó/	'tree'
/é-kpè/	'lion'
/i-ni/	'time'
/i-bà/	'two'
/ù-li/	'grave'
/ù-dzài/	'beauty'

In addition, most V syllables are followed by CV syllables as shown in example (47).

47.

/i -mé/	'patience'
/i -fù/	'laziness'
/è-dù/	'behaviour'
/à-mi /	'I'
/ù-kà/	'your mother'

iii. CV Shape.

According to Abercrombie (1967), and Hyman (1985), the CV syllable is the unmarked unit in a language. It is therefore regarded as the universal structure since it occurs in all natural languages. It is equally observed that CV structure is widespread among children from the babbling stage to about five years of age (Akpan 2004). This shape is the basic and most widespread structure of Anaang syllable. It can occur as a word. Monosyllabic verbs (3.5.3) and prepositions (3.5.6) typically have this shape of a syllable in Anaang. There is no restriction on the quality of vowel at this position. All the vowels can occur here.

48.

/mi/	'here'
/kpé/	'judge'
/dá/	'stand'
/bó/	'say'
/bɔ̃/	'collect'
/dù/	'live'
/fá/	'be lazy'

iv. CVC Shape.

This structure is regarded as a closed syllable. Closed syllables are more restricted than open syllables in Anaang. The coda position is limited to only / p t k m n ŋ /. It occurs in the following examples.

49.

/dʒèp/	'spy'
/kɔ̃t/	'grow'
/kút/	'see'
/ bók/	'gather'
/tèm/	'cook'
/ bán/	'sharpen'
/tán/	'talk'

In Anaang CVC syllable shape contrasts with CVVC structure in most cases in the sense that vowel length is contrastive as will be seen later.

v. CVV Shape.

This structure is also regarded as a heavy syllable since it has a branching rhyme in a non-linear representation. -VV here can be vowel sequence or long vowels

50.

/liá/	'kick'
/suà/	'hate'

Identical long vowels are always closed by a consonant. In a situation where -VV occurs in an open syllable, it must be followed by another syllable. In this situation, -VV identical vowels occur dominantly in non-monosyllabic structure as the first syllable of the words in (51) illustrate.

51.

/kpèèné/	'delay'
/kpòòṅó/	'hew down'
/kààmá/	'stir something to mix'
/tòòró/	'praise'
/níímé/	'quench'
/bḳḳrḳ/	'reply'
/fḥḥrḳ/	'fly'

Non identical -VV sequence occur in structures like:

52.

/kói/	'fetch water'
/b ÷i/	'collect'
/kúḳ/	'sing'
/nùà/	'push'
/tié/	'sit'
/míá/	'slap'
/síó/	'remove'

Observe that one of the members of the sequence must be a high vowel, either /i/, /u/.

vi. CVVC Shape.

-VV- here represents either identical vocoids [a: e: i: o: ḳ: ḥ: u:] /aa ee

ii oo ḳḳ ḥḥ uu / or vowel clusters as the following example shows.

53.

/bààk/	'fear'
/tèèm/	'cook (pl)'
/ḳḳiip/	'pinch'

/bòòm/ 'break'

/sɔ̀ɔ̀p/ 'move stealthily'

/fiut/ 'blow out air'

/dʒtùp/ 'flog'

Example (53) represents CVVC syllable with identical-VV-, while (54) illustrates CVVC syllable non-identical with vowel sequence.

54.

/tùàk/ 'hit'

/núék/ 'mash'

/bíét/ 'resemble'

The structure of the Anaang syllable can be represented in a tree diagram as follows:

(55) Tree diagram showing Anaang syllable structure

The tree diagram simply shows sequential illustration of the Anaang syllable and its internal structure. From the above diagram, it could be deduced that the syllable can have one of the following structures:

56. a. A syllabic nasal which must be homorganic with a following segment.
- b. A vowel which is one of /a e i u /
- c. A consonant plus a vowel.
- d. A consonant, vowel and another consonant.
- e. A consonant, vowel and another vowel.

- f. A consonant, vowel and a glide.
- g. A consonant, vowel, another vowel, and a consonant

The syllabic nasal projects directly from the syllable node and constitutes an independent syllable on its own. Anaang consonants are dominated by a 'C' element, Vowels by 'V', syllabic nasals by 'N' and Glides by 'G' following the multiple tier description (Clement & Keyser 1983, Goldsmith 1990). Consonants and vowels including syllabic nasals and glides are gathered on to trees involving a higher level of organization i.e., the syllable, just like the structure above.

1.5 Research Aims and Questions

In recent phonological theories, the syllable is regarded as an important constituent. The syllable is a domain for a number of phonological processes (Kenstowicz 1994). Given the relevance of these processes to the understanding of Anaang phonology, we find it expedient to conduct a research on Anaang syllables with a view to establishing a basis for the description of Anaang phonology. The main aims of this study are to;

- i. find out why Anaang words and morphemes are constrained to take the forms they are and why certain segments are constrained from certain positions of the internal structure of Anaang syllable.
- ii. find out the role of the syllable in the organization of phonological processes in Anaang.
- iii. find out the relationship between the syllable and other phonological constituents of Anaang and to determine whether or not these constituents operate independently of each other.

The questions arising from these aims are:

- i. What is the relevance of Anaang phonotactic constraints to the understanding of the phonology of the language?
- ii. Are most of the phonological processes in Anaang motivated by the need to respect constraints on syllable structure?
- iii. Is it possible for the syllable as a whole and other constituents of the syllable (say the rhyme), including the segments and tones to constitute the locus of a phonological process in Anaang?

1.6 Significance

No complete descriptive study has been carried out on Anaang phonology. Most of the research works on Anaang are centred on comparative/ contrastive studies (Udondatta 1993, Utip 1985, Udoh 1998) and language acquisition studies (Idem 1994). This research work is therefore an invaluable first step contribution towards understanding the major descriptive issues in Anaang phonology.

As a descriptive work on syllable structure, it is a contribution to current phonological theory which processes that phonological processes cannot be characterized linearly by rules but from dynamics of phonological representations in a phonological hierarchy which has the syllable as its domain.

A descriptive work such as this will be of pedagogical importance to language teachers and linguists since it aims at establishing a structural pattern for the Anaang language.

1.7 Methodology

As a descriptive study that is centred on the structure of a particular language, various methods were employed for successful data collection. The primary source of the data is from Ibadan 400 word list. The word list was enlarged to 700 items by the researcher. The word list was given to respondents who actually provided the Anaang equivalent through reading into a tape recorder.

Secondly, data was gathered from short stories, songs, and narratives. These were equally recorded with a tape recorder and used for our analysis. Thirdly, some of the data were based on the researcher's introspection as a native speaker of Anaang. Other sources such as Udoh (1998), Connell (1997), Michael and Obot (2001) were equally used as reference texts for adequate data collection.

Twelve subjects were selected from across the four dialectal groups of Abak (spoken in Abak, Essien Udim and Etim Ekpo), Ikot- Ekpene (spoken in Ikot-Ekpene, and Obot Akara), Ukanafun (spoken in Ukanafun and Oruk Anam) and Ika (spoken in Ika). The informants were mostly adults above thirty years, and, of low level of education. The selection was done through a stratified random sampling technique. The essence of using a lower level of educated subjects was to get the actual Anaang speech form, since these subjects do not have a high level of interaction with other speech communities.

The data was then sorted into groups: lexical and grammatical levels. The

grouping was necessary to aid the researcher in the selection of items for actual interpretation and analyses. In an attempt to describe the structure of Anaang, the data collected was subjected to formal description. The description was based on the structure of the data and of course their functions. The data was presented in sections using the onset-rhyme model of the multi-tiered representation of autosegmental phonology (Goldsmith 1976).

The application of the onset-rhyme model provided insight into the internal structure of the Anaang syllable.

1.8 Scope and Delimitation

This research is designed to cover the phonological structure of Anaang. The points of focus are on the structures of the syllable as they occur in Anaang phonology. The data used for analysis is enlarged to cover phonology, morphology, and syntax interface.

In this chapter, we have provided background information to the language under investigation. This includes the speakers, and the classification of the language. We equally examined the consonants, vowels, tones and the syllable structure of Anaang. This chapter identified several research questions. It presented the aims, and the scope of the study and moved further to discuss the research methodology. In the next chapter, we shall review a number of theories relevant to the analysis of the syllable structure.

CHAPTER TWO

THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS

In the previous chapter, we presented the background information on the study. This chapter aims at building on the background information provided and providing a framework suitable for the discussion and analyses of the data collected. The ideas in this chapter are organized into four sections. These are; phonology, morphology and syntax interface, multi-tiered framework, CV- tier model and onset-rhyme theory.

2.1 Phonology, Morphology, and Syntax Interface

In Anaang as well as many other languages, it can be seen that phonology interacts with syntax on one hand and with morphology on the other hand. In other words, phonology, morphology, and syntax are inter-related. The separation or classification of description into these three levels is for convenience in linguistic analysis. This makes Urua (2007:5) to conclude that syntax and morphology have contributed immensely to the enrichment and better understanding of phonology in natural languages. In subsequent sections, we shall draw data from Anaang to illustrate how phonology interacts with morphology on one hand and with syntax on the other.

2.2 Interaction between Phonology and Morphology in Anaang

Phonology and morphology are intermixed. Morphology serves to create new meaningful combinations of phonological materials (Katamba 1993, Ussishkin 2007), while phonology serves to 'adjust' the result of such combinations of the sound systems of the language (Kager and Zonneveld 1999, Kager et al 1999). At the same time, a set of phonologically adjusted forms constitute the lexical items of the language, which in turn serve as input to word formation rules. For instance, grammatical constructions can be created by the phonological alteration of the vowel. Consider the following data in Anaang.

(1)a.	singular	b. plural	gloss
	/bòm/	/bòòm/	'break'
	/bán/	/báán/	'sharpen'

/tèm/	/tèèm/	'cook'
/tim/	/tiim/	'pound'

The root verbs in example (1) above, change their internal structure through a phonological process of vowel lengthening to mark plurality.

The difference between (a) and (b) lies in length. Set (a) contains single vowels, whereas (b) contains long vowels. Length here performs grammatical function (i.e plural marker). Plural verbs are formed from their singular forms by lengthening the vowel of the word. Word formation here therefore depends on the phonological process of vowel lengthening within a prescribed position in a given domain (word medially).

Another area of interaction between Anaang phonology and morphology is on the use of tone within a syllable. Tone is said to be a phonological feature, but the alternation of tones on the nuclear element of the syllable contributes to the creation of new lexical items as illustrated in example (2).

2	H	
a.	/dóm/	'bite'
	/dép/	'buy'
	L	
	/dèp/	'rain'
	/dòm/	'imitate'
b.	H L	
	/átà/	'a kind of spice'
	/únèn/	'hen'
	LH	
	/átá/	'sixty'
	/únén/	'right'
c.	H H	
	/bɔ́ɔ́ /	'overtake'
	/mínné/	'snob'

LL	
/bɔ̀kɔ̀/	'prepare'
/minnè/	'squeeze'

A process like compensatory lengthening is a source of language enrichment in Anaang as the example in (3) shows.

3. root	gloss	suffix	output	gloss
/dép/	buy	/mé /	/ déémé /	'buy (many things)'
/tóp /	throw	/mó /	/tóómó /	'throw (many things)'
/fɔ̀p/	roast	/mɔ̀ /	/fɔ̀ómɔ̀ /	'roast (many things)'
/tót/	peck	/ŋó /	/tóóŋó /	'remove from peck (reversive)'
/fik /	press	/ŋ é/	/fiŋé /	'lift (reversive)'

This process occurs across morpheme boundary. It involves the deletion of a consonant and subsequent lengthening of a preceding vowel (cf 4.1). Deletion and reassociation processes occur only in verb roots. This shows that a phonological process can be applied to create new words. But this process must occur within a morphologically defined domain (across morpheme boundary or phrasal level in Anaang).

Another area of interaction is in noun derivation from verb

4.	Verb root	gloss	noun
(i).	/má /	'love'	/ímá / 'love'
(ii)	/mé/	'be patient'	/imé / 'patience'
(iii)	/dɔ̀ŋɔ̀ /	'be sick'	/údɔ̀ŋɔ̀/ 'sickness'
(iv)	/síné/	'put on'	/ínsiné / 'wears'
(v)	/nɔ̀ /	'give'	/ènɔ̀ / 'gift'
(vi)	/dép /	'buy'	/údép / 'market'
(vii)	/nék /	'dance'	/únék / 'dance'
(viii)	/dɔ̀ /	'marry'	/ndɔ̀ / 'marriage'

A syllabic segment is prefixed to the verb root to derive a noun in (4) above. In example (4), the difference between nouns and verbs lies in their initial segments.

In the Lowe Cross languages (Essien 1990, Urua 1990), a noun generally begins with a syllabic prefix while a verb begins with a consonant. CV-suffixation is another area where phonology and morphology seem to be intermixed as illustrated in (5).

5. - CV suffixation

(i)	/bénné/	'carry'	/bénnéké/	negation
(ii)	/támmá/	'jump'	/támmáké/	negation
(iii)	/bèèré/	'open'	/bèèréké/	negation
(iv)	/kâ/	'go'	/káàká/	negation
(v)	/lá/	'chew'	/lááká/	negation

In example (5), -CV suffix is affixed to the root verb to perform negative and reversive functions respectively. /ke/ is affixed to disyllabic verb roots while /RV/ is suffixed to open monosyllabic verb roots.

Affixation as a word formation process is severely guided by Anaang phonotactics. Note that in example (5 i-ii), the -CV suffix has a defined structure /ke/. 'V' of the /RV/ suffix is derived through vowel harmony process. In a situation where we have word formation process like borrowing, initial syllabic segment epenthesis is always applied to nativize loanwords. Example

(6) loanwords

	Anaang	English	gloss
(i)	[m̀m̀m̀òtò]	/məutə/	motor
(ii)	[àk̀ b̀ t̀]	/kʌb ə d/	cupboard
(iii)	[àt̀k̀]	/tʃ:k/	chalk
(iv)	[m̀m̀èrì]	/m ə ri/	Mary
(v)	[àk̀f̀ǹ]	/gʌvnə/	governor

Observe that in the English version, all the words start with a consonant. A repair strategy of insertion is applied to derive the Anaang version since all nouns in Anaang must begin with a syllabic segment. (The emphasis here is on the initial segment we ignore the alteration in word medial and final positions). A syllabic nasal

is prefixed to (6i & iv) and a vowel is fixed to (6ii -iii & v). These examples show that morphology, in the sense of word formation helps to enrich the lexicon. Generally, phonology has a wide array of influence on morpheme positions to the extent that phonological wellformedness can determine certain morpheme positions. For instance, reduplication as a word formation process has both morphological and phonological implications. The reduplicated items can be a word or syllable. Example follows.

- | | | | |
|--------|--------|------|-----------|
| 7. (i) | /di | come | /di:di/ |
| (ii) | /tá/ | chew | /ta:tá/ |
| (iii) | /imá/ | love | /imájma/ |
| (iv) | /fèRé/ | run | /fè:fèRé/ |

The data involve both partial and complete reduplication. Monosyllabic words (7 i-ii) undergo complete reduplication process, while disyllabic words (7iii-iv), undergo partial reduplication where only the first syllable is copied to the root. Phonologically, the reduplicant has a fixed pattern. The first syllable is heavy irrespective of the weight unit of the underlying word.

2.1.2 Interaction between Anaang phonology and Syntax

Phonology interacts with syntax in a number of ways. According to Inkelas and Zec (1996) and Truckenbrodt (2007:441) phonological rules operate over syntactic domain to show that constituents in one component (syntax) is relevant to processes in another (phonology), and that constraints that are phonological in nature may be relevant to syntactic processes. This shows that phonological structure is sensitive to syntactic phrase structure (Selkirk 1996, Truckenbrodt 2007).

Phonological processes may require reference to phonological phrasing, and this phrasing is directly designed from syntactic structure of a language, showing that the process in question may make reference to syntax directly. Tone for instance is said to be a phonological feature, but a process like tonal alteration marks grammatical contrast between statements and questions in Anaang as follows.

7. Question formation

- i (a) /**át**èm m̀kpɔ́/ 's/he is cooking'
 (b) /**át**ém m̀kpɔ́/ 'is s/he cooking?'
- ii (a) /**àfèRè** itɔ́k / 'you are running'
 (b) /**àfèRé** itɔ́k / 'are you running?'
- iii. (a) /**átà** m̀kpɔ́ / 's/he is chewing something'
 (b) /**átá** m̀kpɔ́ / 'is s/he chewing something?'
- iv (a) /**ádž**èm imà ñg^wét/ 'you want to complete your studies'
 (b) /**ádž**ém imá ñg^wét/ 'do you want to complete your studies?'

The difference between (7a) and (7b) lies in tonal pattern of the verb (the verbs here are written in bold form). All tones on the verbs are raised to high in (7b) to change the sentence to yes/no question.

Tones in Anaang are equally used to mark the grammatical function of persons, and aspects. Consider the following sentences.

8. Persons

- (i) a. /**á** tèm m̀kpɔ́ / 'he is cooking'
 b. /**à** tèm m̀kpɔ́ / 'you are cooking'
- (ii) a. /**á** dá áli/ 'he will come'
 b. /**à** dá àli/ 'you will come'
- (iii) a. /**á** bèn èkùt ákék étó **át**ɔ́ / 'he carried an axe and hewed down a tree'
 b. /**à** bèn èkùt ákék étó **át**ɔ́ / 'you carried an axe and hewed down a tree'
- (iv) a. /**á** tuà **ádž**ét/ 'he is crying'
 b. /**à** tuà **ádž**ét/ 'you are crying'

In example (8), the bold vowel /a/ is prefixed to the verb to indicate second or third person singular. The contrast here lies in tone. High tone [´] on the prefix indicates third person, whereas the low tone [˘] indicates second person. In other words, a substitution of the high tone with the low tone in (8) marks a grammatical

contrast between second and third persons. (8a) marks third person singular while (8b) marks second person singular. Let us consider yet another set of data.

(9) persons

- | | | |
|----------|-------------------------------|---|
| (i) a. | /é tèm m̀kpɔ́/ | 'they are cooking' |
| | b. /è tèm m̀kpɔ́/ | 'you are cooking' |
| (ii) a. | /é dà èli/ | 'they will come' |
| | b. /è dà èli/ | 'you will come' |
| (iii) a. | /é bèn èkùt èkék étó étɔ́/ | 'they carried an axe and hewed down a tree' |
| | b. /è bèn èkùt èkék étó étɔ́/ | 'you carried an axe and hewed down a tree' |
| (iv) a. | /é tuà ádzét/ | 'they are crying' |
| | b. /è tuà ádzét/ | 'you are crying' |

There is a substitution of /a/ with /e/ in (9) to mark plurality in persons.

Observe that the prefix /e/, marks second and third persons plural. /è/ marks second person, whereas /é/ functions as third person plural. (Detail analysis on persons is presented in section 3.5.2)

Equally, tonal alteration can mark contrast in aspects as example (10) demonstrates.

(10) Aspect

- | | | |
|-----|--------------------|--|
| i | (a) /á tèm m̀kpɔ́/ | 'he is cooking' (progressive) |
| | (b) /â tèm m̀kpɔ́/ | 'he cooked' (completive) |
| ii | (a) /à dzit úsún/ | 'you are locking the door' (progressive) |
| | (b) /ǎ dzit úsún/ | 'you locked the door' (completive) |
| iii | (a) /á fèḂè itɔ́k/ | 'he is running' |
| | (b) /â fèḂè itɔ́k/ | 'he ran' |

High tone on the prefix in (10 a) indicates progressive while the high-low tone marks completive aspect.

Another area where phonology interacts with syntax in Anaang is in focus construction. Two main phonological processes are involved in focus construction in Anaang. These are reduplication and tonal raising. Consider the following imperative sentences

(11) /fèRé # itók/	→	[fèR itók]	'run'
/fèRé # itók/	→	[fè:fèRitók]	'run' (throughout) emphatic
/biné # àpé/	→	[binêpé]	'pursue him'
/biné # àp é/	→	[bĩ:binêp é]	'pursue him' (continuously) emphatic

The first syllable is reduplicated with an alteration of the tonal structure so that L becomes LH. In essence, underlying high tone is placed on the first syllable of the reduplicant to mark emphasis so that the low tone on the initial syllable of the focused element surfaces as low-high sequence. This observation is not constant in all contexts. Detailed explanation of this phenomenon is given in section 3. 6.1.

It can therefore be concluded that an adequate analysis of Anaang phonological structure requires input from both morphology and syntax since they are all intermixed.

2.2 Multi-Tier Analysis

In Standard Generative Phonology, segments were said to be made up of unordered phonological features. These features are binary [$\pm$] in nature. In this situation, the presence of a feature automatically predicts the absence of the other feature. To Goldsmith (1976), binary features were inadequate to account for complex segments like affricates, diphthongs, geminates etc and even for phenomena other than segments like contour tones, nasality, vowel harmony, some of these features spread over more than one segment, and some, like tone and nasality, even survive deletion of a segment that they initially docked on. This, therefore makes room for the formulation of autosegmental theory (Goldsmith 1976). A number of models of the autosegmental representation have been formulated to take care of these various phonological and even some morphological phenomena. These include: multi-tier representation (Goldsmith 1976, 1990), timing- tier (Clements & Keyser 1983) moraic theory (Hyman 1985), and metrical theory (Goldsmith 1990), among others.

Goldsmith claims that phonological representation consists of several tiers, hence the name multi-tiered representation. Central to multi-tier analysis is the claim that features that represent each sound in an utterance are situated on different, independent, or autonomous tiers. A tier can therefore be identified by features found on it, such that we can have tonal and melodic tiers represented as in example (12) below

The tiers are linked by a universal convention called well formedness condition (Goldsmith (1976).

(13) **Well formedness condition**

- (a) Every unit on one level must be associated with at least one unit on every other level.
- (b) Association lines may not cross.

The first condition above has undergone several modifications by various linguists since 1976. The consensus is stated as follows.

(13b) (i) **mapping**

Associate each tone with a vowel mapping from left to right.

(ii) **spreading**

If there are fewer tones than vowels, associate the final tone with all remaining vowels.

(iii) **dumping**

If there are fewer vowels than tones, associate all remaining tones with the final vowel (Ewen & Hulst 2001).

In the light of these principles, Ewen & Hulst present the following illustration from Mende data.

14 (a) **mapping**

b) **spreading**

(c) dumping

The above shows that multi – tier representation permits many – to – one association as in (c) and one –to-many association as in (14b). Contour tones are therefore given adequate representation as in (14c) above, where two tones are mapped to one segment.

The autonomous characteristics of tonal (auto)segment had been the initial motivation for autosegmental analysis. In the Anaang language for instance, when a tone bearing unit (usually a vowel) gets deleted, the tone becomes delinked and subsequently gets relinked to adjacent vowel thereby forming “tonal Cluster” as follows.

- (15) /èté àdʒit/ → [ètè:dʒit] ‘our father’
- /ìbènè úfòk/ → [ìbèñù:fòk] ‘wall’
- /àkò áfèrè/ → [àkò:fèrè] ‘a pot of soup’

This is illustrated in (16)

The different levels in such a hierarchical representation are known as tiers. We can therefore have the syllable tier, timing tier, melody tier, tonal tier etc.

In example (16), the link between the /a/ melody and its timing slot is severed. This is known as delinking shown by dissociation. The /e/ melody is then associated with the vacated timing slot. This is known as relinking or reassociation.

A related advantage of this association comes from a common phonological process of compensatory lengthening introduced in section 4.1. In many languages including Anaang, a loss of the coda consonant leads to the lengthening of the adjacent nucleus element of the syllable. The deletion and subsequent lengthening occur simultaneously rather than being two independently operative processes. We represent the process simply on separate tiers (4.1).

The entire goal of autosegmental analysis involves the reduction of natural phonological processes to changes that can be expressed in minimal autosegmental notation. Its analysis has shifted emphasis from the structure to the organization of phonological representation which is built on the syllable as the core for various phonological components. For instance, vowels, consonants, tones, stress, nasalization, vowel harmony, insertion, lengthening, and deletion processes etc are bound together by the syllable. The theories in support of the syllable include CV-tier

or timing or skeletal model, metrical theory, moraic model, and onset-rhyme theory among others. These theories all agree on the concept of the syllable as the domain for phonological as well as morphological operations, but they differ in some aspects. While syllables are mapped to metrical grid or tree in metrical theory (Goldsmith 1990), others are of the view that syllable node project CV or skeletal tier, or linked directly to onset and rhyme (Clements and Keyser 1983, Ewen and Hulst 2001), or moraic unit (Hyman 1985, McCarthy and Prince 1996). Consider the following representation. For the purpose of this research, we concentrate on CV-tier model and onset-rhyme theory only.

2.2.1 CV-Tier Model

CV-tier which is also referred to as timing tier forms what Clements and Keyser (1983) call "Universal theory of the syllable". CV tier is a component of the syllable representation regardless of its function in the word formation processes. The tier plays a vital role in the organization of the entire phonological structure. It is the anchor point for all the elements on other tiers. Cs and Vs are therefore employed, together with an essentially flat syllable structure which exhibits internal hierarchy as represented in example (18).

C or V slot is always filled with melodic unit. The tier not only defines the timing organization but also takes over the feature 'syllabic'. Syllabic segments are anchored to "V" slot whereas non-syllabic segments are anchored to "C" slots. In other words, Clements and Keyser claim that the units of CV-tier define functional positions (peak versus non-peak) within the syllable. In example (18) for instance, the vowel /i/ is the peak whereas the non-vocalic segments /s/ and /t/ are treated as non-peak elements. Cs and Vs are neither consonants nor vowels but variables belonging to the morphological and phonological representation.

As already stated, CV-tier analysis is regarded as a universal theory of the syllable. The syllable plays a central role in defining segments. All melodic features are mapped into the syllable if they are to be pronounced. In other words, every

segment must be anchored onto a string on the syllable tier or else gets deleted by stray erasure. The CV tier defines functional peak vs non-peak element within a syllable. V element is the peak, while the C element represents the non-peak element. CV model plays a vital role in the analysis of complex segments like diphthongs, long vowels and geminates among others. Complex segments are multiply linked while single segments have one-to-one association on the timing tier. This is illustrated with long and short vowels in example (19) below.

CV-tier equally plays a vital role on deletion or insertion rule on the syllable. Therefore, an important contribution of non-linear CV-tier model has been to offer an approach transcending between deletion/insertion phenomena. For instance, deletion /insertion is a common rule used in Anaang to account for extrasyllabic segments. Extrasyllabic segments are segments that lack skeletal position of their own; they emerge phonetically only when it is supplied a position by epenthesis. Let us consider the example below.

The segments to the right of the arrow are phonetically realized while the initial consonant in (20i-ii) and the final segment in (20iii) (to the left of the arrow) are not realized phonetically. They are regarded as extrasyllabic and as a result become deleted. The deletion of extrasyllabic consonants here is attributed to non-association of the consonants with the timing slot. Extrasyllabic consonants therefore remain floating with respect to the syllable as well as the skeleton or timing slot; as illustrated in (21).

Since the first consonant in (b) is not linked to the skeleton or timing slot, it is regarded as extra syllabic (Clements and Keyser 1983), and therefore is deleted so that we have a representation as in (21c).

(Note however that fricatives are not possible coda element in Anaang and as such cannot be linked). This shows that extrasyllability of consonants following Clements and Keyser has been achieved by directly marking such consonants as exception to syllabification.

The same principle is applied in insertion rule as illustrated in (22).

There is consonant clustering in the underlying representation which is in violation of the Anaang phonotactics. The first segment of the cluster cannot be syllabified because it is extrasyllabic. /s/, which was initially regarded as extrasyllabic consonant, later emerges phonetically after the insertion of a vowel.

2.2.2 Onset-Rhyme Theory

Onset Rhyme theory as the name suggests, is analysed as comprising two immediate constituents: an (O)nset, containing any consonant preceding the vowel, and the (R)hyme containing the vowel and whatever follows it (Ewen and Hulst

2001, Davis 1988, 1990). The syllable node σ dominates the onset and rhyme. The rhyme branches into the nucleus (and the coda), which in turn dominate the segments.

Onset-Rhyme structure

Onset, Nucleus and Coda can therefore dominate the melody tier directly (23) or project to the timing tier, which in turn dominates the segments (24). The onset and rhyme are seen as autonomous units, each with its own constraints. Every syllable must have at least one constituent at the rhyme whereas the onset constituent is optional. A third tier, the timing tier, is incorporated into the onset-rhyme model for the analysis of the internal structure of the syllable. The justification for the utilization of the onset-rhyme model for our analysis is based on Anaang templates especially with regards to the weight unit.

Anaang has a heavy/ light syllable structure. A light syllable does not have a branching rhyme. It has one of CV, V or N structures. Whereas, heavy syllables have branching rhyme with either CVV, CVC, CVVC structure. This is illustrated in (25).

25. /à tá / [V CV] 'sixty' light /light syllables
 /h tán/ [N CVC] 'sand' light/heavy syllables
 /tié/ [CVV] 'sit' heavy syllable
 /tuàk/ [CVVC] 'hit' super heavy syllable

26. a. b. (a) V light syllable
 (b) CV light syllable

- c. d. (c) N light syllable
 (d) CVC heavy syllable

- e. (e) CVV heavy syllable

(f) CVVC super heavy syllable

However, not all languages draw the distinction between light and heavy syllables in the same way. In some languages, it is not only the number of segments in the rhyme, but also the type of segment, which plays a role. In languages like Mongolian & Lardil (Hayes 1989) CVC and CV structures are regarded as light syllable, whereas CVV syllable is heavy. In Anaang CVC & CVV structures constitute heavy syllable. This implies that CVC & CVV have the same weight unit. Therefore, there is no uniformity in weight classification across languages, but there is uniformity for weight criteria for different processes. For instance, compensatory lengthening process (Hayes 1989) shows that the deletion of either final V or C induces re-association of a preceding adjacent vowel through lengthening. Therefore the deletion of a segment in compensatory lengthening process does not affect the weight unit of the syllable. The weight unit is realigned to the adjacent weight bearing segment through spreading (refer to section 4.1 for illustration). Heavy syllables have only two structures in Anaang:

- (i) Syllables with long vowels/vowel clusters.
- (ii) Syllables with closed consonant.

Super heavy syllable on the other hand occurs as a result of an additional weight unit to an open heavy syllable structure. Recall that heavy syllables have CVC and CVV (closed or open) structure. In a situation where the open heavy syllable structure is closed, such a structure becomes super heavy. Example follows.

27. Anaang super heavy syllable

/déeɸ/	CVVC	'scratch'
/ɸtɸk/	CVVC	'bend'
/fùt/	CVVC	'blow'
/sáát/	CVVC	'be dry'
/úfijèèt/	V-CV-CVVC	'idiom'

The syllable, a phonological constituent, can operate within the domain of the word, phrase, or sentence. In other words, the syllable can be established from a hierarchical structure which corresponds to words /sentences motivated among other things by phonological processes which have the syllable as their domain of application. There is therefore the need not to limit the study of the syllable to phonetics/ phonological level but, to the entire level of grammar which involves phonology, morphology, and syntax interface. The fact that consonants and vowels are grouped into a higher hierarchical structure is very important for the development of phonological theory and we shall devote chapter three to investigate the relevance of Anaang syllables and their roles in phonological study.

This chapter covered a review of theoretical framework. It further justified syllable –based theories relevant to the analysis of the data collected.

CHAPTER THREE

ANAANG SYLLABLE STRUCTURE

This chapter will build on the syllable based theories to analyse and discuss the syllable structure of Anaang, its internal structure and phonotactic constraints on the syllable at the levels of phonology, morphology and syntax.

3.1 The Syllable

The syllable is very important in phonological description. The recognition of the syllable in the premise of multi-linear phonology was first introduced by Kahn (1976) in his *Syllable –Based Generalization in English Phonology*. Other works on the syllable include Kenstowicz and Kisserbeth (1979), Hulst and Smith (1982), Selkirk (1982,1984), Goldsmith (1990), Kenstowicz (1994) among others. Diverse definitions have been proposed based on various approaches: most of which are based on phonetic (Turk 1994, Maddieson & Precoda 1992, Abercrombie 1967) and phonological points of view. The essential component in any syllable is the vowel which provides the nucleus of the syllable. The syllable may be preceded or followed by one or more consonants. Our understanding of the syllable in this context shall be on the basis of its functions in a language. We define the syllable as a natural domain for defining phonotactic patterns in a language after Kenstowicz (1994). Phonotactics refers to the limitation on the distribution of sounds at various points (initially, medially, and finally) in a phonological word. The notion of syllable initial, syllable medial and syllable final positions are needed in the theory of phonological rules in order to express generalization about a number of phenomena. In other words, the syllable defines the well-formedness sequence of segments. The segments /o ɔ ʉ / for instance are not possible initial segments in Anaang. Equally, fricatives and affricates are not possible final syllabic segments in Anaang. Therefore, the fricatives in 'essen', 'effiom' are syllabified as /e-sien/ and /e-fiom/ respectively rather than being treated as geminates.

The syllable is a hierarchical structure represented by means of a tree diagram with its internal structure as in example (1).

1. The Syllable Structure

The CV- and segmental tiers are dominated by the syllable node 'σ' which is higher in hierarchical representation than all other tiers. The syllable node projects the onset (O) and rhyme (R). The rhyme projects into nucleus (N) and coda (C), which in turn dominate the CV- tier. The CV- tier acts as an intermediary between syllables and segments. Languages differ with respect to the syllable structure along various dimensions related to the structure in ONC. The difference lies in the inclusion of more or less marginal elements. The syllable defines syllabicity for segments. The vowel constituent is syllabic, whereas the consonants are non-syllabic elements. Tree structure such as in example (1) has been used to indicate membership of a segment in a particular syllabic constituent.

Syllables provide all details of the constituent; their internal organization and their interface with phonological processes. For instance, the pattern of epenthesis, deletion, and other phonological processes in a given language occur within the syllable. Phonological segments that cannot be parsed into syllables are treated as extrasyllabic. Such segments get deleted in the course of phonological derivation. At the same time, insertion rule can be used to repair a syllable to a well formed structure, but the epenthetic segment must conform to the phonotactic statement of that language (cf. section 4.3).

The syllable therefore plays an important role in the understanding of phonological rules and processes internal to a language.

3.2 Internal Structure of the Anaang Syllable

The internal structure of the syllable has received quite a lot of attention in the phonological literature. Languages differ in terms of the internal structure of the syllable. Assignment of segments onto syllable as already observed follows language specific phonotactic rules. For instance, a language like Hua as described by Blevins (1996:217) has only one syllable type: CV. English on the other hand has more syllable types. A language like Hawaiian does not have any coda so that we have words like *honolulu* and *wakiki* syllabified as /ho-no-lu-lu/, /wa-ki-ki/. Therefore, the syllable in Hawaiian is always open (see Spencer 1996) and (Clements 2000). Standard Chinese allows only the nasal /ŋ/ as closed syllable producing structures like /be-i jŋ/, /shoŋ-hai/. English and Polish on the other hand, as presented in Kenstowicz (1994) and Asbby & Maidment (2005), have complex syllable structures. English, for instance, permits $C_{0-3}VC_{0-4}$ structure (i.e maximum of three consonant clusters at the onset and four consonants at the coda), while Polish has $C_{0-4}VC_{0-5}$ structure (maximum of four initial consonant clusters and five syllable final consonants). Nigerian languages like Hausa, Igbo, Yoruba and Urhobo have no coda, (Eyisi 2003). Anaang has a simple (C)V(C) syllable structure with no consonant cluster. Even though the Anaang syllable is said to have a simple syllable structure, there are restrictions that hold for the distribution of segments at the onset, nucleus and coda positions of the syllable. These restrictions are severely guided by the Anaang phonotactics.

This implies that several languages have a way of segmenting words into syllables. Syllabification therefore differs from language to language. Despite these differences, some phonologists have come up with some universal principles of syllabification such as: the principle of maximal differentiation which states that, the segments the segments of syllable constituents (onset and rhymes), have to be maximally different (Oostendorp 1999:62). Other principles include the principle of irregular coda, the principle of maximal onset, minimal coda and principle of open syllable, proposed by Pulgram (1972) as cited in Hyman (1975). Hyman (1975) says the syllable boundary coincides with the word boundary. As a result, constraints that operate at the beginning of a word should be operative at the beginning of a syllable. This principle on syllabification does not fit into Anaang. The principle that holds for the distribution of consonant initial segments at word level cannot hold in totality for

3. *Laundry*

The word has two peaks of sonority and as such, two syllables. The sonority peak is at the nucleus (vowels) and descends towards the margins, as schematized in (3).

Consonant clusters in English can easily be parsed in this order following SSP. The principle of SSP is practicable to some extent in most languages and as such is said to be the basic rule of syllabification. But this rule applies in Anaang with some modifications as illustrated below.

4. Anaang sonority hierarchy

- Vowels
- Syllabic nasals
- Glides
- Liquids
- Nasals
- Obstruents

Therefore, the word 'ñtèmmé' /ñtèmmé/ 'I am not cooking' can be syllabified as [ñ tèm mé] as schematized in (5) below.

The syllabic nasal is sonorous Anaang like the vowel. Syllable boundary falls at the valley of sonority as presented in (example 5). The word has three sonority peaks and as such three syllables. Syllabic nasals rank next in sonority after vowels in Anaang followed by glides, liquids, nasals, obstruents in that order. Syllabic nasals are tone-bearing units and can occur independently in a syllable just like vowels. Details are presented in subsequent sections.

In the non linear framework, syllabification is a simple process. The number of syllabic elements in a word determines the number of syllables within a word except for words with vowel sequence. In other words the first thing is to identify the syllabic elements. In this case, one starts with the assignment of syllabicity or what is known as nucleus formation in onset-rhyme theory. Let us consider the following data.

6. syllabification of intervocalic segment(s)

- | | | | |
|-------|----------------------|------------------------|-----------------------|
| (i) | / èg ^w ù/ | [è-g ^w ù] | ‘ termite ’ |
| (ii) | / ùkpèk/ | [ù-kpèk] | ‘ a variety of fish ’ |
| (iii) | / èkptùn/ | [è-kptùn] | ‘ anus ’ |
| (iv) | / èkpèk/ | [è-kpèk] | ‘ chin ’ |
| (v) | / ibènè/ | [i-bè nè] | ‘ wall ’ |
| (vi) | / m̀bòró/ | [m-bò ró] | ‘ banana ’ |

To parse these words into syllables, the first thing to be considered here is the number of syllabic elements. Each syllabic element projects a syllable head. The syllable head is indicated by N which is dominated by the (R)hyme in most instances.

The next step involves (O)nset formation which associates the intervocalic segment to the left of the syllable head.

This is followed by syllable formation which involves the joining of the nucleus projection to the syllable node and a preceding onset projection if any.

Finally, we adjoin the consonant on the right of the nucleus to the adjacent preceding syllable if any to form a coda.

Based on this, the words in example (8) contain two syllabic segments each, thereby producing two syllables.

- | | | | | |
|--------|---------------------|-----------------------|--------|------------------|
| 8. (i) | /èg ^w ù/ | [è-g ^w ù] | V-CV | 'termite' |
| (ii) | /ùkpèk/ | [ù- kpèk] | C- CVC | 'a kind of fish' |
| (iii) | /èkptìn/ | [è-kptìn] | V -CVC | 'anus' |
| (iv) | /èkpèk/ | [è-kpèk] | V-CVC | 'chin' |

The data in (9) has three syllabic segments each, resulting in three syllables respectively.

- | | | | |
|--------|----------|--------------|-----------|
| 9. (i) | /ìbènè/ | [ì-bè-nè] | V- CV-CV |
| (ii) | /m̀bòró/ | [m̀- bò- ró] | N- CV- CV |

When a consonant occurs between vowels, the consonant is always syllabified as part of the syllable containing the vowel on the right rather than part of the coda of the syllable containing the vowel on the left (Giegerich 1992). In other words, the intervocalic consonant is adjoined to a following vowel to form a V-CV(C) structure.

This assumption cannot be applied to words with intervocalic consonant clusters or geminates. Again, let us consider another set of data.

- | | | |
|---------|-----------------------|------------------------------------|
| 10. (i) | /g ^w àkká/ | 'enter' |
| (ii) | /típpé/ | 'make a hole' |
| (iii) | /bìðmmó/ | 'bring down (load from ones head)' |
| (iv) | /ùdènné/ | 'umbrella' |

(v)	/àtàṅtàng/	'gnats'
(vi)	/àkpámkpáj/	'wheel'
(vii)	*/èfútkèèt/	'sixteen'
(viii)	*/duòpduòp/	'ten by ten'

11.	(i)	/g ^w àkká/	→	[g ^w àk - ká]	CVC-CV
	(ii)	/típpé/	→	[típ - pé]	CVC -CV
	(iii)	/biòm mó/	→	[biòm - mó]	CVVC-CV
	(iv)	/àkpámkpáj/	→	[à - kpám - kpáj]	V-CVC-CVC
	(v)	/àtàṅtàng/	→	[à - tàṅ - tà ṅ]	V-CVC-CVC

When intervocalic consonant clusters occur in Anaang, the syllable boundary is inserted between members of the sequence to separate them into two adjacent syllables. This implies that the initial consonant is parsed as a constituent of a preceding syllable while the second consonant forms the initial segment of a following syllable, so that the resulting structure conforms to the permitted syllable shape of Anaang as presented in example (11).

The process is very simple throughout the derivation. Examples (11iv - v) result in heterosyllabic structure while (11i-iv) are regarded as geminates (Perlmutter 1996).

Again, let us consider the data in 12.

(12)	(i)	èfútkèèt	→	/è fúto kèèt/	→	[è fú ro kèèt]	V	CV	CV	CVVC
	(ii)	duòpduòp	→	/duòbo duòp/	→	[duò ðò duòp]	CVV	CV	CVVC	

The data in (12) has an underlying unpreferred intervocalic consonant cluster. If syllable boundary is inserted between the clusters, the outcome will be an acceptable syllable shape of Anaang. But the word must first be repaired to comply with the phonotactics on possible segment combination in Anaang. As already stated, non-identical consonant sequences other than nasal + consonant are not permissible in Anaang, as this will violate Anaang phonotactics. Therefore, where ill formed sequences occur, vowel insertion rule is applied to parse such sequences in (12) as indicated with the arrow to the right. We shall return to this point in chapter four.

3.3 Constraints

Constraints refer to the phonotactic statements of the syllable. It justifies why certain segments or clusters are not permissible in certain environments in particular languages. There are constraints on coda, nucleus, syllabic nasal, onset and segment length. These will be the focus of discussion in this section.

3.3.1 Onset Constraints in Anaang

Onset acts as the releasing marginal element of the nucleus. An onset element cannot occur without the nucleus in Anaang, but can occur with or without a coda as the following examples show.

CVC structure with coda

- | | | | | |
|-----|------|-----|-------|---------|
| 13. | (i) | tát | /tát/ | 'loose' |
| | (ii) | díp | /díp/ | 'hide' |

14. V-CV-CV structure without coda

- | | | | | |
|-------|---------|-------------|---------|------------|
| (i) | ídará | /i-dá-rá/ | V-CV-CV | 'joy' |
| (ii) | idáRá | /i-dá-Rá/ | V-CV-CV | 'position' |
| (iii) | àkpàkpà | /à-kpà-kpà/ | V-CV-CV | 'corn' |
| (iv) | m'kpási | /m'-kpá-sí/ | N-CV-CV | 'seed' |

This shows that Anaang does not have a VC syllable structure. There are few onsetless syllables in Anaang. Lexical items with syllabic prefix result in onsetless initial syllables but, these syllables acquire onset elements from the consonant of a preceding syllable later on in the course of its derivation thereby becoming a CV structure. Therefore onsetless syllables cannot occur word internally or at the internal position of a phrase or a sentence in Anaang except before a consonant or a syllabic nasal. In other words, pre-vocalic consonants prefer to occupy the syllable onset.

Let us consider the following data.

15. àfö àbèn ífíát átóp áᵀ ébót ág^wòt ábén átá
 you took stone throw hit goat killed carried ate
 you killed a goat with a stone and ate it

The structure of the syllable if presented vertically is as follows.

16.	à-fò	V-CV	'you'
	à-bèn	V-CVC	'carried'
	ì-tiát	V-CVVC	'stone'
	á-tóp	V-CVC	'you threw'
	á-tɔ́	V-CV	'you hit'
	é-bót	V-CVC	'goat'
	á-g ^w òt	V-CVC	'you killed'
	á-bén	V-CVC	'you carried'
	á-tá	V-CV	'you ate'

Observe that all the words in (16) begin with onsetless syllable V, whereas these words become resyllabified to core syllables, CV, in (17), except for the first word. Observe that most of the data in (16) end with a closed syllable structure respectively. But the same data become open at morpheme boundary in (17). The generalization is that syllabification does not take place until all other processes have applied. Anaang syllable therefore favours maximal onset principle where an intervocalic consonant is syllabified as the onset of a following syllable rather than the coda of a preceding syllable except for heterosyllabic consonant sequences. We can therefore conclude that the onsets of a pre-vocalic consonant is obligatory even if a grammatical or word boundary intervenes as example (17) shows.

17. à-fò: b è ní tíá tá tó pá tɔ́ bó tà g^wò tà bé n à tà
 V-CVV CV CV CV CV CV CV CVV CV CV CV CV CV CV CV

There are no clustering possibilities at the onset. Where we have C_1C_2 sequence in a word, two syllables will occur. C_1 is syllabified as the coda of a preceding syllable while C_2 is syllabified as the onset of a following syllable. Example follows.

18.

- (i) àkánkán 'gong'
- (ii) àkpámkpán 'wheel'
- (iii) àtántàn 'gnats'

The example shows word medial NC sequence. The syllable falls between the sequences as follows

19.

(i)	àkàŋkàŋ	/à-kàŋ-kàŋ/	V-CVC-CVC	'gong'
(ii)	àkpámkpáŋ	/à-kpám-kpáŋ/	V-CVC-CVC	'wheel'
(iii)	àtàŋtáŋ	/à-tàŋ-tàŋ/	V-CVC-CVC	'gnats'

For identical consonant sequences, the syllable boundary still falls between the sequences as presented in (20).

20.

(i)	g ^w àkká	/g ^w àk-ká/	CVC-CV	'turn'
(ii)	tippé	/típ-pé/	CVC-CV	'make a hole'
(iii)	àkpámmá	/à-kpám-má/	V-CVC-CV	'broken bottles'
(iv)	biòmmó	/biòm-mó/	CVVC-CV	'off load'
(v)	ùŋ ^w àŋŋá	/ù-ŋ ^w àŋ-ŋ á/	V-CVC-CV	'bleeding'
(vi)	iníŋŋé	/i-níŋ-ŋ é/	V-CVC-CV	'sweetness'
(vi)	ùdènné	/ù-dèn-né/	V-CVC-CV	'umbrella'

In the Lower Cross languages, onset cluster is more pronounced in Efik at both phonemic and phonetic levels as in example (21).

21 Efik onset clusters

- (i) /brě/ 'play'
- (ii) /tjèt/ 'one'
- (iii) /édwàt/ 'spear'
- (iv) /èkprí/ 'small'

Onset clustering is very restricted in Ibibio (Urua 2007). It occurs as a result of certain phonological processes (Urua 2007, Essien 1990). Consider the following data.

22	CVCV	→	CCV
(i)	/fire/	→	[frě] 'forget'
(ii)	/túwá/	→	[twá] 'cry'

There is a deletion of the vowel which of course gives rise to a CCV structure.

Onset cluster here occurs as a result of the deletion of a vowel so that CVCV structure becomes CCV structure. This process applies to very few words in Ibibio. But there are many lexical items in Efik with CC cluster that are not created by any phonological process. This is not the case in Anaang. There is no onset cluster in Anaang. What appears in the written form as clusters are simple unit phonemes /kp, g^w, ŋ^w tʃ, d₃ /

The CV-approach of the autosegmental analysis (cf Clements and Keyser p. 85) enables these segments to be characterized in terms of one-to-many associations between a single element of the CV-tier and a sequence of elements on the segmental tier as illustrated in example (23)

23.

There is a kind of shared feature relationship where these segments are produced with simultaneous application of articulators and there is no blocking in its transition from the first to the second segment following Steriade (1990, 1992:2). Clark and Yallop (1990) refer to this simultaneous application of articulators as coarticulation or double articulation. The description of coarticulation has to contain two terms of place joined by hyphen as illustrated in example (24) below: Note however that the second segment in the cluster harmonises in [$\pm$ voice] with the preceding segment.

24. Place Features

/kp/	labio – velar	e.g.	[kpàn]	‘warn’
/ŋ ^w /	labio – velar	e.g.	[ŋ ^w àn]	‘dry’
/tʃ/	alveo – palatal	e.g.	[tʃé]	‘look’
/d ₃ /	alveo – palatal	e.g.	[d ₃ ét]	‘wash’
/g ^w /	labio – velar	e.g.	[g ^w èt]	‘write’

25. *Manner features*

kp	stop + stop	= stop
ŋ ^w	nasal + approximant	= nasal
g ^w	stop + approximant	= stop
tʃ	stop + fricative	= affricate
d ₃	stop + fricative	= affricate

In any of the above cases, consonant clustering within a syllable (at both surface and underlying levels) is not attainable. The internal structure of Anaang syllable can rightly be analysed as consisting of a simple onset, a complex nucleus, a simple coda, or an independent syllabic nasal.

3.3.2 **Nucleus Constraints in Anaang**

The nucleus is otherwise known as the peak of the syllable. Anaang has either a simple or complex nucleus structure with or without branching tree as presented in example (26) below.

26. The structure of the Anaang nucleus

The structure shows that nucleus anchors an upper limit of two segments.

These segments are:

- (i) pure vowel V_1 which is obligatory as in /dù/ 'be alive'
- (ii) optional long vowels/vowel clusters (V_1V_2) as in /diiip/ 'hide pl', /túá/ 'cry'

All the vowels can occur at V_1 position after a preceding onset. But only /a e i u / can occur as syllabic prefix thereby constituting an independent syllable as presented in (27). The vowels /o ɔ ɰ / are barred from this position as we shall see later.

27.	syllable prefix	
	/à-tà /	'sixty'
	/è- bé /	'husband'
	/è-g "ù/	'termite'
	/i-nùŋ /	'salt'
	/ù-tóm /	'work'

3.3.2.1 Constraints on V_1V_2

3.3.2.1.1 Constraints on Identical V_1V_2

V_1V_2 are lengthened vowels /vowel clusters. There is no identical V_1V_2 segments in Anaang. What obtains is a single vowel with length feature which may be phonologically or morphologically conditioned. Consider the following example. All the vowels can occur as long vowels in V_1V_2 position as presented in (28).

28.		
(i)	/fùm /	'blow'
	/fùùm /	'roam'
(ii)	/kɔ̃k /	'grind'
	/kɔ̃ɔ̃k /	'pile up'
(iii)	/dómó/	'measure'
	/dóómó/	'be heavy'
(iv)	/d ₃ ɛ́t/	'mix'
	/d ₃ ɛ́tí /	'mix (many things)'
(v)	/ním/	'dive'
	/níím/	'absorb'
(vi)	/nám/	'do'
	/náám/	'intoxicate'
(vii)	/dép/	'buy'
	/déép/	'scratch'

The lexical contrast in (28) lies in length.

It should however be noted that there is no direct link between constraints on segment combination in words and the syllable. As a result, constructs that hold for

word initial, medial, or final positions may not necessarily hold for the syllable at the same position. For instance, long vowels occur dominantly in interconsonantal position of a word in Anaang, but can occur with or without a closing consonant in a syllable.

Let us consider the following data.

A	B
29. (i) /míḥ ðḥ ḡ/ # /èdiánḡ/	→ [míḥ: ḡédiá ḡ] N CVV CV CVVC
wing cricket	‘wing of a cricket’
(ii) /ḡkúúm/ # /étó/	→ [ḡkú: métò] N CVV CV CV
nail wood	‘wooden nails’
(iii) /míḥ ðḥ ḡ/	→ [míḥ: ḡ] N CVVC
	‘wing’
(iv) /ḡkúúm/	→ [ḡkú: m] N CVVC
	‘nails’

The long vowels here in (29 i-ii) occur in an open syllable structure but occur in closed syllable structure in (iii-iv). We therefore posit that long vowels can occur in closed syllable if and only if it occupies a syllable final position.

3.3.2.1.2 Constraints on Non-identical Vowel Sequence

In another situation, V_1V_2 can be non-identical vowel sequence. Let us consider the following example.

- 30.
- (i) /túá/ ‘cry’
 - (ii) /tié/ ‘sit’
 - (iii) /dùè/ ‘offend’
 - (iv) /míá/ ‘slap’
 - (v) /síó/ ‘remove’

31

- (i) /ábiḥḡ/ ‘hunger’
- (ii) /inùèn/ ‘bird’
- (iii) /nsèi/ ‘red clay’

- (iv) /m̀kpáì/ 'unripe palm nut'
 (v) /ń̀sɔ̀ì/ 'carved wood'
 (vi) /ń̀súì/ 'antidote'

In example (30 & 31) where we have V₁V₂ sequences, one of the vowels must be a high vowel /i/ or /u/. However if the high vowel occurs in V₂ position, it is restricted to only the high front vowel /i/. /u/ does not occur as V₂ in this context. This generalization is mainly restricted to lexical items. /u/ can occur as V₂ at grammatical or phrasal level. This is presented thus.

- 32 (i) /àkpɔ̀# úbɔ̀k/ [à-kpɔ̀ù-bɔ̀k] V-CVV- CVC 'beads (for wrist)'
 (ii) /ìkpá # úkòt/ [ì-kpáú-kòt] V-CVV- CVC 'shoes'
 (iii) /ìkó # úkɔ̀t/ [ì-kóú-kɔ̀t] V-CVV-CVC 'calabash'
 (iv) /ìni # úkùwɔ̀ / [ì-niú-kù-wɔ̀] V-CV-CV-CVV 'rainy season'
 (v) /èkà# úfɔ̀k/ [è-kàú-fɔ̀k] V-CVV-CVC 'madam'

In all situations, one of the vowels in a cluster must be a high vowel /u/ or /i/ or both /u/ and /i/.

3.3.3 Coda Constraints in Anaang

Anaang, like other Lower Cross Languages, has an upper limit of one optional element at the coda. There is strict restriction on the type of segments permitted as the coda element in Anaang.

Efik and Ibibio permit [p t k m n ŋ j] as the coda element (Essien 1990), whereas Anaang permits only [p t k m n ŋ] as coda. This shows that the coda is very restricted in its segment selection

Coda in Anaang has a kind of transitional characteristic depending on the environment or context. For instance, when a coda occurs before a following onsetless syllable, it becomes resyllabified as the onset of a following syllable as in the initial syllable of (33 i-ii) and the second syllable of (33 iii-iv).

33.
 (i) /tóp/ # /é- tò/ → [tó-βé-tó] 'throw a stick'
 CVC V-CV CV-CV-CV
 (ii) /d̩́ít/ # /ú-súŋ/ → [d̩́í-rú-súŋ] 'lock the door'
 CVC V-CVC CV-CV-CVC

(iii)	/ú-fɔ̃k/ # /i-bɔ̃k/	→	[ú-fɔ̃- Ri -bɔ̃k]	'hospital'
	V-CVC V-CVC		V-CV-CV-CVC	
(iv)	/ń-sùŋ/ # /i-kàŋ/	→	[ń- sù-ŋi-kàŋ]	'smoke'
	N-CVC V-CVC		N-CV-CV-CVC	
(v)	/ŋ-kɔ̃ŋ/ # /ù-bɔ̃ŋ/	→	[ŋ-kɔ̃ -ŋ ú-bɔ̃ŋ]	'vegetable'
	N-CVC V-CVC		N-CV-CV-CVVC	
(vi)	/i-tɔ̃ŋ/ # /é-bòt/	→	[i-tɔ̃-ŋé-bòt]	'goat's neck'
	V-CVC V-CVC		V-CV-CV-CVC	

The crisp captive coda in (33 i-vi) is released. Generally, coda occurs more frequently at a position where it is not followed by any other vocalic element.

If the onsetless syllable is a syllabic nasal, the coda can retain its position as in (34 iv). At the same time if it occurs before a consonant it cannot be resyllabified (34i-iii).

(34) Coda in Anaang

(i)	/à-kán/ # /kán/	→	[à-kán-kán]	'gong'
	V-CVC CVC		V-CVC-CVC	
(ii)	/à-tàn/ # /tàn/	→	[à-tàn-tàn]	'gnats'
	V-CVC CVC		V-CVC-CVC	
(iii)	/dʒàk/ # /nim/	→	[dʒàk- nim]	'keep it down'
	CVC CVC		CVC-CVC	
(iv)	/nám/ # /ń-náj-ŋá/	→	[nám-ń-náj-ŋá]	'work (command)'
	CVC N-CVC-CV		CVC-N-CVC-CV	

The phonological processes that alter strings of segments under the pressure of constraints on syllable shapes may conspire to supply a nucleus or an onset but never a coda. The coda is the only subpart of the syllable that may be eliminated by processes such as deletion, weakening or resyllabification as shall be seen later.

3.3.4 Constraints on Syllabic Nasals

It is impossible to distinguish in segmental terms /m n ŋ/ and their syllabic counterparts. Their contrast lies in their feature specification and their association to consonantal or non-consonantal position.

The following nasals are syllabic in Anaang [m n ŋ]. They occur commonly in word initial prefix before a non syllabic segment. Syllabic nasals are homorganic

with a following segment. This shows that the place feature specification of a syllabic nasal is always determined by the place feature characteristic of a following segment. Example follows.

35.

- (i) /ṃ-kpána / 'bed'
- (ii) /ṃ-bòppó / 'young lady'
- (iii) /ṇ-tɔ̀rɔ̀dɔ̀ / 'cassava'
- (iv) /ṇ-támmá / 'act of jumping'
- (v) /ŋ̣-kùwà únèn / 'eggs'
- (vi) /ŋ̣-kùdikù / 'owl'

Apart from word initial position, there are restricted number of words where syllabic nasals are seen word medially as represented in example (36)

36.

- [ṃ-bùk-ṃ-bùk] N-CVC-N-CVC 'interestingly'
- [ṇ-dáp-ṇ-dáp] N-CVC-N-CVC 'wonderfully'
- [ṃ-bá-ṇ-sáŋ] N-CV-N-CVC 'groundnut'
- [ṃ-kpá-ṇ-tùk] N-CV-N-CVC 'sweet fruit'
- [i-kpá-ṇ-tùtùn] V-CV-N-CVVC 'extreme deafness'

Generally, syllabic nasals bear tones just like vowels; it is classified as [+cons] [+syl]. It is an independent segment in the syllable. Since the syllabic nasal does not co-occur with any other segment in the syllable, it therefore projects directly from the syllable node. This shows that syllabic nasals can neither co-occur with the onset nor rhyme in Anaang. Hence, the need for its representation as an independent node within the structure of the Anaang syllable.

3.3.5 Segment Lengthening

Segment lengthening is a significant phenomenon in Anaang (1.2.2). In this section and the subsequent section, data shall be drawn from Anaang to show the constraints that hold for the distribution of segment length within the syllable.

3.3.6. Vowel Lengthening

Anaang has a total number of seven phonemic vowels. The seven vowels can all be lengthened. Consider the following examples.

37. lexical lengthening

a		b	
(i)	/fùm/ 'blow'	/fùùm/ 'roam'	
(ii)	/kók/ 'grind'	/kókók/ 'pile up'	
(iii)	/dómó/ 'measure'	/dóómó/ 'be heavy'	
(iv)	/d ₃ út/ 'mix'	/d ₃ úút/ 'mix (many things)'	
(v)	/nìm/ 'dive'	/níím/ 'absorb'	
(vi)	/nám/ 'do'	/náám/ 'intoxicate'	
(vii)	/dép/ 'buy'	/déép/ 'scratch'	

The contrast is seen at interconsonantal position only and within a syllable. Vowel lengthening can equally occur as a result of certain morphological processes. Let us consider the following example

38. V CV V CV(C)

- (i) /éí/ # /ìní/
good time
- (ii) /èé/ # /ènǝ/
father proper name
- (iii) /èkà/ # /ád₃én/
mother child
- (iv) /èdù/ # /úg^wém/
manner life

Observe that the first word in the sequence ends with a single vowel. While the second word begins with the same vowel. This gives room to identical V₁#V₂. Complete vowel assimilation process is applied to prevent this type of sequence. V₁ assimilates V₂ at syllable boundary since Anaang phonotactics do not permit dual syllable heads with identical feature specification without an intervening consonant.

The assimilation process here creates long vowels with open syllabic structure. The example in (38) can be syllabified as follows.

39. V CV # V CV(C)	→	V CVV CV(C)	
(i) /éti/ # /ìni/	→	[é-ti: - ni]	'good time'
(ii) /èté/ # /ènɔ̃/	→	[è-té: -nɔ̃]	'Eno's father'
(iii) /èkà/ # /áɗ ₃ én/	→	[è-kā: -ɗ ₃ èn]	'child mother'
(iv) /èdù/ # /úg ^w ém/	→	[è-dū: -g ^w èm]	'way of life'

Generally, long vowels of any type in Anaang are restricted to only one syllable. Syllable boundary therefore poses a serious constraint to long vowels. But this constraint is not applicable to long consonants otherwise known as geminates.

3.3.7 Constraints on Anaang Geminate Consonants

In the previous section we stated that all the vowels in Anaang can be lengthened, whereas only six consonants / p t k m n ŋ / in Anaang can occur as geminates. Example follows.

40.

- (i) /sánná / 'slip off'
- (ii) /ŋ^wàŋŋá / 'pour out'
- (iii) /tɛ̃mmó/ 'get prepared'
- (iv) /kpékké/ 'cut'
- (v) /g^wáppá / 'collect with force'
- (vi) /ɗ₃ùttɔ̃/ 'double'

The intervocalic segments are regarded as geminates or geminated stops as will be seen later. (40i-iii) represent nasal stop geminate consonants while (40iv-vi) represent oral stop geminates. Other consonants cannot undergo this process probably because Anaang phonotactics do not permit segments other than these six consonants as coda.

A simple extension of this constraint accounts for morphological gemination in Anaang. At morpheme boundaries, Anaang allows geminate stops after a vowel and before another vowel V-V. Generally, in Anaang geminates are found in three conditions:

i. within one morpheme as follows;

41.

- (i) /sikké/ 'move slightly'
- (ii) /dàkká/ 'leave'
- (iii) /bàttà/ 'close up'
- (iv) /kpàppá/ 'lift a heavy substance'

ii. as lexical contrast;

42. a

- (i) /sáná/
- be clean

- (ii) /ɲ^wàɲá/
- be bright

- (iii) /t^hmmó/
- take refuge

- (iv) /biné/
- follow

- (v) /bùmmó/
- scramble

- (vi) /ɲ^wáɲá/
- wrapper

b

- /sánná/
- move further

- /ɲ^wàɲá/
- pour out

- /t^hmmó/
- get prepared

- /binné/
- pursue

- /bùmmó/
- initiate

- /ɲ^wáɲá/
- ring

Here total copying of the intervocalic consonant creates geminates which of course contrast with single consonant segments.

iii. created by morphemes whose suffixation produce a geminate as in (43)

- 43.
- (i) /tèm / + /mè / → [tèmmé]
 cook remove (pot) from fire
- (ii) /fúk/ + /kɔ́/ → [fúkkɔ́]
 cover uncover
- (iii) /kɔ́ŋ/ + /ŋɔ́/ → [kɔ́ŋŋɔ́]
 hang on hooks remove from hooks

Phonotactic constraints on the distribution of geminates equally restrict geminates to intervocalic position only. In other words, geminates in Anaang are permissible in a most restricted phonotactic context; where the single versus geminate contrast is maximally perceptible in some cases. This can occur in nasals only as illustrated in examples (44i-vi, xi-xii)

44. single segments		geminates	
(i)	/sána / 'be clean'	/sánna / 'slip off'	
(ii)	/ŋ ^w àŋá/ 'be bright'	/ŋ ^w àŋŋá / 'pour out'	
(iii)	/tɛ́mó/ 'take hold'	/tɛ́mmó/ 'get prepared'	
(iv)	/bìné/ 'follow'	/bìnné / 'pursue'	
(v)	/bùmó/ 'scramble'	/bùmmó/ 'incite'	
(vi)	/ŋŋ ^w ájá/ 'wrapper'	/ŋŋ ^w ájŋá/ 'ring'	
(vii)		/sikké / 'shift'	
(viii)		/dàkká/ 'leave (command)'	
(ix)		/bàttà/ 'close up'	
(x)		/kpàppá/ carry ... with force'	

Examples (44i-vi) present contrastive nasal stop geminates. Whereas no contrast occurs in (44vii-x). This shows that there is no data to demonstrate clear contrast between single oral and geminate oral stop segments in Anaang. The difference between single and geminate consonants following Connell (1991) lies in the fact that geminate consonants are longer in duration than their single consonant counterparts.

3.3.7.2 Consonant Gemination in Anaang

Anaang has a rich consonantal inventory and employs gemination in syntactic and lexically distinctive roles. As stated earlier, geminate consonants can be derived from different morphemes. The phonological process through which this derivation can occur is known as 'gemination'. Gemination is therefore regarded as the process of a single segment becoming geminate (Harris 1999:1). Gemination is a common phonological process in languages. This has been attested for in Shilluk, Ibibio and Efik among others (Gilley 1992, Essien 1990, Urua 2000, Connell 1991). Gemination affects coda consonants. In this case, the geminated³ element of the syllable occurs twice in a succession in such a way that the second half of the segment automatically takes on a harmonizing vowel and acts as the onset of a following syllable. Example follows.

45.	a		b	
(i)	/tèm/	'cook'	/tèmmé/	'bring down ... from fire'
(ii)	/fúk/	'cover'	/fúkk/	'uncover'
(iii)	/kɔ́ŋ/	'hang'	/kɔ́ŋŋ/	'remove ... from the rope'
(iv)	/ń-tèm/	'I am cooking'	/ń-tèmmé/	'I am not cooking'
(v)	/ŋ-kòp/	'I am hearing'	/ŋ-kòppó/	'I am not hearing'
(vi)	/ń-tàŋ/	'I am talking'	/ń-tàŋŋá/	'I am not talking'

The data in (45) is syllabified in (46). Observe that (45a) has (N)CVC structure. The affixation of a -CV suffix to the verb root in (45a) produces (N)CVCCV structure in (45b) which, of course marks grammatical contrast. Negatives and reversives in Anaang are therefore derived by consonant gemination and vowel harmony processes as presented below.

46.	(N)CVC	+ CV	→	(N)CVC CV	
(i)	/tèm/	+ /mé/	→	[tèm mé]	reversive
(ii)	/fúk/	+ /kɔ́/	→	[fúk kɔ́]	"
(iii)	/kɔ́ŋ/	+ /ŋɔ́/	→	[kɔ́ŋ ŋɔ́]	"
(iv)	/ń-tèm/	+ /mé/	→	[ń-tèm mé]	negation
(v)	/ŋ-kòp/	+ /pó/	→	[ŋ-kòp pó]	"
(vi)	/ń-tàŋ/	+ /ŋá/	→	[ń-tàŋ ŋá]	"

The outcome of the affixation process as presented in (46) above is the gemination of the intervocalic consonants. Long vowels and geminates in Anaang cannot co-occur as the data in (47) illustrates.

47a. root

- (i) /siit/ 'block'
- (ii) /fáák/ 'wedge'
- (iii) /kɔ́ɔ́ŋ/ 'hang on hook'

47b. root + CV

- (i) /siit/ + /té/ → /sitté/ 'unblock'
- (ii) /fáák/ + /ká/ → /fákká/ 'remove from ...wedge'
- (iii) /kɔ́ɔ́ŋ/ + /ŋɔ́/ → /kɔ́ŋŋɔ́/ 'remove ...from hanger'

47c. root + NV

- (i) /sitté/ + /ŋé/ → /siíŋé/ 'unblock (pl)'
- (ii) /fákká/ + /ŋá/ → /fááŋá/ 'remove from ...wedge'
- (iii) /kɔ́ŋŋɔ́/ + /ŋɔ́/ → /kɔ́ŋŋɔ́/ 'remove ...from hanger'

The final consonant of the root in (47b) is geminated through CV suffixation. Suffixation here results in vowel shortening. Whereas (47c) involves vowel lengthening and consonant degemination.

3.3.7.3 Special Behaviour of Anaang Geminates

Geminates are said to form a tight bond that resist disruption by phonological rules. This behaviour is known as integrity. Geminates are said to exhibit integrity (Hayes 1986, 1989, Steriade 1988, Goldsmith 1990, Perlmutter 1996, Kenstowicz 1994), where epenthesis fails to split them up (inseparability), and inalterability where rules fail to apply to them except the whole geminate is involved.

Geminates resist separation by an epenthetic vowel that might otherwise be expected in clusters. A vowel is inserted to break impermissible sequences but this rule fails to apply if the application would separate halves of a geminate. In Anaang

for instance, epenthetic vowel applies to break unlike clusters. But this process is not applicable to geminates.

Consider the following examples.

- 48) (i) /dùòpkèèt/ → /dùòpòkèèt/ → [dùòβòkèèt] 'eleven'
 (ii) /èfùtkèèt/ → /èfütòkèèt/ → [èfüròkèèt] 'sixteen'
 (iii) /támmá → */tám á má/ 'jump'
 (iv) /tàγγà → */tàŋ á γà/ 'quarrel'

The point is that medial insertion rule blocks CC clusters. In other words, consonant clusters induces vowel epenthesis. Since the clusters are not geminates, epenthetic vowel is therefore applied to parse the CC clusters (48i-ii), but epenthesis is blocked in (48 iii-iv), owing to the fact that the data are true geminates. For a language like Anaang which exhibits true geminate characteristics, vowel insertion rule will create meaningless words marked asterisks.

Geminates are equally said to have a special behaviour of 'inalterability', where certain processes fail to apply to them. Segment weakening for instance, cannot affect one half of the geminate without affecting the other. Therefore, it is difficult for a feature changing process to change only one half of geminates.

Let us consider the following data:

49.

- (i) / sítte/ 'make a hole' *sítRé
 (ii) / fíkké/ 'stop pressing' *fikRé
 (iii) / fúkkó/ 'uncover' *fúkó

Segment weakening in (49i-iii) would result in ill formed words to the right. Inalterability is exhibited in (46i-iii). At word boundary, intervocalic voiceless stops are expected to be weakened at onset position in Anaang. But the segment in (49i-iii) cannot be weakened since it equally occupies the coda of a following syllable and the onset of a preceding syllable. It should however be noted that coda element in Anaang cannot undergo a process of weakening, therefore intervocalic weakening is blocked. A true geminate is therefore not transparent to weakening as the following example demonstrates.

50.

(i) /tɪppe/ 'make a hole'

(ii) dʒʊttɔ/ 'mix'

(iii) /tʊkkɔ/ 'try'

We can therefore conclude that Anaang geminates are true geminates since they cannot be separated or altered by any phonological rule or process. Again let's consider the data in (51).

51. intervocalic weakening

(i)	/ésit # ibàk/	'wicked heart'	[ésiribàk]
(ii)	/úfɔ̃k # ibɔ̃k /	'hospital'	[úfɔ̃Rɪbɔ̃k]
(iii)	/ídʒiip # ég ^w ót/	'goat's blood'	[ídʒiβég ^w òt]
(iv)	/dibé/	'hide'	[diβé]

The final stops of the initial stem in (51i-iv) are weakened to their homorganic approximants respectively at intervocalic position since they are non-geminates.

Overall, the syllable appears to be successful as the basic phonological unit. Constraints on syllable structure appear to account for distribution of geminates. Constraints on segment distribution do not permit geminate initial or final segments in Anaang. They must occur in intervocalic environment.

Adequate attention has been devoted to the discussion and the analyses of the constraints on the internal structure of the Anaang syllable. In what follows, our concentration shall be on the constraints on lexical formation as these affect the structure of the Anaang syllable.

3.4 Anaang Syllable Structure and Lexical Innovations

The basic questions considered here are; how does a phonological variant that has never existed previously in a speech community come into use? And what is the effect of these innovations on the syllable structure of the affected language?

Innovation mechanisms proposed by Alderete and Frisch (2007), and Bermúdez-Otero (2007) involve failures of coordination. The listener does not parse the segments in a way that the speaker intended. Innovation, following Bermúdez-Otero (2007), evolves in four stages; phonologization, stabilization, morphologization and lexicalization. Phonologization involves the addition of a new phonological

either of the pair can be used depending on the speakers choice.

When languages adopt loanwords, they typically modify the new items in keeping with the pre-existing structure of the recipient language (Campbell 1998). In other words, loanwords are modified to fit into the phonological as well as the morphological structures of the recipient language. One of the ways of achieving this is by adaptation. Adaptation involves the replacement of a foreign sound (which is absent in the recipient language with the nearest phonetic equivalent to it in the recipient language. For instance the sound /θ/ in the English word 'thousand' /θaʊznd/, is replaced with Anaang /t/ /atausin/, since /t/ and /θ/ share same phonetic similarity in place feature and voicelessness. Where adaptation is impossible, deletion or insertion rule is applied to modify such words.

3.4.1.1 Anaang – English Loanwords

Loanwords constitute the most common ground for lexical innovation in Anaang. They are known as innovations which cannot be accounted for in terms of inheritance and which share a resemblance with the lexical items of the donor language. It comes into existence in order to fill a gap that appeared as a result of the inability of a language to capture all aspects of the culture of the speakers (Jowitt 1991). Newman (2000), in a comparative study of African languages, reveals that it is difficult to determine the true avenue of loanwords in certain contexts. This analogy is not applicable to Anaang. It is very easy for one to determine the true sources of borrowed items in Anaang especially when dealing with unrelated languages.

Loanwords are more widespread in Anaang adjective and noun classes. Let us consider the following nouns borrowed from English. The embolden segments are the segments that are introduced by vowel epenthesis, to repair the loan items into Anaang.

52. Anaang -English loanwords

	English source	syllable structure	Anaang	syllable structure	tonal pattern	
(i)	/məʊtə/	CVCV	[m ^ˈ mótò]	N-CV-CV	L-H-L	motor
(ii)	/məʃɪn/	CVCVC	[m ^ˈ máʃɪn]	N-CV-CVC	L-L-H-L	machine
(iii)	/beɪsɪn/	CVCC	[ábésɪn]	V-CV-CVC	L-H-L	basin

(iv)	/blæŋkit/	CCVC-CVC	[àbàláŋkit]	V-CV-CVC-CVC	L-L-H-L	blanket
(v)	/pòli:s/	CV-CVC	[àbòlisi]	V-CV-CV-CV	L-L-H-L	police
(vi)	/gla:s/	CCVC	[àkàlási]	V-CV-CV-CV	L-L-H-L	glass
(vii)	/spírit/	CCV-CVC	[àsibilit]	V-CV-CV-CVC	L-L-H-L	spirit
(viii)	/θauznd/	CVCCC	[àtáúsin]	V-CVV-CVC	L-HH-L	thousand
(ix)	/tʃɔ:k/	CVCC	[àtʃ ɔ:k]	V-CVC	L-HL	chalk
(x)	/dʒɔ n/	CVC	[àdʒ ɔ n]	V-CVC	L-HL	john
(xi)	/endʒin/	VCCVC	[núdʒin]	N-CVC	H-L	engine
(xii)	/endʒiniə/	VCCVCV	[núdʒ inià]	N-CV-CVV	H-L-HL	engineer

The bold segments are the segments that are inserted into the borrowed words to repair them to the syllable structure of the Anaang nouns.

The data present typical examples of Anaang loan items from English source. Several processes are employed here to repair these items into Anaang. These are insertion, otherwise known as epenthesis (Schane 1973, Spencer 1996), deletion, assimilation, segment modification, adaptation (Matthews 1991) resyllabification, and tonal placement, as will be discussed shortly.

3.4.1.2 Analyses

In this section, we are going to present the analyses of the various processes adopted for the repair of Anaang loanwords. In our analyses, examples shall be drawn from the data in (52) throughout our discussion of borrowed words with the addition of other words where necessary.

3.4.1.2.1 Vowel Insertion processes

Insertion is one of the processes adopted to modify the structure of loanwords to comply with the Anaang syllable structure. Epenthetic vowels can be introduced at word initial, medial, and final positions. In the items in example (52), it can be observed that an initial insertion rule is used in all the items when borrowed into Anaang to comply with Anaang noun class structure since nouns in Anaang start with a syllabic element. Epenthetic rule is equally applied word medially to separate consonant clusters because Anaang does not permit consonant clusters. Final vowel insertion rule is applied to prevent certain segments from occurring at word final position. Details are presented in the subsequent sections.

3.4.1.2.2 Word Initial Insertion Process

Observe that the loanwords belong to the noun items. Nouns in Anaang do not have non-initial syllabic segment, therefore initial syllabic prefix is employed to repair the English loan items into Anaang. Prefixation process here is applied to modify the borrowed items to fit into the morphological structure of Anaang. There is a uniformity in the prefixation process: words with initial oral consonant take on a vowel prefix /a/, whereas a syllabic nasal is prefixed to items with initial nasal segment.

53. Prefixation

English		Anaang		
i) /beɪsn/	CVCC	[à-bésin]	V-CV-CVC	'basin'
(ii) /blæŋkit/	CCVC-CVC	[à-bàlŋkit]	V-CV-CVC-CVC	'blanket'
(iii) /pəli:s/	CVC-VC	[à-bò-lí:-sì]	V-CV-CV	'police'
(iv) /glɑ:s/	CCVC	[à-kàlá:sì]	V-CV-CV	'glass'
(v) /spɪrɪt/	CCV-CVC	[à-sì-bì-lit]	V-CV-CVC	'spirit'
(vi) /θauznd/	CVCCC	[à-táú-sin]	V-CVV-CVC	'thousand'
(vii) /tʃɔ:k/	CVCC	[à-tʃɔ:k]	V-CVC	'chalk'
(viii) /dʒɒn/	CVC	[àdʒɒn]	V-CVC	'john'

There is a syllabic vowel affixed to all the items in Anaang whereas the English source has an initial consonant segment. The prefixed segment is always predictable. If the initial segment of the source language is an oral consonant other than /l, r/, the low vowel /a/ is prefixed to the loan items as seen in example (53). Generally, the low vowel /a/, occurs more frequently as a syllabic prefix in loan items and even in the production of lexically similar items in related languages of the Lower Cross where the lexical items begin with one of /o, ɔ/ since these vowels are not possible initial segments in Anaang. Example follows.

54. Efik/Ibibio	Anaang	
(i) /òkón/	[àkón]	'night'
(ii) /òbót/	[àbót]	'creator'
(iii) /òkpókóró/	[àkpókóró]	'table'

(iv) /ɔ́kɔ́/ [àkɔ́] 'fence'

In another instance, /u/ rather than /a/ is prefixed to the base.

55. /u/ prefix

English		Anaang		
(i)	/reidiəu/ CVCVV	[ùrádiò]	V-CV-CVV	'radio'
(ii)	/rais/ CVC	[ùlási]	V-CV-CV	'rice'
(iii)	/reit/ CVC	[ùrét]	V-CVC	'rate'

/u/ is inserted before a following /l,r/, whereas other oral consonants take on the /a/ prefix.

If the loan item has an initial nasal consonant segment, a syllabic nasal is prefixed as follows.

56. syllabic nasal prefix

English		Anaang		
(i)	/məutə/ CVCV	/m̩mótò/	NCVCV	'motor'
(ii)	/məʃin/ CVCVC	/m̩məʃin/	NCVCVC	'machine'
(iii)	/meri/ CVCV	/m̩mèri/	NCVCV	'mary'

The syllabic nasal copies the feature specification of the initial consonant of the base completely as in the initial segment of (56). This generalization does not hold for words with initial VC or VN-structure. Let us consider the following data.

57	English	Anaang		gloss
(i)	/endʒin/ VC-CVC	[ú-dʒin]	N-CVC	'engine'
(ii)	/endʒiniə/ VC-CVCV	[ú-dʒi-nià]	N-CV-CVV	'engineer'
(iii)	/envələup/ VCCVCV	[ŋ-fé-lòp]	N-CV-CVC	'envelope'
(iv)	/iŋk/ VCC	[ŋ-kí]	N-CV	'ink'
(v)	/ŋɡlɪʃ/ VC-CCVC	[ŋ-kí-ri-si]	N-CV-CV-CV	'English'

There is an alteration of the syllable at the initial position of the items in (57) even though the words all have an initial (vocalic) syllabic segment. The reason is that Anaang has no VC syllable structure. If the structure of the word is adopted without repair, it will violate onset constraints, which states that a syllable cannot be closed by a coda (consonant) if it does not have an onset element. (Details are presented as follows).

a. vowel initial segment is deleted leaving behind the nasal consonant so that we have structure such as in (58).

58.

- | | | |
|-------|------------------------|-----------|
| (i) | /nd ₃ in/ | CCVC |
| (ii) | /nd ₃ iniâ/ | CCV-CVV |
| (iii) | /nfélòp/ | CCV-CVC |
| (iv) | /ŋkɪ/ | CCV |
| (v) | /ŋkirisɪ/ | CCV-CV-CV |

The effect of this deletion is the formation of initial CC sequences.

b. Since Anaang syllable does not have nouns with initial consonant segment, the initial syllable is further repaired to comply with Anaang phonotactics. Where a consonant is preceded by an initial nasal segment word initially, the nasal always manifest as [+syllabic]. Based on this, the initial nasal in (58) takes on [+syllabic] feature respectively to manifests as syllabic nasals as presented in example (59)

59.

- | | | |
|-------|--------------------------|------------|
| (i) | [ń-d ₃ in] | N-CVC |
| (ii) | [ń-d ₃ ɪ-niâ] | N-CV CVV |
| (iii) | [m _ɲ -fé-lòp] | N-CV-CVC |
| (iv) | [ŋ-kɪ] | N-CV |
| (v) | [ŋ-kɪ-ri-sɪ] | N-CV CV CV |

Recall that syllabic nasals on their own can constitute independent syllable structure in Anaang. Therefore the structure of the initial syllable now becomes N

while the adjacent following consonant forms the initial segment of the second syllable of the loanword.

3.4.1.2.3 Word Final Insertion Process

Epenthetic vowel is inserted word finally if the loan items end in a consonant other than one of /p k t m n ŋ/.

Let us consider the data in (60).

60.	English	Anaang	gloss
(i)	/maɪkəl/	[m̩maɪkədè]	Michael
(ii)	/saɪəns/	[àsáínsi]	science
(iii)	/dʒeɪmz/	[àdʒémsi]	James
(iv)	/saɪləs/	[àsálási]	Silas
(v)	/ælis/	[àdìsi]	Alice
(vi)	/dʒɔːdʒ/	[àdʒɔːdʒi]	Gorge
(vii)	/lʌv/	[àdɔːfù]	Love

The high vowel is inserted syllable finally in (60) after a sibilant irrespective of the feature specification of a preceding vowel. Whereas non-sibilants copy the vowel feature of a preceding segment (60i). The vowel /i/ is affixed to items in (60ii-vi), while /u/ is added to (60 vii). The choice between rounded and unrounded vowel alternation is borne out of the fact that the lips are wide spread in the production of fricative /s/ and the affricate /dʒ/. Whereas, lip spreading is reduced to a kind of narrowed space which approximates to lip rounding, in the articulation of /f/. Therefore rounded high vowel is added to a preceding /f/ while unrounded high vowel is inserted after a final /s/ or /dʒ/. Recall that Anaang phonotactics do not permit segments other than voiceless stops or nasals at word/syllable final position hence the need for final vowel insertion. Sibilants and liquids are not possible word final segments in Anaang, as a result cannot constitute the closing elements of a syllable.

3.4.1.2.4 Syllable Medial Insertion Process

Medial insertion rule is applied to parse consonant clusters as follows.

61.	English	Anaang	clusters	inserted segments	gloss
(i)	/swetə(r)/	[àsibétà]	/sw/	/i/	sweater
(ii)	/skelitn/	[àsikélétèn]	/sk/	/i/	skeleton
(iii)	/kla:k/	[àkàlak]	/kl/	/a/	clerk
(iv)	/wenzdi/	[àwénésidè]	/nzd/	/e/, /i/	wednesday
(v)	/ɪŋgliʃ/	[ɲ'kirisì]	/gl/	/i/	English

Items (i-iii) involve words with initial consonant clusters. While items (iv-v) involve consonant clusters at word medial position. In (i-iii) a vowel is inserted to parse the initial consonant clusters. The feature specification of the inserted segment is predictable. The epenthetic segment copies the feature of an adjacent segment to the right or to the left if there is no preceding vocalic segment.

Observe that;

/i/ is inserted to parse /sw/ cluster in (i).

/i/ epenthesis is applied in (ii) to parse /sk/ cluster.

/i/ is equally used in (v) to parse /gl/ cluster.

(iv) involves the insertion of more than one vocalic segment. /e/ and /i/ are applied to parse triconsonantal clusters in (iv).

The pattern of epenthesis here is equally predictable just like in word final position. Where one of the clusters is a sibilant, the vowel /i/ is inserted to parse such clusters. Whereas others involve a copy of an adjacent vowel to parse the clusters. Generally, medial and final insertion processes involve progressive vowel copying in an environment of non-sibilants.

The tones borne by the inserted loan items are fixed for segment initial and final positions. Apart from syllabic nasal epenthesis, all the inserted segments carry low tone.

3.4.1.2.5 Loanwords and Segment Deletion Processes

Deletion here affects both consonant and vowel segments.

3.4.1.2.5.1 Consonant Deletion

Consonant deletion in this context takes place mainly to repair the loan items to correspond to the structure of the Anaang syllable. Therefore, where we have consonant clusters, deletion rule is applied to parse such clusters where epenthesis is impossible. Let us consider the following items.

62. English	Anaang	deleted segments	gloss
(i) /θaʊznd/	CVCCC [ã-táú-sìn]	V-CVV-CVC /d/ C ₃	thousand
(ii) /bæŋk/	CVCC [ã-bâŋ]	V-CVC /k/ C ₂	bank
(iii) /bærəks/	CV-CVCC [ã-bá-rák]	V-CV-CVC /s/ C ₂	barracks
(iii) /peɪnt/	CVCC [ã-bên]	V-CVC /t/ C ₂	paint
(iv) /pʌmp/	CVCC [ã-bõm]	V-CVC /p/ C ₂	pump
(v) /sɪmənt/	CV-CVCC [ã-sè-mén]	V-CV-CVC /t/ C ₂	cement

The above data has a cluster of C₁C₂ as the coda element.

Deletion affects C₂ in (ii-v). Generally, if the two segments in the cluster are possible coda elements, deletion will affect C₂ as shown in (ii-v). Consonant deletion is only possible at syllable final position in Anaang. Where the clusters occur in a position other than syllable final position, insertion rule is used to separate such clusters as in words like; /ákàlási/ 'glass' /asɪbilit/ 'spirit' where a vowel is inserted to parse /gl/ and /sp/ respectively.

3.4.1.2.5.2 Vowel Deletion

Vowel deletion is not commonly employed in the repair of loanwords. This is in tune with the preservative principle of loanwords which states that segments in the source language should be maximally preserved (Paradis, 1995). However, in a situation, where phonological adaptation requires more than a certain number of changes, certain segments of the source language can be deleted. Let us repeat the data in (59) for our discussion here.

63.	English		Anaang		
(i)	/en-vələʊp/	VC-CVCV	[n̩-fě-lòp]	N-CV-CVC	'envelope'
(ii)	/iŋk/	VCC	[ŋ̩-ki]	N-CV	'ink'
(iii)	/iŋ-gliʃ/	VC-CCVC	[ŋ̩-ki-ri-si]	N-CV-CV-CV	'English'

In the source language, there is an initial VC syllable structure. The V of the VC is deleted in conformity to Anaang syllable structure which does not permit any coda without an onset. The initial vowel of the loan items is deleted while a syllabic feature is added to the nasal that constitutes an independent syllable structure.

3.4.1.2.6 Adaptation

Under normal circumstances, Anaang phonotactics do not permit consonant sequences other than a nasal and a following consonant. This notion is modified in the examples such as the following.

64.	English	Anaang	gloss
(i)	/tʃæptə/	[ətʃáptà]	'chapter'
(ii)	/bæptizəm/	[àbàptisim]	'baptism'
(iii)	/kəʊtist/	[àkàtkísi]	'catechist'
(iv)	/dɒktə(r)/	[àdɔ́kt ɔ́]	'doctor'
(v)	/kəmˈpjʊ:tə(r)/	[à kɔ́mpútà]	'computer'
(vi)	/kæptɪn/	[àkápɛ̀n]	'captain'

Apart from initial vowel prefix, the consonants are allowed to remain the way they appeared in the source language without any alteration. An analysis of the structure of the word shows that representation such as this violates the constraint on segment combination into words without violating the constraints on the structure of the syllable of such items. Observe that the structures are made up of the following consonant sequences.

65.		
(i)	/ətʃáptà/	/pt/
(ii)	/àbàptisim/	/pt/
(iii)	/àkápɛ̀n/	/pt/

- (iv) /əkàtkísi/ /tk/
 (iv) /àdɔ́kt ɔ́/ /kt/
 (vi) /əkɔ́mpútà/ /mp/

Apart from (v) all others produce a sequence of two stops, which is rare in Anaang.

Syllabification rule states that a syllable boundary should be inserted between two consonants to prevent consonant clusters in Anaang. Following this rule, if we insert a syllable boundary between the stops, it will produce the following structures.

66. syllabification

- (i) /à-tʃá**p**-tà/ V-CVC- CV
 (ii) /à- bà**p**-tí- sìm/ V-CVC-CV-CVC
 (iii) /à-ká**p**-tèn/ V-CVC-CVC
 (iv) /à-kàt-kí-sì/ V-CVC-CV-CV
 (v) /à-dɔ́**k**-t ɔ́/ V-CVC-CV
 (vi) /à-kɔ́**m**-pú-tà/ CV-CVC-CV-CV

The initial stop in each of the sequences is a possible syllable final segment while the second segment is a possible syllable initial segment. Based on this, these structures are therefore adapted into the target language without any modification of the consonant sequences.

It should however be noted that words that do not undergo complete repair process in Anaang such as above, are those words that are rather represented with circumlocution since they do not have one word calques in Anaang as example (67) shows. Historically, such words represented educated speakers intuition, which have become fossilized and actually adopted by that native speakers as arbitrary Anaang words without modification.

67.	Anaang	gloss	description	meaning
(i)	/àtʃáptà/	'chapter'	ig ^w uo ηg ^w et	the head of a book
(ii)	/àbàptísim/	'baptism'	mbɛR ɔ́ ke ηη ^w ɔ́k	immersion
(iii)	/əkàtkísi/	'catechist'	akpeep mkpɔ́ ufɔ́Rabasi	one who teaches in the church
(iv)	/à dɔ́k t ɔ́/	'doctor'	abia ibɔ́k mbakara	English medicine specialist
(v)	/əkáptèn /	'captain'	atie itak ubom	the director of the canoe

Sometimes the spelling remains the way it appears in the source language, with slight modification in pronunciations. Example follows.

68. English	Anaang	gloss
(i) /baɪbl/	[abaɪbulu]	bible
(ii) /sa:m/	[asa:m]	psalm
(iii) /vaɪn/	[afain]	vine
(iv) /eksreɪ/	[ekseare]	X-ray

Ukut (1996) refers to this phenomenon as complete borrowing.

3.4.1.2.7 Segmental Alterations

In the previous sections, we demonstrated the changes affecting the syllable and morpheme structures of the loanwords through the process of segment deletion, assimilation, or insertion. These changes occur mainly to make the loanwords to conform to the constraints on syllabification and of course the syllable organization of Anaang. In what follows, we shall discuss segmental alterations as they occur in Anaang loanwords. These include consonantal and vocalic alterations.

3.4.1.2.7.1 Vowel Alteration

Vowel alteration occurs as a result of the variation in the number and feature specifications between the vowels of the source and recipient languages. The result of these variations leads to the substitution of one vowel in the source language with another vowel in the recipient language. Let us consider the following data.

69. English	Anaang		altered segments	gloss
(i) /fræŋk/	[âfâráŋ]	/æ/	→ [a]	frank
(ii) /kæmfə/	[âkómft̪]	/æ/	→ [t̪]	camphor
(iii) /pʌmp/	[âb̥m]	/ʌ/	→ [ɔ]	pump
(iv) /taʊn/	[âtân]	/au/	→ [a]	town
(v) /reɪdiəʊ/	[ûrediò]	/əʊ/	→ [o]	radio

The reason for the alteration is that Anaang has a fewer number of vowel inventory compared to the English language. What happens is a replacement of all English vowels with approximate phonetic vowel features of Anaang where variations occur.

Details of the alteration are as follows.

a. The low vowel /æ/ is absent in Anaang, it is realized as the Anaang equivalent [a] as shown below.

70.	English	Anaang			gloss
(i)	/fræŋk/	[áfáráŋ]	/æ/	→	[a] frank
(ii)	/kæmfə/	[àkámfɛ]	/æ/	→	[a] camphor
(ii)	/bæŋk/	[ábâŋ]	/æ/	→	[a] bank
(iii)	/mæŋg əu/	[mímáŋkò]	/æ/	→	[a] mango

b. The central vowel /ʌ/ does not occur in Anaang. Therefore /ʌ/ in loanwords is substituted with Anaang [ɔ].

Example

71.	English	Anaang			gloss
(i)	/pʌmp/	[ápɔ̂m]	/ʌ/	→	[ɔ] pump
(ii)	/gʌvnə/	[àkɔ́fúnɔ̂]	/ʌ/	→	[ɔ] governor
(iii)	/klʌp/	[àkɔ́lɔ̂p]	/ʌ/	→	[ɔ] club
(iv)	/kʌp/	[àkɔ́p]	/ʌ/	→	[ɔ] cup
(v)	/drʌm/	[àdúrɔ̂m]	/ʌ/	→	[ɔ] drum
(vi)	/kʌmfət/	[àkɔ́mfɔ̂t]	/ʌ/	→	[ɔ] comfort

c. The central vowel /ə/ is not present in Anaang therefore, syllables with /ə/ are realized as one of [o a e ɔ] as illustrated in (72)

72.	English	Anaang			gloss
(i)	/kəmiʃnə/	[àk.ɔ́mí síɔ̂nà]	/ə/	→	[a] commissioner
(ii)	/kɒmən/	[àkɔ́mɔ̂n]	/ə/	→	[ɔ] common
(iii)	/məʊtə/	[mímótò]	/ə/	→	[o] motor

(iv)	/kəmjuːniən/	[əkɔ̃ muniɔ̃n]	/ə/ →	[ɔ̃]	communion
(v)	/məri/	[miməri]	/ə/ →	[e]	Mary
(vi)	/kɔːrəs/	[əkɔ̃rɔ̃si]	/ə/ →	[ɔ̃]	chorus

The choice of what vowel to be substituted with is determined by the English spelling form of the word, the English vowels are produced the way they are written by Anaang speakers and thereby transferred to Anaang with some kind of approximation to the English version where there is similarity in the two languages. This is borne out of the fact that there is no remarkable difference between the written form of Anaang and the spoken form especially in vowel representation.

d. Other vowels like /ɪ ʊ ɜ/ are substituted with Anaang /i u e/ respectively.

73.	English	Anaang			gloss
(i)	/ʃʊgə/	[ʃúkà]	/ʊ/ →	[u]	sugar
(ii)	/pɪn/	[âbîn]	/ɪ/ →	[i]	pin
(iii)	/kɒfi/	[əkɔ̃fi]	/ɪ/ →	[i]	coffee
(iv)	/kɜːtʃɪf/	[ɲkèsí]	/ɜ/ →	[e]	ker-chief
(v)	/skɜːt/	[àsikét]	/ɜ/ →	[e]	skirt
(vi)	/mɜːsi/	[mmèsí]	/ɜ/ →	[e]	mercy

The reduced or short vowels in English are substituted with full vowel equivalents in Anaang since there is no reduced or short vowels in Anaang.

e. Anaang does not have diphthongs but single vowels or vowel clusters within a syllable. Therefore English diphthongs are replaced with single vowel equivalence in Anaang loanwords as follows.

74. /ei/ is substituted with /e/

	English	Anaang			gloss
(i)	/beɪsn/	[âbésin]	/ei/ →	[e]	basin
(ii)	/seɪtn/	[àsétàn]	/ei/ →	[e]	Satan

(iii)	/mædʒɪstreɪt/	[m̩mædʒɪsɪteret]	/ei/	→	[e]	magistrate
(iv)	/steɪdiəm/	[àsɪtédi ð̩m]	/ei/	→	[e]	stadium
(v)	/dʒeɪmz/	àdʒémsɪ	/ei/	→	[e]	James

f. /i ə/ is substituted with /i e/ or /ia/ so that we have;

75.

- (i) [àbíé] for /biə(r)/ /iə/ → /ie/ 'beer'
 (ii) [údz iníà] for /endʒiniə/ /iə/ → /ia/ 'engineer'

g. /u ə/ is replaced with /ɔ/ so that we have [in] ɔ ran] for /ɪnʃuəns/ 'insurance',
 [à t̩] for /tuə(r)/ 'tour'

h. /əʊ/ is replaced with /o/ as in (76)

76.	English	Annang	alteration		gloss
(i)	/təʊl/	[t̩]	/əʊ/	→	[o] toll
(ii)	/stəʊv/	[àsɪtófù]	/əʊ/	→	[o] stove
(iii)	/mæŋg əʊ/	[m̩máj̩kò]	/əʊ/	→	[o] mango
(iv)	/k əʊk əʊ/	[àkókò]	/əʊ/	→	[o] cocoa
(v)	/t əmat əʊ/	[àtòmátò]	/əʊ/	→	[o] tomato

3.4.1.2.7.2 Consonant Alteration

We have seen that loanwords must take into consideration the phonetic feature specifications of the segments of the recipient language. Consider the data in (77)

77.	English	Anaang	altered segments		gloss
(i)	/junivɜsɪtɪ/	[àjùnifésítɪ]	/v/	→	[f] university
(ii)	/sigəret/	[àsikàlèt]	/r/	→	[l] cigarette
(iii)	/gʌm/	[àkɔ̩m]	/g/	→	[k] gum
(iv)	/pɪtə(r)/	[àbíta]	/p/	→	[b] peter
(v)	/prɒfɪt/	[àbɔ̩r ɔ̩fèt]	/p/	→	[b] prophet

(vi)	/rəʊz/	[ʊdósl]	/z/	→	[s]	rose
(vii)	/isθə/	[àsita]	/θ/	→	[t]	esther
(viii)	/bærɪstə(r)/	[àbádístà]	/r/	→	[r]	barrister
(ix)	/raɪs/	[ùlɔ́si]	/r/	→	[l]	rice
(x)	/kɑ:d/	[àkâ :t]	/d/	→	[t]	card

The reason for alterations such as above can be attributed to the variations in the consonant inventory in the two languages as follows.

a. The voiced fricatives /v/ and /z/ are absent in Anaang. These segments become devoiced when adapted into Anaang so that /v/ → [f]

/junivɜsiət/ → [ájùnífésítí]
 while /z/ → [s] /rəʊz/ → [ʊdósi]

b. /t/ and /s/ are in free variation in Anaang. In this case /t/ can be realized as [s] or [t] /tɔ́/ → [átósi]

c. The dental fricative /θ/ is substituted with the stop [t]. The stop shares the same state of the glottis and place feature specification with the fricative.

/θaʊznd/ → [átáusin] /θ/ → [t]

d. /r/ is substituted with one of [r, l, d] /sigəret/ → [àsikafèt] /r/ → [r]

/bærɪstə(r)/ → [àbádístà] /r/ → [d]

[r, l, d] are in free variation in Anaang. Therefore loan items with /r/ can be substituted with any of these since Anaang does not have /r/

e. The bilabial /p/ does not occur syllable initially or as an intervocalic element in Anaang except as geminate. On this basis, the English initial and the intervocalic segment, /p/, undergoes a process of voicing where /p/ → [b]

78. /peɪnt/ → [àbên] /p/ → [b]

/pʌmp/ → [àbɔ́m] /p/ → [b]

/spɪrɪt/ → [àsibilit] /p/ → [b]

f. On the other hand, the voiced counterpart becomes devoiced syllable finally, since voiced stops cannot occur at syllable final position in Anaang so that

/d/ → [t] /ka:d/ → [âkât]

g. The voiced stop /g/ is absent in Anaang therefore, loanwords with /g/ are realized as devoiced [k] since the voiceless counterpart is present in Anaang.

/gAm/ → [âkôm] /g/ → [k] generally, segmental alterations occur as a result of contrast between the two languages. As observed by Steriade (2007:143), speakers' judgments of identity and distinctiveness are rendered at the lexical level: listeners perceive speech sounds in terms of the grid provided by the lexical alphabet of the languages they speak.

3.4.1.2.8 Tonal Placement

Another area of modification is in the use of pitch. Anaang is said to be a tonal language where tone is placed on every syllable just like other Lower Cross languages (Williamson and Blench 2000). Observe that English on the other hand uses stress as presented in example (79).

79. English	Anaang	tone	gloss
(i) /`kofɪ/	[â-kô-fî]	L-L-H	coffee
(ii) /treɪn/	[â-tè-rên]	L-L-HL	train
(iii) /`kɔrəs/	[â-kô-rô-sî]	L-H-L-L	chorus
(iv) /ki-tʃɪni/	[â-ki-sin]	L H L	kitchen
(v) /`prai-mri/	[â-ba-dí-ma-rî]	L-L-H-L-L	primary
(vi) /títʃə/	[â-ti-sà]	L-H-L	teacher
(vii) /sɪŋ-glet/	[a-síŋ-ki-nî]	L-H-L-L	singlet
(viii) /flut/	[a-fù-rût]	L-H-HL	flute
(ix) /kraɪst/	[â-kà-rái-sî]	L-LH-H-L	Christ
(x) /`kris-məs/	[a-k-idísi-mô-sî]	L-L-H-L-L-L	Christmas
(xi) /prɪn-səpl/	[a-bi-lin-si-bà]	L- L- H- L- L	principal

Every syllable in Anaang has at least one tone. In English, stress occurs on different syllables in ways that are somewhat perceptible. In contrast to the nature of tones, (Ladefoged 1993, 2001, Grabe & Warren 1995) stressed sounds are those sounds in which the speaker expends more muscular energy. Two types of stress are placed on the English source: primary and secondary stress. The secondary stress is not marked. Analyses on stress pattern reveal that primary stress is more prominent than secondary stress (Beckman 1986, Haraguchi 1991, Zech 2007). The difference between the two languages lies in the fact that; in English, only one syllable per word may carry primary stress in the case of disyllabic word, whereas all syllables in Anaang carry the same strength (Udoh 1998) since there is no reduced vowel in Anaang. This shows that all tones in Anaang are produced with the same strength.

3.4.1.2.9 Syllable Structure Alteration

Another area of alteration manifests in the structure of the syllable as the following examples show.

80. English	syllable structure	Anaang	syllable structure
(i) /təul/	CVVC	[à-tó-wèt]	CV-CV
(ii) /eindʒəl/	VCCVC	[n-dʒé-lè]	N-CV-CV
(iii) /greis/	CCVC	[àkírísí]	V-CV-CV-CV
(iv) /swetə/	CCVCV	[àsiwétà]	V-CV-CV-CV
(v) /kəmpleint/	CVC-CCVC	[àkòmbèrèn]	V-CVC-CV-CVC

Observe that there is no monosyllabic structure in the Anaang borrowed items in (80)⁵, whereas the source language has quite a large number of monosyllabic structures. The reason behind the difference lies in the fact that the data in (80) are adopted from nouns only. Nouns in Anaang have a minimum structure of two syllables including the syllabic prefix. Therefore loanwords such as presented in (80) are restructured to comply with the minimum acceptable shape of the structure of Anaang nouns. Secondly, the English examples have structures with initial

consonantal or vocalic segment. Whereas all the items in Anaang take on syllabic elements word initially since all nouns in Anaang must have a syllabic prefix.

3.4.1.2 Anaang – Igbo Loanwords

As earlier stated, loanwords exist in a language owing to languages in contact. Anaang and Igbo share the same geographical boundary. This makes it possible for certain Igbo words to be adapted into Anaang. Let us consider the following words.

76. Igbo	Anaang	gloss
(i) /òkìrikà/	[àkìrikà]	second hand materials
(ii) /òkpòrókó/	[ákpòrókó]	stockfish
(iii) /òbìòmá/	[ábìòmá]	mobile tailor
(iv) / ùtázi/	[ùtási]	a kind of bitter leaf

Items (i-iii) begin with /o/ in Igbo. These are replaced with /a/ owing to the fact that Anaang does not have words with syllable initial /o/.

In (iv) Igbo /z/ is replaced with /s/ in Anaang because /z/ is absent in Anaang. The relevance of this illustration is that even when Anaang adapts loanwords from a Nigerian language, the words must be repaired to suit the structure of the Anaang syllable.

All the data used for our illustration indicate that nouns in Anaang all have initial syllabic segments. Therefore, a syllabic prefix is inserted to repair all loanwords with non-initial syllabic structures into Anaang. In a situation where such modification is impossible, deletion rule is used to delete such a segment to avoid the violation of the constraints on syllabification. Generally deletion/insertion rules are applied to prevent illicit clusters or any other unacceptable structure of the syllable in Anaang.

3.6 Morphologically Complex Words in Anaang

In the previous sections, we concentrated on the effects of lexical innovations on the internal structure of the Anaang syllable. This section will however present, analyse and discuss the internal structure of complex morphological words in Anaang which occur as a result of word formation or productive processes including derivation such as affixation. Our concentration is on the morphological structures of

nouns, verbs, adverbs, pronouns, prepositions and adjectives, the derivational processes and the internal structures.

The Anaang word class can easily be identified by the structure of the syllable. The word class include; nouns, verbs, adverbs, pronouns, prepositions and adjectives.

3.6.1 Nouns

Nouns in this research work are classified into phonological and morphological forms.

Phonologically, nouns in Anaang begin with a syllabic nasal or a vowel as represented in example (82).

82.

- (i) /úkót/ 'leg'
- (ii) /èlèm/ 'bag'
- (iii) /ímá/ 'love'
- (iv) /áfùm/ 'wind'
- (v) /ífúút/ 'breeze'
- (vi) /áféré/ 'soup'
- (vii) /mbót/ 'boil'
- (viii) /ńlǎŋ/ 'maggot'
- (ix) /ńŋà/ 'garden egg'

Morphologically, a noun begins with a syllabic prefix. This form of noun is derived from the verb as presented in example (83).

83. Verbs		nouns	
(i) /kuǎ/	'sing'	/íkúǎ/	'song'
(ii) /tém/	'clear the bush'	/ntém/	'bush clearing'
(iii) /kpá/	'die'	/m̀kpá/	'death'
(iv) /dǎ/	'marry'	/ndǎ/	'marriage'
(v) /ŋ ^w ǎŋ/	'drink'	/ŋŋ ^w ǎǎŋ/	'water'
(vi) /nǎ/	'give'	/ènǎ/	'gift'

A vowel prefix are substituted with a nasal in some cases to inflect for numbers results. This occurs in words like:

84	Singular		Plural
(i)	/á!bɔ́ɔ́ŋ/	'chief'	/m!bɔ́ɔ́ŋ/
(ii)	/ábià/	'specialist'	/m̀bià/
(iii)	/àkúkú/	'priest'	/ŋkúkú/

Observe that the plural form has a syllabic nasal prefix while the singular form has a vowel prefix initial syllable. At the same time, a phonological modification of the vowel of the base form of the noun is applied to mark plurality as in example (85).

85.	singular		plural
(i)	/m̀bíimé/	'question'	/m̀bíimé/
(ii)	/ńsíné/	'attire'	/ńsiiné/
(iii)	/ŋkúnó/	'wrapper'	/ŋkúuńó/

The syllable structure of nouns in Anaang can be of any length but there is no monosyllabic noun structure. Therefore, the basic syllables of nouns in Anaang can be represented as [V-CV, V-CV-CV, V-CVC, CVC]. Again, let us consider the following example.

86.		
(i)	/m̀kpútàɔ́útàk /	'centipede'
(ii)	/m̀kpufíó̀bùfiòp/	'butterfly'
(iii)	/ńsíkpàrikpa/	'tadpole'
(iv)	/àtúfò̀búfòp/	'dragon fly'
(v)	/ŋkúkúmm̀kpɔ́ɔ́ɔ́ríɔ́ɔ́/	'locust'

These nouns are not derived from any source. Examples (i-iv) have five syllables each. Whereas (v) has seven syllables. Observe that there is a common feature that cuts across the data in (86) even though they vary in the number of syllables. There is a kind of partial reduplication of the antepenultimate syllable. This reduplicated structure is separated by the penultimate syllable. This type of

reduplication cannot be accounted for in word formation process because it is impossible to cut, separate any of the syllables as the base, root, or affix. There is no record on the derivational history of nouns with this type of structure the history has been lost.

Generally whatever purpose a noun performs in Anaang, the structure of the initial syllable must be a syllabic element; either V or N.

3.6.2 Structure of the Anaang Pronouns

Generally pronouns are said to function as the subject or object of a sentence. They are equally used in indicating possessive function as will be seen shortly.

3.6.2.1. Subject Pronoun

- | | | |
|---------------|-------|--------------------------|
| 87. (i) /àmì/ | V CV | ‘first person singular’ |
| (ii) /áfò/ | V CV | ‘second person singular’ |
| (iii) /àjé/ | V CV | ‘third person singular’ |
| (iv) /àdʒìt/ | VCVC | ‘first person plural’ |
| (v) /àjìn/ | V CVC | ‘second person plural’ |
| (vi) /àmô/ | V CV | ‘third person plural’ |

The personal singular marker at the subject position all have initial syllabic structure just like the plural marker.

The subject pronoun can be dropped in a stretch of speech without affecting the meaning of the word but, this is realised on the verb as a syllabic prefix in the following example.

- | | | |
|------------------------|-------------------------|------------|
| 88. (i) àfò àkèré dié? | ‘what is your name?’ | àkèré dié? |
| (ii) àmì ñkèré dié ? | ‘ what is my name?’ | ñkèré dié? |
| (iii) àjé àkèré dié ? | ‘what is his name?’ | àkèré dié? |
| (iv) àjìn èkèré dié? | ‘what are your names?’ | èkèré dié? |
| (v) àdʒìt ikèré dié? | ‘what are our names?’ | ikèré dié? |
| (vi) àmô èkèré dié? | ‘what are their names?’ | ékèré dié? |

The syllabic prefix which occurs before the verb is a concord marker which indicates persons. In all the examples, subject pronouns in Anaang have a maximum of two syllables.

3.6.2.2 Object Pronoun

89.

- | | | | |
|-------|---------|-------|--------------------------|
| (i) | /ɲièn/ | CVVC | 'first person singular' |
| (ii) | /fièn/ | CVVC | 'second person singular' |
| (iii) | /àɲé/ | V-CV | 'third person singular' |
| (iv) | /dʒidè/ | CV-CV | 'first person plural' |
| (v) | /ɲinè/ | CV-CV | 'second person plural' |
| (vi) | /mémɔ̃/ | CV-CV | 'third person plural' |

Apart from the third person singular marker, pronouns in object position have an initial non-syllabic segment. This shows that the plural marker at the object position has two syllables except for the first and second person singular.

3.6.2.3 Possessive Pronoun

90.

- | | | | |
|-------|---------|------|--------------------------|
| (i) | /âmi/ | V-CV | 'first person singular' |
| (ii) | /âfò/ | V-CV | 'second person singular' |
| (iii) | /àɲé/ | V-CV | 'third person singular' |
| (iv) | /âdʒit/ | V-CV | 'first person plural' |
| (v) | /àɲin/ | V-CV | 'second person plural' |
| (vi) | /âmɔ̃/ | V-CV | 'third person plural' |

The syllable structure of the possessive pronoun is disyllabic. Pronouns here have initial syllabic segment just like those in the subject position.

Even though pronouns are said to be used in place of nouns, it can be seen that they do not have the same structure as nouns. All nouns in Anaang must have an initial syllabic segment. The structures of Anaang pronoun vary according to their functions. Therefore, pronouns in Anaang can either have an initial syllabic or non-syllabic initial segment.

The difference between (93a) and (93b) lies in the fact that the subject of the sentence is present in (a) but absent in (b). Equally observe that -V suffix which functions as verbal extension is affixed to the verb in (b). This suffix hereby relates to the subject of the sentence just like the reflexive pronoun. The affix is derived by vowel harmony process. There is a kind of intervocalic consonant weakening if the root verb is closed by a voiceless oral stop segment.

3.6.3 Anaang Verb Structure

Anaang verb has an inflection considerably more complex than any other category like in most African languages (Criessels et al 2008). The categorical distinction between nouns and verbs is usually evident in syllable distribution, tonal as well as formal morphological grounds.

All verbs in Anaang begin with a consonantal element as presented in examples (94-97).

94. CV(V) structure

- (i) /dí/ 'come'
- (ii) /bó/ 'say'
- (iii) /kaá/ 'go'
- (iv) /náá/ 'lie down'

95. CV(V)C structure

- (i) /tóp/ 'throw'
- (ii) /bén/ 'carry'
- (iii) /sùàn/ 'scatter'
- (iv) /kpécép/ 'teach'

96. CVVC(V) structure

- (i) /dáára/ 'rejoice'
- (ii) /bɔ̀rɔ̀/ 'answer'
- (iii) /nɔ̀nɔ̀/ 'spoon feed'
- (iv) /kéép/ 'wink'

97. CVC(C)V structure

- | | | |
|-------|---------|---------|
| (i) | /sàǵá/ | 'walk' |
| (ii) | /tòbó/ | 'tie' |
| (iii) | /siné/ | 'wear' |
| (iv) | /tèmmé/ | 'guide' |
| (v) | /kánná/ | 'turn' |
| (vi) | /bénné/ | 'carry' |
| (vii) | /támmá/ | 'jump' |

The examples above present various structures of the Anaang verb. Basically Anaang verb is either monosyllabic or disyllabic. These basic syllable structures can be extended through reduplication process or affixation to perform various grammatical functions. In other words, additional structures of the verb can be created from these basic forms through affixation or reduplication processes.

3.6.3.1 Verbal Reduplication

The processes involved in verbal reduplication in Anaang is similar to Ibibio as presented by Essien (1990), Urua (1990)

Verbs in this context are reduplicated to intensify meaning or to place emphasis on the action. In other words, reduplicated forms represent actions which are repeated, processes which are prolonged and states which are enduring (Egbokhare 1990:83). For the purpose of this research work, five different structures of the verb root shall be considered. These are: CV(V), CVC, CVCV, CVVC(V) and CVCCV.

3.6.3.1.1 CV(V) Structure

The CV(V) verb root undergoes a complete reduplication process thereby giving rise to CV(V)CV structure as presented below.

98.

- | | | | | |
|-------|-------|--------|----------|--------------------|
| (i) | /dí/ | —————▶ | [dí:dí] | 'come (emphatic)' |
| (ii) | /táá/ | —————▶ | [ta'tá] | 'chew intensively' |
| (iii) | /bó/ | —————▶ | [bó:bó] | 'say emphatically' |

(iv) /kàá/	→	[kǎ:ká]	'go intensively'
(v) /nàá/	→	[nǎ:nà]	'lie down (emphatic)'
(vi) /kǎ/	→	[kǎ:kǎ]	'fish intensively'
(vii) /nǎ/	→	[nǎ:nǎ]	'give intensively'

The initial syllable of the reduplicant is heavy irrespective of the weight unit of the verb base. When an item is reduplicated in Anaang, the initial syllable must necessarily be heavy.

3.6.3.1.2 CVC Structure

99.

(i) /tóp/	→	[tó:tóp]	'throw intensively'
(ii) /bén/	→	[bé:bén]	'carry (emphatic)'
(iii) /kǎ/	→	[kǎ:kǎ]	'cough intensively'
(iv) /nǎ/	→	[nǎ:nǎ]	'keep (emphatic)'
(v) /nǎ/	→	[nǎ:nǎ]	'dive intensively'
(vi) /màn/	→	[mǎ:màn]	'born'

CVC structure undergoes a partial reduplication process. The closing element of the syllable of the verb root is dropped thereby making the initial syllable of the reduplicant to become open. The generalization is that reduplication process copies only CV structure of the syllable (Urua 1990). Therefore if the syllable of the root verb was initially closed, the coda will become deleted leaving the first syllable with an open structure.

3.6.3.1.3 CVVC(V) Structure

100.

(i) /sùàn/	→	[sùásuàn]	'scatter intensively'
(ii) /kpéép/	→	[kpé:kpéép]	'teach' intensively'
(iii) /dáára/	→	[dá:dáára]	'rejoice intensively'
(iv) /bǎǎ/	→	[bǎ:bǎǎ]	'reply (emphatic)'
(v) /nǎǎ/	→	[nǎ:nǎǎ]	'spoon-feed intensively'

In CVVCV verb structure, the initial syllable of the root is copied thereby expanding the syllable of the verb to CVV CVVCV. But the reduplication of CVVC involves the deletion of the coda element of the root verb. This is in line with the principle of open syllabicity, which posits that the initial syllable of reduplicated verbs must necessarily be open. We shall consider another example involving disyllabic verb root in subsequent sections.

3.6.3.1.4 CVCV Structure

101.

(i)	/díbé/	→	[di:díbé]	‘hide (emphatic)’
(ii)	/sùḂḂ/	→	[sù:sùḂḂ]	preserve (emphatic)’
(iii)	/sàḡá/	→	[sǎ:sàḡá]	‘walk (emphatic)’
(iv)	/tóbó/	→	[tó:tóbó]	‘tie intensively’
(v)	/síné/	→	[si:síné]	‘wear’ (emphatic)’

Where the root verb has a CVCV structure, the initial syllable of the base is copied leaving out the second syllable. But in a CVCCV, where the initial syllable is closed by a coda as in example (102), the coda of the initial syllable of the base has to be dropped before reduplication.

3.6.3.1.5 CVCCV Structure

103.

(i)	/tèmmé/	→	[tè:tèmmé]	‘guide intensively’
(ii)	/kpékké/	→	[kpé:kpékké]	‘cut intensively’
(iii)	/kánná/	→	[ká:kánná]	‘turn intensively’
(iv)	/bénné/	→	[bé: bénné]	‘carry (emphatic)’
(v)	/támmá/	→	[tá: támmá]	‘jump intensively’

It can be observed that there is a uniform principle guiding verbal reduplication. In partial reduplication, the initial syllable of the reduplicant is made heavy through a process of vowel lengthening irrespective of the weight unit of the initial syllable of the root verb.

Secondly, there is a fixed tonal pattern for the reduplicated verb. The initial syllable of the verb must have a high tone. In this situation, where the root verb had an initial low tone, it takes on an additional high tone thereby forming a low-high tone. This shows that the initial syllable structure must have either a high tone or a low-high tonal structure.

3.6.3.2 Contrastive Verbal Reduplication

Verbal reduplication can be separated by a CV interfix, which acts as a negative marker. Example follows.

3.6.3.2.1 CV(V) Base

104.

- | | | |
|-------|-----------------|----------------------------|
| (i) | a. /dī/ | 'come' |
| | b. /dīdī/ | 'come (emphatic)' |
| | c. /ń-dīíRédí/ | 'I am not even coming' |
| (ii) | a. /tá/ | 'chew' |
| | b. / taátá/ | 'chew intensively' |
| | c. /ń-tááBátá/ | 'I am not even chewing' |
| (iii) | a. /bó/ | 'say' |
| | b. / bóóbó/ | 'say emphatically' |
| | c. /m- bóóBóbó/ | 'I am not even saying' |
| (iv) | a. /kàá/ | 'go' |
| | b. /kàáká/ | 'go intensively' |
| | c. /ń-kááBáká/ | 'I am not even going' |
| (v) | a. /nàá/ | 'lie down' |
| | b. /nàánà/ | 'lie down (emphatic)' |
| | c. /ń-nàáBánà/ | 'I am not even lying down' |
| (vi) | a. /kḵ/ | 'fish' |
| | b. /kḵkḵ/ | 'fish intensively' |
| | c. /ń-kḵBḵkḵ/ | 'I am not even fishing' |
| (vii) | a. /nḵ/ | 'give' |
| | b. /nḵnḵ/ | 'give intensively' |
| | c. /ń-nḵBḵnḵ/ | 'I am not even giving' |

The examples in (104c) above are cases of contrastive verbal reduplication.

- a. is the stem
- b. represents complete reduplication of the base.
- c. demonstrates CV affixation between the base and the reduplicant.

RV affix is inserted between the base and the reduplicant since the root verb has no closing consonant or coda. The affix functions as a contrastive marker thereby negating the action of the reduplicated form. Apart from the monosyllabic verb root with open structure of the syllable, other structures can undergo contrastive reduplication process.

3.6.3.2.2 CVC Base

105.

- (i) a. /fúk/ 'cover'
- b. /fú:fúk/ 'cover not otherwise'
- c. /m'-fúkkófúk/ 'I am not covering...'

- (ii) a. /wáj/ 'wrap'
- b. /wá:wáj/ 'wrap intensively'
- c. /ŋ'-wájŋáwáj/ 'I am not wrapping'

- (iii) a. /sín/ 'put'
- b. /sí:sín/ 'put repeatedly'
- c. /ń-sínnésín/ 'I am not putting'

- (iv) a. /wák/ 'tear'
- b. /wǎ:wák/ 'tear continuously'
- c. /ŋ'-wákkáwák/ 'I am not tearing'

- (v) a. /džát/ 'crown'
- b. /džǎ:džát/ 'crown intensively'
- c. /ń-džáttádžát/ 'I am not crowning'

- (vi) a. /búúŋ/ 'break'
 b. /búúbúúŋ/ 'break continuously'
 c. /ní-búúŋǎbúúŋ / 'I am not breaking'
- (vii) a. /wèt/ 'write'
 b. /wě:wèt/ 'write intensively'
 c. /íj-wèttéwèt/ 'I am not writing'
- (viii) a. /kún/ 'wrap'
 b. /kú:kún/ 'wrap intensively'
 c. /íj-kúnnókún/ 'I am not wrapping'

a. is the verb root

b. consists of a copy of the CV structure of the verb root plus the verb root

c. involves complete reduplication of the base which is separated by a CV contrastive affix.

Unlike CV(V) base form which takes on RV affix, the feature specification of the CV affix here changes according to the final segment of the verb root. In this situation, /C/ copies the last consonant of the root while /V/ harmonises with the vowel as indicated earlier. Let us consider contrastive reduplication with disyllabic verb root.

3.6.3.2.3 CVCV Verb Base

106. (i) a. /díbé/ 'hide'
 b. /dí:díbé/ 'hide continuously'
 c. /ń-díbékédíbé/ 'I am not hiding'
- (ii) a. /súúǎ/ 'preserve'
 b. /sú :súúǎ / 'preserve (not other wise)'
 c. /ń-súúǎ késúúǎ/ 'I am not even preserving'
- (iii) a. /sàŋá/ 'walk'
 b. /sǎ:sàŋá/ 'walk intensively'
 c. /ń-sàŋákésàŋá/ 'I am not walking'
- (iv) a. /tóbó/ 'tie'
 b. /tó:tóbó/ 'tie intensively'
 c. /ń-tóbókétóbó/ 'I am not even tying'

- (v) a. /síné/ 'wear'
 b. /sí:síné/ 'wear continuously'
 c. /ñ-sínékésiné/ 'I am not even wearing'

The data in (106) involves a disyllabic verb root.

There is a marked difference in the type of affix added to the verb here.

Observe that contrastive reduplication is produced by total reduplication of the verb root.

Unlike monosyllabic verb root, /ke/ is affixed to all the verb to marks contrast.

The entire verb stem and the contrastive suffix is attached to the copied structure.

Secondly, the affix has a fixed pattern where /ke/ is inserted to separate the reduplicant from the roots. Formal analysis of contrastive reduplication is postponed to section (4.8)

3.6.3.3 Verbal Suffixes

Three types of verbal suffixes shall be presented in this section. These are -V suffix, -CV suffix and -CVCV suffix.

3.6.3.3.1 -V Suffix

107.

- | | | | | |
|--------|---------|---------|---------|---------------------|
| (i) | /fúk/ | 'cover' | [fúkú] | 'cover oneself' |
| (ii) | /wáj/ | 'wrap' | [wájá] | 'wrap oneself' |
| (iii) | /sín/ | 'wear' | [síné] | 'wear (reflexive)' |
| (iv) | /wák/ | 'tear' | [wáká] | 'tear yourself' |
| (v) | /džát/ | 'crown' | [džárá] | 'crown yourself' |
| (vi) | /bítíj/ | 'break' | [bítíj] | 'break yourself' |
| (vii) | /wèt/ | 'write' | [wèré] | 'write on yourself' |
| (viii) | /kún/ | 'wrap' | [kúnó] | 'wrap oneself' |

A look at the data shows that :

-V suffixation here has reflexive meaning.

-V suffixation is derived through vowel harmony process.

Suffixation gives room to intervocalic consonant.

As is the case with all intervocalic stop consonants in Anaang, the final consonant of the verb root becomes weakened to its homorganic continuants or tap respectively, if it is closed by a voiceless stop segment so that /t/ → [r], while /k/ → [ʁ] after suffixation.

Observe equally that the suffix combines with the final segment of the stem to form a second syllable.

The syllable structure of the root that was initially closed by a consonant becomes open after suffixation since the coda of the root verb is released to the onset of a following syllable.

The vowel of the suffix takes on a high tone irrespective of the tonal structure of the root vowel (cf 107 iv, v, viii)

3.6.3.3.2 -CV Suffix

Early analysis shows that a -CV suffix is affixed to a verb root to perform certain grammatical functions like reversive, reflexive, negation etc. (Urua 1990).

108.

(i)	/tèm/	cook	[tèmmé]	bring down ... from fire'	(reversive)
(ii)	/ɲùk/	bend	[ɲùkk ɔ́]	'bend down'	
(iii)	/mín/	frown	[mínné]	'frown at someone'	
(iv)	/bén/	carry	[bénné]	'carry'	
(v)	/fík/	press	[fikké]	'relieve'	(reversive)
(vi)	/fùk/	cover	[fùkk ɔ́]	'uncover'	(reversive)
(vii)	/siit/	seal	[sítte]	'remove seal'	(reversive)
(viii)	/líp/	conceal	[líppé]	'expose'	(reversive)
(ix)	/wáj/	wrap	[wájɲá]	'unwrap'	(reversive)

In -CV suffixation, the suffix obtains its segmental melody from the base through consonant gemination and vowel harmony processes to perform certain grammatical functions. Observe that in (i, v-ix) suffixation is applied to perform a

reversive function which, of course is the exact opposite of the function or meaning of the verb root, whereas the same process in (ii-iv) functions as meaning extension. -CV can equally be affixed to a CV(V) verb root as presented in (109).

3.6.3.3.3 CV Verb Root + -CV Suffix

CV → CV: CV

109.

(i) /sé/	'look'	[ń-sé:ʋé]	negation
(ii) /má/	'love'	[m'-má:ʋá]	negation
(iii) /dí/	'come'	[ń-dí:Ré]	negation
(iv) /bɔ̃/	'collect'	[m'-bɔ̃:ʋɔ̃]	negation
(v) /nɔ̃/	'give'	[ń-nɔ̃:ʋɔ̃]	negation
(vi) /dá/	stand	[ń-dá: ʋá]	negation
(vii) /tɔ̃/	'plant'	[ń-tɔ̃:ʋɔ̃]	negation
(viii) /kpá/	'die'	[m'-kpá: ʋá]	negation
(ix) /kpi/	'cut'	[m'-kpi:Ré]	negation
(x) /kpé/	'judge'	[m'-kpé:Ré]	negation
(xi) /nâá/	'lie down'	[ń-nâ: ʋá]	negation
(xii) /kâá/	'go'	[ń-kâ: ʋá]	negation

There is uniformity in the affixation process involving CV verb root.

The consonant of the suffix remains /R/

The V of the suffix harmonises with the vowel of the root.

RV suffix here marks negation.

The negative suffix is described as a CV syllable with a high tone.

Suffixation here results in the alteration of the weight unit of the syllable of the root.

The initial syllable acquires an additional weight unit or becomes heavy through vowel lengthening.

3.6.3.3.4 -CVCV Suffix

-CVCV suffix comprises two bound morphemes. The first morpheme, which comes immediately after the CVC verb root, is a reversive affix, reflexive affix or as meaning extension. The second morpheme, which is affixed to the base (made up of the root plus a CV suffix) functions as a negative marker. This indicates that the verb root can have more than one suffix as the data in (110) demonstrates. The suffix here are of two types even though they all have a CV structure. The feature specification of the suffix in (b) is determined by the feature specification of the verb root. In this case, the -C of the CV copies the coda of the verb root completely while the -V of the suffix harmonises with the vowel of the root to perform diverse functions.

110.

- (i) a. /tèm/ 'cook'
 b. /tèmmé/ 'bring down ... from fire'
 c. /ń-tèmméké/ 'I am not bringing down'
- (ii) a. /ɲùk/ 'bend'
 b. /ɲùkkú/ 'bend down'
 c. /ń-ɲùkkúké/ 'I am not bending down'
- (iii) a. /mín/ 'frown'
 b. /mínné/ 'frown at someone'
 c. /m'-mínnéké/ 'I am not frowning at someone'
- (iv) a. /bén/ 'carry'
 b. /bénné/ 'carry'
 c. /m'-bénnéké/ 'I am not carrying'
- (v) a. /fik/ 'press'
 b. /fikké/ 'relieve'
 c. /m'-fikkéké/ 'I am not relieving'
- (vi) a. /fúk/ 'cover'

- b. /fəkk ɛ/ 'uncover'
 c. /m'-fəkkɛkɛ/ 'I am not uncovering'
- (vii) a. /sɪt/ 'seal'
 b. /sittɛ/ 'remove seal'
 c. /ɪ-sittɛkɛ/ 'I am not removing seal'
- (viii) a. /lɪp/ 'conceal'
 b. /lippɛ/ 'expose'
 c. /ɪ-lippɛkɛ/ 'I am not exposing'
- (ix) a. /wáj/ 'wrap'
 b. /wájɣá/ 'unwrap'
 c. /ɪj-wájɣákɛ/ 'I am not unwrapping'

The verb stem in (c) takes on a uniform feature specification of the -CV suffix in a way that /-kɛ/ is affixed to all the stems irrespective of the feature specifications of the segments of the stem. /-kɛ/ suffix here performs the grammatical function of negation. The semantic essence of negation is different from reversive. For instance, the difference between /tem/ 'cook' and /témém/ 'bring down something from fire' indicates that of contrast between 'placing a pot on fire' and 'bringing down a pot from fire' rather than negation. The negative form of /tem/ is /kûtem/, 'do not cook' while the negation of /témém/ is /kûtémém/. Another difference is centred in the fact that reversive induces action whereas negation triggers no action.

3.6.3.4 Complex Verbal Structure

Observe that all the verbs above begin with a consonantal segment. However, when verbs are used in sentence construction, a syllabic prefix is always attached to the verb root except for imperatives/ commands. Let us consider the following sentences.

111.

- (i) **fèkèdí** 'run down here'
 (ii) **dáídžà** ídáp 'sleep'
 (iii) **támmá fùrɔ́** 'jump and pass'
 (iv) **bén** m̀kpɔ́ àfò kó **diá** 'take your food there and eat'

In the above sentences, the verbs, which are written in bold form, have an initial non-syllabic structure just like those in isolation. Let us consider yet other sentences.

112.

- (i) àmì **ńdàídžà** ídáp 'I am sleeping'
 (ii) àfò **àdàídžà** ídáp 'you are sleeping'
 (iii) àdžìt **ìdàídžà** ídáp 'we are sleeping'
 (iv) àjìn **èdàídžà** ídáp 'you are sleeping' pl

We can observe that the structure of the verbs in the above construction all have an initial syllabic element. Actually, the structure of the verb is supposed to begin with a consonant under normal circumstance. But the structure of the verb here is modified to agree with the subject of the sentence in number, person, and tense. The concord marker therefore produces a syllabic prefix.

/ń/ in 'àmi **ń-dàídžà** ídáp' is in agreement with the first person singular present tense.

/ì/ in 'àdžìt **ì-dàídžà** ídáp' agrees with first person plural present tense.

/à/ in 'àfò **à-dàídžà** ídáp' agrees with second person singular present tense.

/è/ in 'àjìn **è-dàídžà** ídáp' agrees with second person plural present tense.

Generally, the pronoun (àmi, àdžìt, àfò, and àjìn) could be dropped without affecting the meaning of the sentence in so far as the concord on the verb is properly marked.

A common characteristic of the verb is that it can consist of just the root, and one or more affixes indicating: concord, number, tense, aspect, negation, mood etc. Consider the following imperatives.

113.

- (i) m̀kpàákésídáídʒá 'I would have been sleeping from time to time'
 (ii) ɲkímá:Rá 'I did not like it'
 (iii) m̀firéké 'I have not forgotten'
 (iv) údʒírékédʒíré 'You are not even pursuing'

a. /m̀-kpàá-ké-sí-dáí dʒá/ is made up of five morphemes and six syllables.

/m̀/ is a concord marker

/kpàá/ a modal marker

/ké/ a tense marker

/sí/ an aspectual marker

The verb root is /daidʒa/.

b. /ɲ-kí-má:-Rá/ has four morphemes and four syllables.

/ɲ/ is a concord marker

/kí/ is a tense marker

/má/ is the root

/Rá/ is a negative marker.

c. /m̀-firé-ké/ has three morphemes and four syllables.

/m̀/ is a concord marker

/firé/ is the root

/ké/ is a negative marker.

d. /ú-dʒí ré-ké-dʒí ré/ is made up of four morphemes and six syllables.

/ú/ is a concord marker

/dʒíré/ the root, is duplicated for emphasis

/ké/ marks negation.

This shows that the root can take on several affixes to perform certain grammatical functions. The relevance of this is that, the structure of the Anaang verb, which was said to be either monosyllabic or disyllabic can be expanded to three or more syllables depending on its functions.

3.6.4 Structure of Anaang Adjectives

The structure of Anaang adjectives is quite similar to nouns in the sense that adjectives begin with a syllabic prefix. We present this with the following data.

- 114.
- (i) /àfiá/ 'white'
 - (ii) /àpán/ 'long'
 - (iii) /údzài/ 'fine'
 - (iv) /m̀biàrá/ 'bad'
 - (v) /m̀bóró/ 'round'
 - (vi) /údzííjé/ 'tinny'
 - (vii) /íj̀kùàŋja/ 'crooked'

From the above data, we can deduce that Anaang adjectives comprise two or three syllables. Adjectives can be derived from verbs, nouns or another adjective. Examples follow.

3.6.4.1 Derived Adjectives

115. Verb	adjective
(i) /símé/ 'be stupid'	/ú-sémé/ 'stupid person'
(ii) /fiá/ 'be bright'	/à-fiá/ 'white'
(iii) /má/ 'love'	/ú-má/ 'selfish person'
(iv) /bùró/ 'be confused'	/ú-!bùró/ 'foolish person'
(v) /t́/ 'multiply'	/u-í́/ 'multiple'
(vi) /sèré/ 'be disorganized'	/n-`sèré/ 'unkempt'
(vii) /sɛ̀:nɛ̀/ 'be rough'	/n`stɛ̀:nɛ̀/ 'untidy'

Observe that, the difference between the verb and the adjective lies in the initial syllable. A syllabic prefix is affixed to the verb to derive the adjective. Let us consider the derivation of adjective from the noun word class.

116 noun

- (i) /ńlòm/ 'clay'
 (ii) /íg^wát/ 'grey hair'
 (iii) /ílèt/ 'hair'
 (iv) /ńkáj/ 'charcoal'
 (v) /ńń^wóóń/ 'water'
 (vi) /èkpàt/ 'bag'
 (vii) /ákúbè/ 'chameleon'
 (ix) /ùwák/ 'plenty'

adjective

- /ńlòm-ńlòm/ 'chalky'
 /íg^wát-íg^wát/ 'grayish hair'
 /ílèt-ílèt/ 'hairy'
 /ńkáj-ńkáj/ 'black'
 /ńń^wóóń-ńń^wóóń/ 'watery'
 /èkpàt-èkpàt/ 'bogus'
 /ákúbè-ákúbè/ 'unpredictable'
 /ńwák-ńwák/ 'plenteous'

Adjectives in example (116) are derived through reduplication of the nouns. The syllable structure of the base including the tones remain unaltered when reduplicated. In another situation, an adjective can be derived from another adjective. This type of process occur mainly to intensify the adjectival quality as in the following example.

117. adjective

- | | | | |
|-----------------|-----------|-------------------|-----------|
| (i) /àfíá/ | adjective | /àfíá-àfíá/ | 'white' |
| (ii) /àńán/ | | /àńán-àńán/ | 'long' |
| (iii) /ùdžai/ | | /ùdžài-ùdžài/ | 'fine' |
| (iv) /m̀biàrà/ | | /m̀biàrà-m̀biàrà/ | 'bad' |
| (v) /m̀bóró/ | | /m̀bóró-m̀bóró/ | 'round' |
| (vi) /ńdžíńjé/ | | /ńdžíńjé-ńdžíńjé/ | 'tinny' |
| (vii) /ńkúáńńá/ | | /ńkúáńńá-ńkúáńńá/ | 'crooked' |
| (viii) /ùtò/ | | /ùtò-ùtò/ | 'yellow' |

Sometimes adjectives occur only in reduplicated forms without a syllabic prefix.

Example follows.

118. (i) /ń^wèn/ 'be black' / àń^wé:ń^wèn/ 'black'
 (ii) /dàt/ 'be red' / àdǎ:dàt/ 'red'
 (iii) */wá/ 'be green' / àwàwà/ 'green'

When adjectives are reduplicated, the reduplicant still carries a syllabic prefix since the process involves complete reduplication of the root. Sometimes an item can function as either an adjective or an adverb when reduplicated depending on usage.

Adjectives can be applied to mark grammatical contrast. This contrast is derived by a process of nasalization or vowel lengthening or a combination of the two processes. Let us consider the following data.

Plural formation

119. Singular		plural
(i)	/ètòk/ 'small'	/ntòk/
(ii)	/imúk/ 'short'	/mmúk/
(iii)	/àṅán/ 'tall'	/ṅán/
(iv)	/âfíá/ 'white'	/mífiá/

Plural formation in (119) above is achieved by the alternation of the initial prefix from an oral to a nasal consonant. The nasal consonant is homorganic to the consonant of a following syllable.

The second process of plural formation involves vowel lengthening and nasalization as illustrated in (120) below.

120. singular		plural
(i)	/m̀biàrà/ 'rotten'	/m̀bià:ṅá/
(ii)	/nsítte/ 'leaky'	/nsí:ṅé/

The vowel of the second syllable is lengthened to form a plural adjective. Observe equally that there is an alteration of the consonant of the final syllable, from oral to nasal consonant in (113i-ii).

Generally, plural formation in adjectives is not predictable since it does not have a fixed or uniform process. Let us consider yet another example.

121. singular		plural
(i)	/àdã:dát/ 'red'	/ndãát/
(ii)	/àṅ ^w ẽ:ṅ ^w èn/ 'black'	/ṅ ^w ṅ ^w èèn/

- | | | |
|----------------|-------------|------------|
| (iii) /èkámhá/ | 'big' | /m̀kpóón/ |
| (iv) /ùdžàì/ | 'beautiful' | /m̀fɔ́ɔ́n/ |

Plural formation in (114iii-iv) leads to a change in the morphological structure by creating new words. Whereas (i-ii) involve the deletion of the reduplicant, nasalization of the initial prefix and vowel lengthening. In all the examples, the initial syllable of Anaang adjectives is usually syllabic.

3.6.5 Anaang Adverbs

Adverbs and nouns share the same word structure in the sense that they all begin with a syllabic segment just like adjectives.

122a.

- | | |
|---------------|-------------|
| (i) /m̀kpɔ́ŋ/ | 'yesterday' |
| (ii) /m̀fɪn/ | 'today' |
| (iii) /ɪ̀jkó/ | 'there' |
| (iv) /m̀mí/ | 'here' |

Adverbs can be derived from nouns or adjectives. Example follows.

122b. nouns		adverbs	
(i) /étó/	'stick'	/étó-étó/	'stiffly'
(ii) /ímá/	'love'	/ímá-ímá/	'lovingly'
(iii) /ímé/	'patience'	/ímé-ímé/	'patiently'
(iv) /m̀fɔ́n/	'grace'	/m̀fɔ́n-m̀fɔ́n/	'gracefully'
(v) /m̀kpá/	'death'	/m̀kpá-m̀kpá/	'deadly'
(vi) /m̀biré/	'play'	/m̀biré-m̀biré/	'playfully'
(vii) /ibàk/	'wickedness'	/ibàk-ibàk/	'wickedly'

123. adjectives		adverbs	
(i) /ètòk/	'small'	/ètòk-ètòk/	'very small'
(ii) /idiɔ́k/	'bad'	/idiɔ́k-idiɔ́k/	'badly'
(iii) /̀ndisímé/	'stupid'	/̀ndisímé-̀ndisímé/	'stupidly'
(iv) /à̀nán/	'long'	/à̀nán-à̀nán/	'very long'

Adverbs are derived from nouns or adjectives through a process of complete reduplication. While verbs in Anaang begin with consonant, adjectives, nouns, and adverbs begin with a syllabic segment.

Certain ideophones can perform adverbial function. Ideophone is said to be a word, often onomatopoeic, which describes a predicate, qualitative or adverb in respect to manner, colour, sound smell, action, state or intensity (Ekere 1987, 1996:26). This type of adverb can occur without a syllabic prefix as presented in (124).

3.6.5.1 Adverbial Ideophones

Ideophones are generally described as having not only the phonological properties that set them apart from other categories, but also distributional characteristics that justify analyzing them as constituting a syntactic category (Creissels et al 2008:127)

124. (i) /ádùḶ tèm / 'he fell down heavily'
 (ii) /ádùḶ dʒim/ 'he fell down heavily'
 (iii) /ákpi tàp/ 'he cuts very fast'
 (iv) /ásàjà sḶḶp/ 'he walks stealthily'
 (v) /ámìà kpâ/ 'he slaps mercilessly.'
 (vi) /ámèn dʒùt/ 'he swallowed easily'
 (vii) /ámèn kpùt/ 'he swallowed heavily'
 (viii) /áfùrù dʒíáŋ / 'he passes very fast'
 (ix) /átḶ tèp/ 'it drops slowly'

The ideophones as presented in the example above is applied to describe the intensity of various actions. The ideophones that function as adverbs can be reduplicated to intensify the degree of action. The reduplication of adverbial ideophones does not affect the structure of the syllable of the base. The syllable of the base including the tones are completely reduplicated without any modification

irrespective of the type of syllable involved (i.e. whether open or close syllable) so that we have structures such as presented in (3.6.5.1.1).

3.6.5.1.1 Reduplicated Adverbial Ideophones

125.

- (i) /ádùḽ tèm - tèm/ 'he fell down heavily (with loud sound)'
 (ii) /ádùḽ dʒim - dʒim/ 'he fell down heavily (with force)'
 (iii) /ákpi tàp- tàp/ 'he cuts very fast (sharp cut)'
 (iv) /ásanja sḽḽp - sḽḽp/ 'he walks stealthily (very slow)'
 (v) /ámìà kpâ - kpâ / 'he slaps mercilessly (furiously)'
 (vi) /ámèn dʒùt - dʒùt/ 'he swallowed easily (very fast)'
 (vii) /ámèn kpùt -kpùt/ 'he swallowed heavily (noisily)'
 (viii) /áfùrù dʒíán - dʒíán/ 'he passes very fast (very fast)'
 (ix) /átḽi tèt - tèt/ 'it drops slowly (continuously)'

Observe that adverbial ideophones do not have an initial syllabic segment. Therefore, our generalization on the structure of Anaang adverbs does not include adverbial ideophones.

3.6.6 Structure of Anaang Prepositions

The structures of Anaang prepositions are predictable. Anaang prepositions have either a CV or NCV syllable. Generally, prepositions in Anaang cannot be derived. Let us consider the following data.

126.

- (i) ábà ké úfḽk 'he is **at** home'
 (ii) ábiòm ké íg^wò 'he is carrying it **on** his head'
 (iii) ásìn ké ínùà 'he puts it **in** his mouth'
 (iv) ábḽ ké úbḽk 'he collects it **with** his hand'
 (v) abòìdʒò ké àwindò 'he passes **through** the window'

- (vi) áfùrù ké àkɔ 'he jumped **over** the fence'
 (vii) ábòidzò ké áŋ^wá 'he walked **across** the field'
 (viii) álùŋ ìmè flààd 'he lives **with** mad people'
 (ix) ábà ìmè ág^wó 'he is **with** somebody'

Anaang has only two lexical items as prepositions viz: /ké/ CV and /ìmè/ NCV. /ké/ is used for: 'at, on, in, with, above, over, through, across etc., whereas /ìmè/ is restricted to only 'with'.

This type of structure only obtains when the preposition occurs in isolation. However, there is an alteration of the structure of the syllable of the preposition when it is used in sentence construction. Vowel deletion takes place if the preposition is followed by another word with an initial vowel. Recall that Anaang does not permit vowel hiatus. The deletion rule therefore applies to prevent this hiatus. The deletion here affects either V₁ or V₂ based on the relative heights of the vowel. Like in other Lower Cross languages, Essien 1990). A low vowel becomes deleted while a high vowel survives. Equally, the syllabic nasal in /ìmè/ is deleted in sentence construction leaving the preposition with a CV structure so that the syllable structure of the preposition of (126) above becomes modified as presented below.

127. Preposition+ noun			preposition phrase
(i) /ké	+ úfɔ́k/	→	[kúfɔ́k]
in	house		in the house
(ii) /ké	+ íg ^w ò/	→	[k íg ^w ò]
on	head		on the head
(iii) /ké	+ ínùà/	→	[kínùà]
in	mouth		in his mouth
(iv) /ké	+ úbɔ́k/	→	[k úbɔ́k]
with	hand		with his hand
(v) /ké	+ àwíndò/	→	[kàwíndò]
through	window		through the window
(vi) /ké	+ àkɔ́/	→	[kàkɔ́]
over	fence		over the fence

(vi) /ké	+ áŋ ^{wá} /	→	[káŋ ^{wá}]
across	field		across the field
(viii) /m̀m̀è	+ íl̀ààd/	→	[m̀í l̀ààd]
with	madman		with mad people
(ix) /m̀m̀è	+ ág ^{wó} /	→	[m̀ě g ^{wó}]
with	some one		with some one

Overall, the structure of Anaang word class shows that verbs have the largest morphological complex structure than any other word class.

In the sections covered so far, much attention has been devoted to the role of the syllable in the analyses of Anaang word structure and the relevance of the syllable in word formation. In what follows, we shall deviate a little from word formation rules to the relevance of the syllable in word structure rules i.e. 'compounding processes'.

3.7 Anaang Compounds

The concept of compound is an interesting phenomenon in morphology (Matthews 1991, katamba 1993, Anderson 1992, Yule 2006, Spencer 1991). Compounds provide motivation for assigning internal structure to words. This is achieved through a process known as compounding. Compounding deals with word structure rules rather than word formation rules. According to Anderson (1992), a word formation rule operates on a single word (stem) to manipulate its phonological rule by affixation as well as other properties. Compounding in contrast, involves the combination of stems from the lexicon into a phrase or word. Compounding is viewed as a morpho-syntactic process by Spencer (1991), in the sense that elements of a compound may have relations to each other which resemble the relations holding between the constituent of a sentence. These are head modifier, predicate-argument and apposition. These characteristics are very typical in English compounds. Anaang compounds are made up of two elements without any further dependency holding between them. Even though compounding is a morpho-syntactic process, it has implications on the structure of Anaang phonology in the sense that compounding equally involves certain phonological processes which of course affect the internal structure of the syllable as presented in the following sub-sections.

3.7.1 Structure of Anaang Compounds

Compounds occur more frequently in nouns than other word classes. Since nouns in Anaang generally begin with a syllabic segment all compounds must have an initial syllabic element. Consider the following example.

3.7.1.1 Compound Nouns

128.

(i)	/úfúk # áɔ́ɔ̀/	→	[úfúʌáɔ́ɔ̀]
	covering sun		umbrella
(ii)	/úfòk # ábàsi/	→	[úfòʌábàsi]
	house God		church
(iii)	/úfòk # íbòk/	→	[úfòʌíbòk]
	house drugs		hospital
(iv)	/úfòk # ñg ^w èt/	→	[úfòkñg ^w èt]
	house # book		school
(v)	/étfit # íkòt/	→	[étfiríkòt]
	interior bush		bush
(vi)	/étfit # úfòk/	→	[étfirúfòk]
	interior house		rooms
(vii)	/íkòt # èkpèné/	→	[íkòʌèkpèné]
	family proper name		place name
(viii)	/èkpàt # úbòk/	→	[èkpàʌúbòk]
	bag hand		hand bag
(ix)	/ítút # áfit/	→	[ítúʌáfit]
	vagina faeces		anus

3.7.1.1 Formal Analysis of the Structure of Anaang Compounds

Compounding in Anaang involves the alteration of the phonological structure of the underlying constructs. In other words, the internal structure of the syllable can be affected by compounding process in the following ways.

- (i) segment weakening/voicing assimilation
- (ii) coda shift

- (iii) vowel deletion/ complete vowel assimilation
- (iv) syllable weight alteration
- (v) tonal alteration
- (vi) resyllabification/disyllabification

3.7.1.1.1 Segment Weakening/Voicing Assimilation

When the first noun in a construct ends with a voiceless stop segment, such a segment becomes weakened to its homorganic continuants if it is followed by another word with an initial vocalic segment. Since nouns generally begin with a syllabic prefix, the juxtaposition of two nouns produces VC#V structure iff the first noun ends in a consonant while the second noun begins with a vocalic segment. Voiceless stops in Anaang are voiced between vowels at word boundary. The intervocalic consonant assimilates to the voicing feature of the vowel. When this applies, the consonant becomes weakened to a tap or fricative respectively.

3.7.1.1.1.1 Weakening Involving /p/

129. compounds		underlying form	weakened segment
(i) /itʃíp/ # /áɔ́zòp/	→	[itʃíβáɔ́zòp]	/p/ → [β]
nut oil palm		coconut	
(ii) /úkɛ́p/ # /ákò/	→	[úkɛ́βákò]	/p/ → [β]
covering pot		pot cover	
(iii) /ifɔ́p/ # /ébót/	→	[ifɔ́βébót]	/p/ → [β]
roasted goat		roasted goat	

3.7.1.1.1.2 Weakening Involving /t/

130. compounds		underlying form	weakened segment
(i) /étʃít # íkòt/	→	[étʃíríkòt]	/t/ → [r]
interior bush		bush	/t/ → [r]

- (ii) /étfít # úfɔ̀k/ → [étfirúfɔ̀k] /t/ → [r]
interior house rooms
- (iii) /íkɔ̀t # èkpèné/ → [ikɔ̀rèkpèné] /t/ → [r]
family proper name place name
- (iv) /èkpàt # úbɔ̀k/ → [èkpàrúbɔ̀k] /t/ → [r]
bag hand hand bag
- (v) /ítút # áfít/ → [ítúráfít] /t/ → [r]
virgina faeces anus

3.7.1.1.1.2 Weakening Involving /k/

131. compounds

- | | underlying form | weakened segment |
|--------------------------------------|----------------------------|------------------|
| (i) /úfúk # áɔ̀zò/
covering sun | → [úfúʙáɔ̀zò]
umbrella | /k/ → [ʙ] |
| (ii) /úfɔ̀k # àbàsi/
house God | → [úfɔ̀ʙábàsi]
church | /k/ → [ʙ] |
| (iii) /úfɔ̀k # íbɔ̀k/
house drugs | → [úfɔ̀Ríbɔ̀k]
hospital | /k/ → [R] |
| (iv) /idàk # étó/
under tree | → [idàRétò]
shade | /k/ → [R] |
| (v) /úbɔ̀k # èlèm/
hand behind | → [úbɔ̀Rélèm]
bribe | /k/ → [R] |
| (vi) /úlúk # íkɔ̀t/
rope bush | → [úlúRíkɔ̀t]
snake | /k/ → [R] |
| (vii) /úfɔ̀k # ùrùà/
house market | → [úfɔ̀ʙùrùà]
shop | /k/ → [ʙ] |

- (viii) /ákɔ́k # úkɔ́t → [ákɔ́:ɸúkɔ́] /k/ → [ɸ]
 branches raffia tree bamboo
- (ix) /íták # étó/ → [ítáRétò] /k/ → [R]
 root tree tree

3.7.1.1.2 Coda Shift

In another situation, compounding or the juxtaposition of two words can result in the alteration of the internal structure of the syllable, where the crisp captive coda of a preceding syllable is released to become an onset of a following onsetless syllable.

132. Noun structure # noun structure		compound structure
V CVC	V CVC	V CV CV CVC
(i) /úsúŋ/ # /úfɔ́k/		[úsúŋúfɔ́k]
road	house	door
(ii) /ítɔ́ŋ/ # /úbɔ́k/		[ítɔ́ŋ úbɔ́k]
neck	hand	wrist
(iii) /úbóm/ # /áfùm/		[úbómáfùm]
canoe	air	aeroplane
(iv) /ítán/ # /ísɔ́ŋ/		[ítánísɔ́ŋ]
sand	ground	soil
(v) /úbɔ́k # /èlèm/		[úbɔ́Rèlèm]
hand	behind	bribe
(vi) /èkpàt/ # /úbɔ́k/		[èkpàrúbɔ́k]
bag	hand	handbag
(vii) /ítfíp/ # /ádʒòp/		[ítfípádʒòp]
nut	oil palm	coconut

The second syllable that was initially closed by a coda becomes open while the coda shifts to a following syllable thereby producing the structure as presented in (133) using Onset - Rhyme theory.

133.

The illustration indicates that the alteration occurs mainly at the internal structure of the syllable, whereas the number of the syllable that were underlyingly four still surfaced as four after the alteration.

Coda shift is only possible in the environment of a consonant at word boundary before a following onsetless (vocalic) syllable. This shows that syllabification process does not count at word boundary.

3.7.1.1.3 Vowel Assimilation/Vowel Deletion

The examples in (133) involve compounds with word final consonant only. Let us consider compound construction where the first noun ends in a vowel.

134.	Noun	syllable Structure	noun	syllable structure	compound	syllable structure
(i)	/m̀bàrà/ nails	N-CV-CV	/ék̀pè/ tiger	V-CV	[m̀bàrè:kpè] bramble	N-CV-CVV-CV
(ii)	/f̀kpá/ skin	V-CV	/à̀ṅ̀ṅ̀/ sky	V-CVC	[f̀kpa:ṅ̀ṅ̀] sky	V-CVV-CVC
(iii)	/m̀bòró/ banana	N-CV-CV	/éb̀ḁ̀k/ monkey	V-CVC	[m̀bòrèb̀ḁ̀k] black banana	N-CV-CV-CVC

$V_1\#V_2$ is created in example (134). This is made possible since most nouns in Anaang begin with a vowel and end with a vowel. Since Anaang does not permit vowel hiatus in most cases, one of the $V_1\#V_2$ is either deleted or gets completely assimilated to the adjacent vowel. It should however be observed that V_1 assimilates V_2 in (134 i-ii). In this case, a lower vowel becomes assimilated to a relatively high vowel (134i). Assimilation here is determined by the tonal structure. Vowels with like-tonal structure cannot undergo assimilation process. Based on this, assimilation does not occur in (134iii), rather it involves the deletion of V_1 .

3.7.1.1.4 Syllable Weight Alteration

When two independent morphemes are compounded into one word, there is bound to be an alteration of the weight unit of the syllable. The weight of the syllable can be increased or reduced depending on the internal structure of the affected syllable. The data iv (132), is repeated as (135) for our analysis.

135.	noun	+	noun	compound	syllable structure
	V CVC	+	V CVC		V-CV-CV-CVC
(i)	/úsúṅ/	#	/úf̀ḁ̀k/	[ú-sú-ṅú-f̀ḁ̀k]	V-CV-CV-CVC door
(ii)	/it̀ḁ̀ṅ/	#	/úb̀ḁ̀k/	[i-t̀ḁ̀ṅú-b̀ḁ̀k]	V-CV-CV-CVC wriste
(iii)	/úb̀óm/	#	/áf̀ùm/	[ù-b̀ó-má-f̀ùm]	V-CV-CV-CVC aeroplane
(iv)	/ń̀tán/	#	/ís̀ḁ̀ṅ/	[ń̀- tá- ní- s̀ḁ̀ṅ]	V-CV-CV-CVC soil
(v)	/úb̀ḁ̀k	#	/èl̀èm/	[ú-b̀ḁ̀- Ré- l̀èm]	V-CV-CV-CVC bribe
(vi)	/ék̀pàt/	#	/úb̀ḁ̀k/	[è- kpà- rú- b̀ḁ̀k]	V-CV-CV-CVC hand bag
(vii)	/it̀f̀íp/	#	/ád̀z̀òp/	[i-t̀f̀í- ßá- d̀z̀òp]	V-CV-CV-CVC coconut

The weight unit of the second syllable is reduced from heavy to light syllable structure as is indicated by the arrow to the right. This occurs when the crisps captive coda in CVC syllable is released to the onset of a following V syllable as formalised in (136).

136. $V\ CVC + V\ CVC \rightarrow V\ CVC\ V\ CVC \rightarrow V\ CV\ CV\ CVC$
- | | | | | | | |
|-------|---------|---|---------|-------------|--------------|-------------|
| (i) | /úsúŋ/ | # | /úfɔ̀k/ | V-CVC-V-CVC | [úsúŋúfɔ̀k] | V-CV-CV-CVC |
| (ii) | /itɔ̀ŋ/ | # | /úbɔ̀k/ | V-CVC-V-CVC | [itɔ̀ŋúbɔ̀k] | V-CV-CV-CVC |
| (iii) | /úbóm/ | # | /áfùm/ | V-CVC-V-CVC | [úbómáfùm] | V-CV-CV-CVC |
| (iv) | /ítán/ | # | /ísɔ̀ŋ/ | V-CVC-V-CVC | [ítánísɔ̀ŋ] | V-CV-CV-CVC |
| (v) | /úbɔ̀k | # | /èlèm/ | V-CVC-V-CVC | [úbɔ̀kèlèm] | V-CV-CV-CVC |
| (vi) | /èkpát/ | # | /úbɔ̀k/ | V-CVC-V-CVC | [èkpátúbɔ̀k] | V-CV-CV-CVC |
| (vii) | /itfíp/ | # | /ádʒòp/ | V-CVC-V-CVC | [itfípádʒòp] | V-CV-CV-CVC |

This is autosegmentalised thus

In another situation, compounding can result in an underlying $V_1\#V_2$ as follows.

- | | | | | | | |
|----------|---------|---|---------|---------------|----------------|--------------|
| 138. (i) | /ikpá/ | # | /àŋɔ̀ŋ/ | V-CV-V-CVC | [í-kpá: -ŋɔ̀ŋ] | V-CVV-CVC |
| | skin | | heaven | | sky | |
| (ii) | /ŋkùwà/ | # | /únèn/ | N-CV-CV-V-CVC | [ŋ-kù-wàú-nèn] | N-CV-CVV-CVC |
| | seed | | hen | | egg | |
| (ii) | /ikpá/ | # | /úkót/ | V-CV-V-CVC | [í-kpáú-kòt] | V-CVV-CVC |
| | skin | | leg | | shoes | |

(iv)	/élémè/	#	/íkán/	V-CV-CV-V-CVC	[é-lé-mèi-kàn]	V-CV-CVV-CVC
	tongue		fire			flame

$V_1\#V_2$ projects underlying dual syllable heads. Since Anaang does not permit dual syllable heads without an intervening consonant in most cases, one of the syllable heads is pruned. Observe that the penultimate syllable in the underlying form has a light V structure, whereas, the antepenultimate syllable has a CV light structure. The syllable head of the penultimate syllable becomes deleted by dual syllable head pruning rule. The pruning process results in the increase on the weight unit of the preceding syllable. The weight unit of the penultimate syllable increases from light to CVV heavy structure as a result of the desyllabification process. (Details are presented in 3.7.1.1.5)

3.7.1.1.5 Resyllabification/Desyllabification

All the processes in compounding result in resyllabification. This is illustrated in (139)

139.

(i)	/ìkpá/	/àḅḅḅ/	V-CV- V- CVC	[ì-kpâ: -ḅḅḅ]	V-CVV-CVC
	skin	up		sky	
(ii)	/ìkpá/	/úkót/	V-CV-V-CVC	[ì-kpáú-kòt]	V-CVV-CVC
	skin	leg		shoes	
(iii)	/élémè/	/íkán/	V-CV-CV--V-CVC	[é-lé-mĩ: -kàn]	V-CV-CVV-CVC
	tongue	fire		flame	
(iv)	/àkpó/	/ébót/	V-CV-V-CVC	[á-kpá-bòt]	V-CV-CVC
	male	goat		he-goat	
(v)	/úsúḅ/	/úfḅḅk/	V-CVC-V-CVC	[ú-sú-ḅḅ-fḅk]	V-CV-CV-CVC
	road	house		door	
(vi)	/itḅḅ/	/úbḅḅk/	V-CVC-V-CVC	[i-tḅḅ-úbḅk]	V-CV-CV-CVC
	neck	hand		wrist	
(vii)	/étfit/	/úfḅḅk/	V-CVC-V-CVC	[é-tfi-rú-fḅk]	V-CV-CV-CVC
	heart	house		room	

In examples (i-v), the penultimate syllable desyllabifies, whereas the coda of the antepenultimate syllable resyllabifies to a following syllable in (vi-viii).

3.7.1.1.6 Tonal Modification

Apart from proper names, compound nouns in Anaang have a fixed tonal pattern. The tone on the penultimate syllable is usually high, whereas the last syllable carries a low tone irrespective of the tonal pattern of the underlying form. The data (132) is repeated here to illustrate our point.

140.	underlying form		tones	compounds	tones
(i)	/úsúŋ/ # /úfɔ̃k/		H-H-H-L	[úsúŋúfɔ̃k]	H-H-H-L
	road	house		door	
(ii)	/itɔ̃ŋ/ # /úbɔ̃k/		L-H-H-H	[itɔ̃ŋ úbɔ̃k]	L-H-H-L
	neck	hand		wrist	
(iii)	/úbóm/ # /áfùm/		L-H-H-L	[úbómáfùm]	L-H-H-L
	canoe	air		aeroplane	
(iv)	/ítán/ # /ísɔ̃ŋ/		H-H-H-L	[ítánísɔ̃ŋ]	H-H-H-L
	sand	ground		soil	
(v)	/úbɔ̃k # /èlèm/		H-H-L-L	[úbɔ̃Rélèm]	H-H-H-L
	hand	behind		bribery	
(vi)	/èkpát/ # /úbɔ̃k/		LLHH	[èkpárúbɔ̃k]	LLHL
	bag	hand		handbag	
(vii)	/ítfíp/ # /áɔ̃ɔ̃p/		H-H-H-L	[ítfíβáɔ̃ɔ̃p]	H-H-H-L
	nut	oil palm		coconut	

3.8 Anaang Syllable Structure and Grammatical Constructions.

There is a great deal of interaction between Anaang phonology and syntax in such a way that some phonological processes may be required for some sentence constructions. This shows that phonological constituents are not restricted to phonological or morphological domains only. Our concentration here shall be on two types of grammatical constructions in Anaang: negative and focus constructions.

3.8.1 Negative Construction in Anaang

Negation involves two affixation processes determined partly by the type of sentence and partly by the structure of the syllable. It involves both prefixation and suffixation processes.

3.8.1.1 Negative Prefix

The morpheme *ké-* is the only negative prefix in Anaang. *Ké-* can be prefixed to either a monosyllabic or a disyllabic verb root to perform negation. Let us consider the following example.

141. (i) /kûdí/ 'do not come'
 (ii) /kûtém/ 'do not cook'
 (iii) /kûkédé/ 'do not be worried'

The above imperatives are made up of: a negative prefix /*ké*/ 'do not', a concord marker /*ù*/ 'second person negative marker' and a verb root. The concord marker /*ù*/ separates the verb root from the negative marker. The negative marker is therefore prefixed to the stem rather than the root. Details are presented as in (142).

142. Prefix	personal marker	verb root	syllable structure	ouput	syllable structure
(i) / <i>ké</i> /	<i>ù</i>	/ <i>dí</i> / come	CV-V-CV	[<i>kû:-dí</i>]	CV-CV do not come
(ii) / <i>ké</i> /	<i>ù</i>	/ <i>n ð</i> / give	CV-V-CV	[<i>kû:-nð</i>]	CV-CV do not give
iii) / <i>k é</i> /	<i>ù</i>	/ <i>tém</i> / cook	CV-V-CVC	[<i>kû:-tém</i>]	CV-CVC do not cook

Two phonological processes are involved: vowel assimilation and tonal alteration. The vowel of the negative marker is assimilated by the concord /*u*/, so that the negative marker surfaces as /*kû*/. Secondly, the final low tone on the verb is raised to a high tone. The premise is that the final syllable in imperative negative sentences with CV verb root in Anaang is inherently high.

3.8.1.1.1 CV Verb Root

For a CV monosyllable, the output has a low-high tonal pattern if the tonal pattern of the root verb is low, but maintains a high tonal pattern if it is high as presented in example (143).

	marker	verb root	output	tone	syllable structure	
(i)	/ké/	ù /dí/ come	[kû:-dí/	HL-H	CV-CV	'do not come'
(ii)	/ké/	ù /nǝ/ give	[kû:-nǝ]	HL-LH	CV-CV	'do not give'
(iii)	/ké/	ù /kǝ/ Pluck	[kû:-kǝ]	HL LH	CV-CV	'do not pluck'
(iv)	/ké/	ù /mǎ/ finish	[kû:-mǎ]	HL LH	CV-CV	'do not finish'
(v)	/ké/	ù /kpù/ disappoint	[ku:-kpù]	HL LH	CV-CV	'do not fail'
(vi)	/ké/	ù /dǝ/ marry	[kû:-dǝ]	HL H	CV-CV	'do not marry'

We can therefore conclude that for negation that involves CV- prefix in Anaang, the final syllable of the verb must be associated with a level high tone or a low-high sequence depending on the weight unit of the final syllable of the root verb.

3.8.1.1.2 CVC Verb Root

The verb root in CVC or heavy syllable structure has a level high tone irrespective of the tonal pattern of the underlying form of the base. This is formalized in example (144).

	Root	tone	negation	tone	gloss
(i)	/tèm/	L	[kû:tém]	HL-H	'do not cook'
					cook
(ii)	/bòm/	L	[kû:-bóm]	HL-H	'do not break'

- break
- (iii) /dʒɛp/ L [kû:-dʒɛp] HL-H 'do not spy'
spy
- (iv) /fõt/ L [kû:-fõt] HL-H 'do not peel'
peel
- (v) /dép/ H [ku:ˆ-dép] HL-H 'do not buy'
buy
- (vi) /fõp/ H [ku:ˆ-fõp] HL-H 'do not roast'
roast
- (vii) /tóp/ H [kû:-tóp] HL-H 'do not throw'
throw

What is constant here is that the vowel of the negative prefix assimilates to the vowel of the concord marker irrespective of the structure of the syllable.

3.8.1.1.3 CVCV Verb Root

There is no alteration of the tonal structure in disyllabic CVCV verb root. Example follows.

145. root verb	tone	negation	tone	gloss
(i) /kéré/ think	HH	[kû:kéré]	HL-H-H	'do not think'
(ii) /bìré/ play	LH	[kû:bìré]	HL-L-H	'do not play'
(ii) /bèré/ lean on	LH	[kû:bèré]	HL-L-H	'do not lean'
(iv) /sàṅjá/ walk	LH	[kû:sàṅjá]	HL-L-H	'do not walk'
(v) /tóbó/ tie	HH	[kû:tóbó]	HL-H-H	'do not tie'

(vi) /síné/	HH	[kû:siné]	HL-H-H	'do not wear'
wear				
(vii) /dʒùttò/	LL	[kû:dʒùttò]	HL-L-L	'do not double'
double				
(viii) /kpàkkà /	LL	[kû:kpàkkà]	HL-L-L	'do not double cross'
double cross				

Apart from prefixation, negation can equally be constructed by suffixation as demonstrated by (Essien 1990) Lower Cross languages.

3.8.1.2 Negative Suffix

Let us consider negation by suffixation

146.	Verb	negative	syllable	output	syllable	gloss
	Root	suffix	structure		structure	
(i)	/dí /	/Ré/	CV CV	[n̩-dii-ɛ é]	CVV-CV	'I am not coming'
(ii)	/dá /	/Rá/	CV CV	[n̩-dáá-Rá]	CVV-CV	'I am not standing'
(iii)	/bɔ̃/	/ɛɔ̃/	CV CV	[m̩-bɔ̃ɔ̃-ɛɔ̃]	CVV-CV	'I am not receiving'
(iv)	/nɔ̃/	/ɛɔ̃/	CV CV	[n̩-nɔ̃ɔ̃-ɛɔ̃]	CVV-CV	'I am not giving'
(v)	/tèm/	/mé/	CVC CV	[n̩-tèm-mé]	CVC-CV	'I am not cooking'
(vi)	/bán/	/ná/	CVC CV	[m̩-bán-ná]	CVC-CV	'I am not sharpening'
(vii)	/fèRé/	/ké/	CV CV CV	[m̩-fè-Ré-ké]	CV-CV-CV	'I am not running'
(viii)	/bénné/	/ké/	CVCCVCV	[m̩-bén-né-ké]	CVC CV CV	'I am not carrying'
(ix)	/támmá/	/ké/	CVCCV CV	[n̩-tám-má-ké]	CVC-CV-CV	'I am not jumping'

In the above representation, -CV suffix is affixed to the verb root to form negation. The phonetic feature of the suffix is determined by the structure of the syllable of the root verb as will be seen later.

3.8.1.2.1 CV – Verb Root

If the root verb has a CV monosyllabic structure, /CV/ suffix is affixed to the root as in (147i-iv).

147. (i)	/di/	+ /Ré/	CV CV	[diiR é]	CVV CV
	come	neg		... coming	
(ii)	/dá/	+ /Rá/	CV CV	[dááRá]	CVV CV
	stand	neg		...not standing	
(iii)	/bɔ̃/	+ /ʒɔ̃/	CV CV	[bɔ̃ɔ̃ʒɔ̃]	CVV CV
	take	neg		...not taking	
(iv)	/nɔ̃/	+ /ʒɔ̃/	CV CV	[nɔ̃ɔ̃ʒɔ̃]	CVV CV
	give	neg		...not giving	

The feature specification of the consonant is fixed /R/ or /ʒ/. But the phonetic content of the vowel varies based on the feature of the root vowel. The vowel of the suffix is derived by vowel harmony process. If the root verb has a CV structure, the vowel of the root must be lengthened even when there is no segment deletion. The premise is that the root verb must necessarily remain heavy since the vowel of the suffix is derived by vowel harmony process.

-CV suffix can equally be affixed to Anaang verb root with CVC structure to mark negation.

3.8.1.2.2 CVC Root Verb

148.	root verb	suffix	negation	gloss
(i)	/tèm/	/mé/	[n-tèm-mé]	'not cooking'
(ii)	/bán/	/ná/	[n-bán-ná]	'not sharpening'
(iii)	/sàŋ/	/ŋá/	[n-sàŋ-ŋá]	'not moving'
(iv)	/bàt/	/tá/	[m-bàt-tá]	'not counting'
(v)	/bɔ̃ p/	/pɔ̃/	[m-bɔ̃p-pɔ̃]	'not tying'
(vi)	/kɔ̃ k/	/kɔ̃/	[ŋ-kɔ̃k-kɔ̃]	'not grinding'

If the root has a CVC verb structure, it takes on a CV suffix. The C of the suffix is derived by gemination of the final consonant of the root, while the vowel harmonises with the root vowel.

3.8.1.2.3 CV(C)CV Verb Root

The only process involved in negation with disyllabic base is /ke/ suffixation.

149. root verb	suffix	negation
(i) /bénné/ carry	ké	[m-bénnéké] I am not carrying
(ii) /támmá/ jump	ké	[ń-támmáké] I am not jumping
(iii) /sàṅá/ walk	ke	[ń-sàṅáké] I am not walking
(iv) /fèRé/ run	ke	[ń-fèRéké] I am not running
(v) /dárá/ rejoice	ke	[ń-dáráké] I am not rejoicing

Disyllabic verb root takes on /-ke/ suffix to mark negation. The personal pronoun here is normally replaced with a syllabic nasal which marks concord with the first person. Emphasis here is on the verb root and the negative marker, therefore, we ignore all other processes.

In conclusion therefore, it can be seen that the structure of the syllable is a determinant in the selection of the feature of the affixes in negative construction in Anaang. In all the cases except for CVCV verb root, the vowel of the suffix is determined by the feature specification of the vowel of the root. The root vowel must harmonise with the vowel of the suffix. There is no tonal perturbation in negation which involves suffixation.

3.9 Focus Construction

Focus construction in Anaang can be achieved by both syntactic and phonological processes (Essien 1990).

In Anaang, nouns, pronouns, verbs, adverbs, and adjectives can be focused in a stretch of speech. Our focus here is on phonological processes. Phonologically, focus construction in Anaang is achieved through reduplication. Consider the data in (150)

150.

- | | | |
|-------|-------------------------------|---------------------------------------|
| (i) | àmi m̀fèRè it̀ɔ̀k | 'I am running (unmarked sentence)' |
| (ii) | àmi m̀fèRè íɔ̀R it̀ɔ̀k | 'I run seriously ' |
| (iii) | àmi àmi m̀fèRè it̀ɔ̀k | 'it is I who run' |
| (iv) | àmi m̀fèfèRè it̀ɔ̀k | 'I am running (not otherwise)' |

The focused element is made bold in the above data. The difference between the focused and the non-focused items is that the non-focused items are not duplicated. The focused elements in (150ii-iv) are reduplicated. Verbs in focused construction undergo a partial reduplication process as in (150iv), whereas other classes like nouns, pronouns, etc exhibit complete reduplication process as in (150iii). Again, let us consider another data.

151.

- | | | |
|-------|-----------------------------|-----------------------------------|
| (i) | ímá ábɔ̀k áféré | 'ima is cooking (unmarked)' |
| (ii) | ímá ábɔ̀:ábɔ̀k áféré | 'ima is cooking (not other wise)' |
| (iii) | ímá ábɔ̀k áféré:féré | 'ima cooks only soup ' |

152a.

- | | | |
|-------|---|---|
| (i) | ébót átà ig ^w á | 'the goat eats cassava (unmarked)' |
| (ii) | ébórébót átà ig ^w á | 'it is only the goat that eats cassava' |
| (iii) | ébót átã:tà ig ^w á | 'the goat eats cassava (not other wise)' |
| (iv) | ébót átà ig ^w á íg^wá | 'the goat eats only cassava ' |

Where the emphasis is on a structure other than the verb, a complete duplication will occur without tonal alteration.

The focused items in (152a_{ii}, iv) are nouns.

Verb is the focus in (iii). Observe that partial reduplication is applied here which involves the copying of the CV element of the verb root so that we have structure such as in (152b).

152b. bɔ́k → bɔ́:bɔ́k
 tá → tá:tá

Two other processes are involved here. These are tonal alteration and segment lengthening. Observe that the vowel of the initial syllable of the focused item is lengthened. This is followed by tone raising. In other words if the focused item is a verb, the initial syllable must have a high tone. In this situation, if the first syllable has a low tone, the additional high tone will produce a low-high sequence. The premise is that, there is an inherent high tone attached to the verb root to make it prominent. In all the cases, the structure of the initial syllable must remain open and heavy in such a way that even if the root verb has a CV structure as in (iii), the vowel of the initial syllable must be lengthened for emphasis. Again, let us consider the following imperative constructions.

153.	Root	tonal	syllable	focused	tonal	syllable	gloss
	Word	Pattern	structure	form	pattern	structure	
(i)	/bó	H	CV	[bó: -bó]	H-H	CV-CV	'say it'
(ii)	/nɔ́/	L	CV	[nɔ́: -nɔ́]	LH-L	CV-CV	'give'
(iii)	/bɔ́/	L	CV	[bɔ́: -bɔ́]	HL-L	CV-CV-	'take'
(iv)	/tém/	L	CVC	[tɛ́: -tém]	LH-L	CV: -CV	'cook'
(v)	/tém/	H	CVC	[tɛ́: -tém]	H-H	CV: -CV	'cut(the grass)'
(vi)	/kpàppá/	LH	CVCCV	[kpǎ:kpàppá]	LH-L-H	CV: -CVC-CV	'carry'
(vii)	/bénné/	HH	CVCCV	[bé:bénné]	H-HH	CV: -CVC.-CV	'lift'
(iv)	/fèkédí/	LLH	CVCVCV	[fɛ́:fèkédí]	LH-L-L-H	CV: -CV-CV	'run'

Verbal reduplication affects only the initial syllable irrespective of the number of the syllables of the base. Secondly, the initial syllable of the focused item remains constantly open irrespective of the pattern of the syllable at the root.

At the same time, the duplicated item can be separated by a negative marker or contrastive affix as presented in example (154).

154. Root	syllable	focused	syllable
word	structure	form	structure
(i) /bó/	CV	[bó- Ró -bó]	CV-CV-CV
		'not saying other wise'	
(ii) /tèm/	CVC	[tèm- mé -tèm]	CVC-CV-CVC
		'not cooking at all'	
(iii) /kpàppá/	VCCV	[kpàp- pá -ké-kpàp- pá]	CVC-CV-CVC-VCCV
		'not carrying'	
(iv) /bénné/	CVCCV	[bénné- ké bénné]	CVC-CV-CV-CVC-CV
		'not lifting'	

The negative marker is emboldened. The verb here undergoes complete duplication process irrespective of the structure of the root.

There is another situation where focus construction is achieved by ideophonic lengthening as the following data illustrates.

155. [átèm míkpɔ́]	'he is cooking'
[átèè-è-è-è-è-m]	'he is cooking assorted...'
[ákɔ́ŋ ikɔ́ŋ]	'he is coughing'
[ákɔ́ŋ-ŋ-ŋ-ŋ]	'he is coughing seriously'

This type of construction involves the lengthening of a segment over or more than one slot. Lengthening of this type does not increase the number of the syllable of the root; rather, it involves longer duration within a syllable.

We have presented the various positions with respect to the syllable and the constraints surrounding the distribution of segments and their internal structure in Anaang. Anaang segments have been said to be closely tied up with the internal structure of the syllable. Certain segments are constrained from certain syllable positions. The internal structure of the Anaang syllable is a simple one with no

consonant clusters. These phonotactics further extend to govern the distribution of segments in lexical as well as grammatical constructions in Anaang. Loanwords that do not fit into the structure of the language are further repaired to comply with the Anaang phonotactics. Anaang phonotactics therefore play a vital role in defining a well formed syllable in Anaang, while the structure of the syllable is the basis for all phonological processes in Anaang as is going to be presented in chapter four.

CHAPTER FOUR

SYLLABLE STRUCTURE PROCESSES IN ANAANG

Our concentration in this chapter is on the following syllable structure processes: compensatory lengthening, vowel deletion, vowel assimilation, vowel insertion, parasitic delinking, tonal clustering, vowel harmony, and nasalization, which further illustrate the simple nature of Anaang syllable structure.

4.1 Compensatory Lengthening in Anaang

A concept is termed Compensatory Lengthening (CL) if an adjacent segment spreads its features to occupy a space left behind by a deleted segment (Hayes 1989, Bickmore 1995, Beckman and Edward 1990, Goldsmith 1990). In other words, there must be a pre-existing displaced slot for the segment to spread to, as formalized in rule (1) below

X and Y are on the skeletal tier, Z and N are on a phonemic tier. X is associated to Z, Y that was initially associated to N at an earlier stage of the derivation is deleted as indicated with z. Z spreads rightward and associates to Y by the process of compensatory lengthening as the broken line shows.

Generally, compensatory lengthening is triggered mainly by the deletion of a coda element of the syllable. Let us consider the example in (1)

1.
 - (i) tóp + CV $\longrightarrow$ /tóp m'ó/ $\longrightarrow$ [tó:m'ó] throw (many things)
throw
 - (ii) fúk + CV $\longrightarrow$ /fúk η' / $\longrightarrow$ [fú:η'] uncover
cover
 - (iii) f'p + CV $\longrightarrow$ /f'p m' / $\longrightarrow$ [f':m'] roast
roast
 - (iv) k'k + CV $\longrightarrow$ /k'k η' / $\longrightarrow$ [k':η'] vomit
grind

CV suffix is affixed to the CVC verb to perform certain grammatical functions. Suffixation here creates a CC cluster. The coda element of the verb root is deleted leaving the base with an open syllable structure. This is subsequently followed by the lengthening of an adjacent surviving vowel to compensate for the lost segment as formalized in (2).

2a. (i)	/tóp mo /	CVC-CV	→	[tó:mó]	CVV-CV
(ii)	/fúkŋ ɔ́ /	CVC-CV	→	[fú:ŋɔ́]	CVV-CV
(iii)	/fɔ́ pm ɔ́ /	CVC-CV	→	[fɔ́ : mɔ́]	CVV CV
(iv)	/k ɔ́ kŋɔ́ /	CVCCV	→	[kɔ́ : ŋɔ́]	CVV CV

The deletion of a coda consonant here is necessary to prevent unpreferred consonant sequence. Despite the deletion of one segment, the first syllable which begins with three skeletal slots still surface with three skeletal slots through vowel spreading. The main function of compensatory lengthening in Anaang is to maintain the weight unit of root verb. This process is applicable to other Lower Cross languages like Efik (Cook 1985, Connell 1991), and Ibibio (Urua 2000, 2007). Observe that the first syllable of the base is underlyingly heavy (CVC). Deletion of the coda element leaves the initial syllable with a CV light structure, the adjacent surviving vowel becomes lengthened to maintain the number of the constituents on the rhyme, and to equally maintain the weight unit of the initial syllable as illustrated in example (5).

Apparently, compensatory lengthening is triggered by the deletion of a coda element. Whereas, vowel lengthening can occur without any deletion. This is common in a CV monosyllabic structure. Consider the following data.

2b (i)	/dí/	'come'
(ii)	/ń-díí-Ré/	'I am not coming'
(iii)	/sé/	'look'
(iv)	/ń-séé-Ré/	'I am not looking'
(v)	/tá/	'chew'
(vi)	/ń-táá-ɓá/	'I am not chewing'

-CV suffixation process is used to mark grammatical functions like reversive, frequentation and reflexive among others (Urua 1990). These processes require the initial syllable of the root to be heavy. Therefore the vowel of the root in (2b) is lengthened to satisfy weight requirements in languages even though there is no pre-existing deleted slot. This type of lengthening is common in the Lower -Cross languages (Connell 1991, 1995, Urua 1990, 2007).

Compensatory lengthening does not occur at random. The structure of the syllable plays a vital role in compensatory lengthening in Anaang. Let us consider a structure with CVCCV verb base.

3. CVCCV

- | | | CVCVV | |
|-------|-------------------------------------|--------------|--|
| (i) | /tèkké/ + NV
hold down | → /tèkkéŋé/ | → [tè:ŋé]
'hold down (many things)' |
| (ii) | /bàkká / + NV
share | → /bàkká ŋé/ | → [bà:ŋá]
'share (several times)' |
| (iii) | /fèkké / + NV
dislocate | → /fèkkéŋé/ | → [fè:ŋé]
'dislocate (several times)' |
| (iv) | /dàppá / + NV
remove...from fire | → /dàppáŋé/ | → [dà:má]
'remove many things' |
| (v) | /fikké / + NV
remove wedge | → /fikkéŋé/ | → [fi:ŋé]
'remove (many things)' |
| (vi) | /dippé/ + NV
carry | → /dippéŋé/ | → [dí:mé]
'carry (many things)' |

Items (i-vi) have disyllabic roots where the syllable boundary falls between C₁C₂. CV suffix is equally affixed to this data to perform certain grammatical functions. To achieve this, the second syllable gets deleted thereby reducing the root verb to a CVC syllable.

4.

- (i) /tèkké/ + NV → [tè:ɲé] 'hold down (many things)'
- (ii) /bàká / + NV → [bà:ɲá] 'turn (several times)'
- (iii) /fèkké / + NV → [fè:ɲé] 'carry (many times)'
- (iv) /dàppá / + NV → [dà:má] 'jump (many times)'
- (v) /fikké / + NV → [fi:ɲé] 'lift (many things)'
- (vi) /dippé/ + NV → [di:mé] 'carry (many things)'

In our earlier analysis, geminates have special behaviour of inalterability; where one of the segments cannot be altered by any phonological process except both segments are involved. Therefore the second half of the geminate, which constitutes the coda of the surviving syllable is equally deleted leaving the syllable with a CV structure. This of course is subsequently followed by the lengthening of the root vowel to maintain the weight unit of the affected syllable.

We illustrate this with CV-tier model in (5).

dippé + mé → [di:mé]

In all the examples, compensatory lengthening takes place after the deletion of a constituent of the rhyme. The number of the constituents of the rhyme determines the weight unit of the syllable. In all cases, the verb root must be heavy.

Vowel lengthening is only possible with the deletion of a constituent of the rhyme. Onset constituent does not constitute any weight unit of the syllable in a given language. Deletion of an onset consonant following Hyman (1985), de Carvalho (2002), does not cause compensatory lengthening because onset is not part of the rhyme constituent. Generally, the concept of compensatory lengthening is best understood when enriched within the moraic model of the non-linear framework to clearly demonstrate the number of weight units, which, must necessarily be bi-moraic.

4.2 Vowel Deletion in Anaang

Vowel deletion as a process affects the structure of a syllable in a language. It is one of the processes that is applied to prevent the violation of phonotactic constraints of Anaang. Vowel deletion involves the omission of vowel segment(s) in certain environments. In Anaang vowel deletion is triggered by vowel juxtaposition at syllable boundary. It should however be noted that vowel hiatus is not permitted by Anaang phonotactics in most cases. The syllable boundary therefore acts as a constraint to vowel co-occurrence in Anaang. Deletion rule applies in most cases to prevent such hiatus. Unlike Ibibio (Urua 2000), vowel deletion in Anaang does not occur within the word, it is possible at the phrasal level only. Consider the following example

6.

- | | | | | |
|-------|------------------|--------|--------------|-----------------------|
| (i) | /dómó # àfòŋ/ | —————> | [dómô: fòŋ] | ‘measure ones clothe’ |
| (ii) | /fèRé # itók/ | —————> | [fè Rì: tók] | ‘run a race’ |
| (iii) | /tók # áŋ é/ | —————> | [tók] | ‘hit at him’ |
| (iv) | /bénné # ú bók / | —————> | [b énnú bók] | ‘lift up ones hand’ |

Vowel deletion occurs in (6iii-iv), whereas (6i-ii) involves vowel assimilation process. The above example shows that deletion in this context is predictable. Low vowels get deleted while high vowels survive when the vowels are juxtaposed at syllable boundary.

In Anaang, two syllable heads cannot occur together without an intervening onset. This applies to syllables that end with a vowel before a following onsetless syllable. Again, let us consider the following data.

7. underlying form	underlying form
(i) /m'fudò # úkúm/	/m'fudòúkúm / 'cotton'
(ii) / ndà # ádzò/	/ndàádžò / 'dry season'
(iii) / èkà # ébót/	/èkàébót/ 'a big goat'
(iv) /élémè# ikàŋ/	/élémèikàŋ / 'flame of fire'
(v) / úmàna # àfà/	/úmànààfà/ 'children'
(vi) / m'kpó# étó/	/m'kpó#étó/ 'broken sticks'
(vii) /mbàrá # èkpè/	/mbàráèkpè / 'bramble'

In the course of the derivation of the above lexical items, Anaang syllable constraint is violated by creating dual syllable heads without an intervening consonant as the underlying form in (7) indicates.

To avoid this violation, dual syllable head-pruning rule is applied to resyllabify such a structure. For the pruning to be effective, one of the [+V] contents is deleted as indicated in the surface form in example (8).

8 underlying form		surface form	
(i) /m'fudòúkúm/	N-CV-CV-V-CVC	[m'-fù-dù:-kúm]	N-CV-CV-CVC
(ii) / èkè ébót /	V-CV-V-CVC	[è-kè: -bòt]	V-CVV-CVC
(iii) /mbà#èkpè/	N-CV-CV-V-CV	[m'-bà-rè:-kpè]	N-CV-CVV-CV
(iv) /ndò ádzò/	N-CV-V-CV	[n'-dã:-džò]	N-CVV-CV
(v) /élémèikàŋ/	V-CV-CV-V-CVC	[é-lé-méi-kàŋ]	V-CV-CVV-CVC
(vi) /m'kpó# étó/	N-CV-CV-V-CV	[m'-kpó-#é-tò]	N-CV-CV-CV
(vii) /úmà# àfà /	V-CV-CV-V-CV	[ú-mà-nà-fà]	V-CV-CV-CV

The leftmost syllable is pruned if V_1 is deleted as in (8i-v).

Observe that the data in (8) involves processes. These are vowel deletion and complete vowel assimilation. Complete vowel assimilation involves the deletion of only the phonemic material while the vowel slot remains undeleted (Urua 2000, Nolan 1994, Holst and Nolan 1995). Example (8i-iv) presents a good example of complete vowel assimilation. Complete vowel deletion on the other hand occurs when

a vowel melody with its position on the skeletal slot is deleted as is the case with (8vi-vii). We will make the distinction clearer in the following subsection.

4.2.1 Complete Vowel Deletion.

Vowel deletion in Anaang is conditioned by three factors: height constraints, tones and the structures of the syllable. In our discussion, the representation shall be categorized into two types of the structure of the syllables. These are CV and CVC(C)V.

4.2.1.1 Height Parameter

9. CV structure

loc # noun

(i)	/ké # úf ɔ̃k/	→	[kúf ɔ̃k]	'at home'
(ii)	/ké # ákpá/	→	[kékpá]	'on the water surface'
(iii)	/ké # ábót/	→	[kébót]	'on the hill'
(iv)	/ké # áɲ ^w á/	→	[kéɲ ^w á]	'in the open air'
(v)	/ké # àŋŋɔ̃ŋ/	→	[kéèɔ̃ŋ]	'on top'
(vi)	/ké # èsà/	→	[kéèsà]	'in the lobby'
(vii)	/ké # ini/	→	[kiini]	'on time'
(viii)	/ké # ùrùà/	→	[kùùrùà]	'in the market'

In Ibibio for instance, when two contiguous vowels are juxtaposed at word boundary, deletion will affect a low vowel while a higher vowel survives (Essien 1990, Urua 2000). The same principle applies to Anaang (Udoh 1996, 1997). Deletion can therefore affect either V_1 or V_2 depending on the relative height of the vowels. Generally a high vowel survives while a relatively low vowel gets deleted.

In (9) above, deletion affects V_1 in (i) whereas V_2 is deleted in (ii-iv) depending on the relative heights of the vowel. V_2 is relatively higher than V_1 in (9i). Whereas V_2 is lower than V_1 in (9ii-iv).

This is formalized in (10)

10. Underlying form	syllable structure	heights		deleted segment	tone	surface form	syllable structure
		V ₁	V ₂				
(i) /ké úfɔ̃k/	CV-V-CVC	mid	high	V ₁	H-H-L	[kú-fɔ̃k]	CV-CVC
(ii) /ké ákpá/	CV-V-CV	mid	low	V ₂	H-H-H	[ké-kpá]	CV-CV
(iii) /ké ábót/	CV-V-CVC	mid	low	V ₂	H-H-H	[ké-bót]	CV-CVC
(iv) /ké áŋ ^w á/	CV-V-CV	mid	low	V ₂	H-H-H	[ké-ŋ ^w á]	CV-CV

We illustrate this in 11 below.

Observe that the phonemic material with the V-position on the skeletal slot is deleted. Finally, the penultimate syllable desyllabifies thereby reducing the structure from three to two syllables.

4.2.1.2 Tonal Constraints

Another factor that triggers segment deletion in this context is the tone. A look at the data in (12) shows that complete deletion occurs in (i-iv), whereas (v-vii) undergo an assimilation process. These differences are conditioned by tonal constraints. Like in other Lower Cross languages), specifically, Efik (Cook 1985), and Ibibio (Urua1 987), vowels with unlike adjacent tones cannot undergo complete vowel deletion process. Rather one of the vowels will assimilate to the adjacent vowel even though the vowels have unequal heights as presented in (4.2.1). As earlier stated, complete vowel deletion in Anaang does not occur in an environment of two adjacent unlike tones. Consider the data in (12).

12. CVCCV base

- (i) /bénné # úbɔ́k/ → [bénnúbɔ́k] 'lift up ones hand'
- (ii) /bénné # ídem/ → [bénnídem] 'lift up ones body'
- (iii) /bénné # áɲèn/ → [bénnéɲèn] 'lift up ones eye'
- (iv) /bénné # élɔ́ŋ/ → [bénnéɔ́ŋ] 'lift ones knee'
- (v) /bénné # ùsan/ → [bénnúùsàn] 'carry a plate'
- (vi) /bénné # itɔ́ŋ/ → [bénniitɔ́ŋ] 'lift ones throat'

- (vii) /bénné # àkò/ → [bénnéèkò] 'carry a pot'
 (viii) /bénné # èlèm/ → [bénnéèlèm] 'lift up ones back'

The same principles that apply for CV structure apply here. Observe that V_1V_2 are juxtaposed at word boundary. Vowel deletion occurs in (i-iv) only, owing to the fact that they have adjacent like tonal structures as presented in (13).

13. underlying form	tone	output
(i) /bénné úbɔ́k/	HHHH	[bénnúbɔ́k]
(ii) /bénné idém/	HHHH	[bénnidém]
(iii) /bénné áɲèn/	HHHH	[bénnéɲèn]
(iv) /bénné élɔ́ŋ/	HHHH	[bénnéɔ́ŋ]

However, vowel deletion is blocked by tonal constraints in (13v-viii) rather what obtains is vowel assimilation since the adjacent tones are of unequal pitch.

13. underlying form	tone	output
(v) /bénné ùsàn/	HILL	[bénnúùsàn]
(vi) /bénné ítɔ́ŋ/	HILLH	[bénníítɔ́ŋ]
(vii) /bénnéàkò/	HILL	[bénnéèkò]
(viii) /bénnéèlèm/	HILL	[bénnéèlèm]

4.2.2 Complete Vowel Assimilation

An assimilation is a process where one sound becomes identical with another because of the influence of an adjacent sound (Steriade 1990 Ohala 1990) in a way that neither of the contiguous segments is deleted. Word boundary is a common enabling environment for deletion to occur in Anaang. Let us consider the example in (14).

14.			
(i)	/èté # ádzén/	[ètédz:èn]	father
(ii)	/èté # été/	[èté:té]	grand father
(iii)	/n̄tò # ékpó/	[n̄tè:kpò]	evil agents
(iv)	/èkà # étó/	[èkè:tò]	big tree
(v)	/ísó # ág ^w ó/	[ísó:g ^w ò]	human face
(vi)	/n̄tò # ákpá/	[n̄tò:kpá]	orphans

What obtains here is a complete assimilation rather than deletion since no vowel position in the data is deleted as formalized in (15)

15. underlying	syllable	surface	syllable
form	structure	form	structure
(i)	/èté ádzén/	V-CV-V-CV C	[è-té: -dzèn] V-CVV-CVC
(ii)	/èté été/	V-CV-V-CV	[è-té: -té] V-CVV-CV
(iii)	/n̄tò ékpó/	N-CV-V-CV	[n̄-tè: -kpò] N-CVV-CV
(iv)	/èkà étó/	V-CV-V-CV	[è-kè: -tò] V-CVV-CV
(v)	/ísó ég ^w ót/	V-CV-V-CVC	[í-sá: -g ^w òt] V-CVV-CVC
(vi)	/n̄tò ákpá/	N-CV-V-CV	[n̄-tò: -kpá] N-CVV-CV

Observe that the numbers of the V slots in the data still remain the same after the assimilation process.

Height parameter plays a vital role in this assimilation process. It can be observed that, V₂ assimilates to V₁ in (15iii-vi) owing to the fact that V₂ is relatively lower in height than V₁. Whereas V₂ assimilates to V₁ in (i-ii) since V₂ is higher than V₁. In all the presentations the V slot on the skeleton remains unaffected. It is only the phonemic material that is altered as formalized in (16) with [èkè:tò]

16. Complete vowel assimilation

/əkà# étó/ → [è-k è: -tò]

Assimilation here results in the deletion of the antepenultimate syllable. The melodic material that was earlier anchored to the deleted syllable later becomes associated to the surviving syllable to the right.

4.2.2.1 Anaang Syllable Structure and Complete Vowel Assimilation

As earlier stated, assimilation process is determined by three phonological factors. These are; syllable structure, vowel height, and tonal structure.

The structure of a syllable is determinant factor in complete vowel assimilation process. Secondly, tonal structure constitutes a major constraint to assimilation process. When V_1V_2 are juxtaposed at word boundary, complete deletion is bound to occur (as discussed in 4.2.1.2) if the tones on the juxtaposed vowels are either low-low or high- high. Whereas complete vowel assimilation takes place if the vowels are associated with unlike tones. But this depends sorely on the structure of the syllable of the base as will be seen shortly.

4.2.2.1.1 Structure of the Syllable

As mentioned earlier, like-tonal pattern does not permit complete vowel assimilation. But this constraint is not applicable to VCV syllable or structures with initial syllable prefix.

17a. VCV base form

underlying form	tone	surface form	tone
(i) ñt̃ # ékpó	L-L-H-H	[ñ-t̃: -kpò]	L- LH-L
(ii) èkà # étó	L-L-H-H	[è-k̃: -tò]	L-LH-L
(iii) èté # été	L-H-L-H	[è-té: -té]	L-HH-H
(iv) ísó # ég ^w ót	H-H-H-H	[í-só: -g ^w ót]	H-HH -L
(v) ísó # ág ^w ó	H-H-H-H	[í-só: -g ^w ò]	H-HH- L
(vi) ñt̃ # àkpá	L-L-L-L	[ñ-t̃: -kpá]	L-LH-L
(vii) èté # ádzén	L-H-H-H	[è-té: -adzén]	L-HH-L

(vii) èté # ádzén L-H-H-H [è-té: -adzén] L-HH-L

An examination of the structure of the data in (17a) shows that the base begins with a syllabic prefix thereby producing a VCV syllable structure. The juxtaposed vowels at word boundary have like -tones in (17a iv-vii); while (i-iii) have unlike tones. There is no vowel deletion irrespective of the tonal pattern of the word. What obtains here is complete vowel assimilation.

It can equally be observed that, there is an alteration of the tonal pattern of the data at the surface level. Final high tones are reduced to low tones at the output except in (vi).

The pattern of the tone is borne by the type of construct we are adopting for our discussion. The data in (17a) are compounds constructed from two nouns. Anaang compounds have a fixed tonal pattern irrespective of the tonal pattern of the underlying construct (cf 3.7.1). The tonal realization of the second noun in Anaang compounds is H-L irrespective of the tonal pattern on the words that constitute the compounds. In other words, the final syllable of a compound must have a low tone while the penultimate syllable must be associated with a high tone. The tones on / ètèté/ (i.e. iii), are not altered owing to the fact that the noun is constructed by reduplication and not compounding process.

Observe that in (17a iv), /o/ and /e/ are of equal height. Vowel deletion does not occur here. Rather, there is a kind of vowel merging where /o/ and /e/ change to the mid central vowel [ə]. This leads to the generalization that the juxtaposition of mid vowels in V_1V_2 environment in most instances triggers vowel coalescence rather than deletion. The new segment shares the feature specification of the two underlying vowels i.e. [-high] [-low] but differs in [$\pm$ backness]. More examples follow.

17b /àkò/ # /ékpó/	[àkǒkpò]	'evil pot'
/ísó/ # /ékpó/	[ísá:kpò]	'masque'
/m̀kpóRó/ # /étó/	[m̀kpóR á:tò]	'broken sticks'
/àkò/ # /ég ^w á/	[àkǒ:g ^w à]	'dogs pot'

/ékpó/ # /èkà/

[ékpâ:kà] 'very poor mother'

This type of merging is known as reciprocal assimilation (Crystal 1997) (or what Schane (1996) calls fusion) since one cannot really determine which segment triggers the assimilation process.

Let us consider structures with initial consonant segment repeated here as (18).

18 CV/CVCCV Base

(i)	/ké # àṅṅ/	[kéèṅṅ]	'on top'
(ii)	/ké # èsà/	[kéèsà]	'at the balcony'
(iii)	/ké # ìní/	[kîni]	'in time'
(iv)	/ké # ùrùà/	[kúùrùà]	'at the market'
(V)	/bénné # ìbà/	[bénnîbà]	'carry two'
(vi)	/bénné # ùsàn/	[bénnúùsàn]	'carry...plate'
(vii)	/bénné # itṅ/	[bénnîitṅ]	'lift up ...neck'
(viii)	/bénné # àkò/	[bénnéèkò]	'carry pot'

Tone and vowel height play a vital role in the deletion or assimilation of a vowel in a contiguous context in CV or CVC-CV structure. Observe that V_1V_2 in (18) are associated with unlike-tones, which trigger complete vowel assimilation. A low vowel assimilates to a higher vowel as presented in (19)

19. Underlying form	syllable structure	segment affected	tone	output	syllable structure
(i) /kéàṅṅ/	CV-V-CVC	V_2	HLH	[ké:ṅṅ]	CVV-CVC
(ii) /kéini/	CV-V-CV	V_1	HLL	[kî:ni]	CVV CV
(iii) /kéùrùà/	CV-V-CVV	V_1	H L L L	[kù:rùà]	CVV-CVV
(iv) /bénnéìbà/	CVC-CV-V-CV	V_1	H H L L	[bénnî:bà]	CVC-CVV-CV
(v) /bénnéùsàn/	CVC-CV-V-CVC			V_1 HHL[bénnú:sàn]	CVC-CVV-CVC
(vi) /bénnéitṅ/	CVC-CV-V-CVC	V_1	HHLH	[bénnî:itṅ]	CVC-CVV-CVC
(vii) /bénnéèkò/	CVC-CV-V-CV	V_2	HHLL	[bénné:kò]	CVC-CVV-CV

In all the cases, the penultimate syllable desyllabifies even though no vowel is deleted.

4.2.3 Height Parameter Vs Environment

Even though vowel deletion is determined by height, this prediction is not constant. In some instances unlike-vowel sequences survive deletion at syllable boundary. In all situations, a low vowel is always affected if deletion must occur, while a relatively high vowel survives irrespective of the environment. Generally, vowel deletion in Anaang is blocked by the high vowels /i/ and /u/, if the first word has an initial vocalic syllabic segment. For the purpose of illustration, we hereby present each of the high vowels in Anaang as they occur in non-deleting environment.

4.2.3.1 High Vowels

If the high vowels /u, i/ occur in V_1 position vowel deletion is blocked irrespective of the tonal structure or the height of a following segment. Therefore, height parameter plays no role in this context. Let us consider example involving /u/.

4.2.3.1.1 /u/ in V_1 position

20.underlying form	syllable structure	surface form	syllable structure
(i) /èdù # ìbàk/	V-CV-V-CV	[è dùìbàk]	V-CVV-CV
		wicked behaviour	
(ii) /èdù # ékpò/	V-CV-V-CV	[è dùákpò]	V-CVV-CV
		wicked attitude	
(iii) /èdù # ábòt/	V-CV-V-CVC	[è dùábòt]	V-CVV-CVC
		natural attitude	

/u/ is described as a high rounded vowel. When /u/ occurs as V_1 at syllable

boundary, before a following vowel (either high or non-high) no deletion can take place. Rather what obtains is the transformation of a following vowel to either a glide or a central vowel. This is followed by disyllabification, where the penultimate syllable desyllabifies to a preceding syllable, thereby making a four syllabic word to surface as three (i.e. V-CV-V-CV(C) to surface as V-CVV-CV(C) structure).

4.2.3.1.2 /u/ in V₂ position

When /u/ occurs as V₂ at syllable boundary, no deletion occurs either. Observe that what occurs here is complete vowel change. We therefore posit that the high vowel /u/ blocks deletion at syllable boundary in certain instances. Even if no segment is deleted or assimilated, dual syllable head constraint is not violated. This shows that every process occurs to respect syllable constraints.

underlying form	syllable structure	affected segment	surface form	syllable structure
/èté # úfɛ̀k/	V-CV-V-CV C	V ₁	[ètəú:fɛ̀k] master	V-CVV-CVC
/ǹtè # úfɛ̀k/	N-CV-V-CV C	V ₁	[ntəú:fɛ̀k] house helps	N-CVV-CVC
/èkà # úfɛ̀k/	V-CV-V-CVC	V ₁	[èkəú:fɛ̀k] mistress	V-CVV-CVC
/isó # ùkùùt/	V-CV-V-CVC	V ₁	[isəù:kù:t] distressed	V-CVV-CVC

4.2.3.1.3 /i/ in V₁ position

The same process that occurs in the deletion of /u/ in V₁ position applies here.

(22) underlying form	syllable structure	surface form	syllable structure
----------------------	--------------------	--------------	--------------------

/éí # àg ^w ó/	V-CV-V-CV	[éíàg ^w ò]	V-CVV-CV	a good person
/éí # èkà /	V-CV-V-CV	[éíàkà]	V-CVV-CV	a good mother
/éí # ùkót/	V-CV-V-CVC	[éíùkòt]	V-CVV-CVC	a good leg

In Anaang, the vowels that can co-occur with another vowel in a cluster are the high vowels /i/ or /u/. In (22) V₁ is the high vowel /i/. Juxtaposition of V₁V₂ here does not trigger vowel deletion; what obtains is disyllabification of the penultimate syllable to a preceding syllable so that a four-syllable word manifests three syllables. The same result occurs if /i/ is in V₂ position as presented below.

4.2.3.1.4 /i/ in V₂ position

underlying form	syllable structure	surface form	
(i) /èdù # ibàk/	V-CV-V-CV	[èdùibàk]	V-CVV -CV wicked behaviour
(ii) /èté # ílùj/	V-CV-V-CVC	[ètéílùj]	V-CVV -CVC king
(iii) /n̄t̄ó # ín̄ó/	N-CV-V-CV	[n̄t̄óín̄ó]	N-CVV -CV young thieves
(iv) /èkà # ílíén /	V-CV-V-CVVC	[èkàílié:n]	V-CVV -CVVC a proper woman
v) /ísó # ibàk/	V-CV-V-CVC	[ísóibàk]	V-CVV -CVC wicked appearance

The structure of the syllable plays a vital role in the deletion process involving /i/ as V₂. Apart from a situation where we have the locative /ke/ as a CV base, none of the vowels can be deleted if the first word has a CV structure except in a situation where /i/ occurs as V₂.

4.3 Vowel Insertion in Anaang

Anaang employs strategies such as deletion or insertion to 'repair' imperfect syllables. An inserted segment is an empty structural position whose presence is required by language-specific 'phonotactics' (Davis 1995). Thus phonotactics defines whether or not consonant clustering is allowed. In other words, insertion is driven by an imperfect match between input segments and the syllable structure requirement. For instance, when the syllable contains a cluster of consonants, whereas the language requires no such clustering, syllabification then enforces the separation of the clusters by providing an empty vowel position which was not filled by the input.

Vowel insertion rule applies in Anaang specifically to parse consonant clusters. It can equally be applied to repair word class structure or to prevent unpreferred sequences. Example follows.

- 24 (i) kèèt kèèt → kèèt(è)kèèt → [kèèrèkèèt] 'one by one'
 (ii) èfút kèèt → èfút(ò)kèèt → [èfùròkèèt] 'fifteen'
 (iii) dùòp kèèt → dùòp(ò)kèèt → [dùòβòkèèt] 'eleven'

Here vowel epenthesis occurs between two roots to prevent unpreferred consonant sequences rather than parse clusters. Recall that Anaang phonotactics do not permit consonant sequences other than nasal stop segments. Therefore epenthesis applies to parse /t k/ or /p k/ sequences respectively.

a. In (24i), /e/ is inserted between C₁C₂ where /e/ copies the vowel of the underlying word.

b. Epenthetic /o/ is applied to parse the consonant sequences in (ii) & (iii).

Various other processes that occur here after the insertion include:

- i. Insertion here changes the position of the consonants /t / from syllable coda position to the onset position (intervocalic context) as illustrated in (24b) below with /kèèrèkèèt/.

- ii. There is a modification of the feature specification of the consonant that precedes the inserted vowel where /t/ becomes a tap.
- iii. The voiceless stops /t/ and /p/ undergo a process of voicing intervocalically.
- iv. The intervocalic stops are weakened to their homorganic continuants i.e. tap or fricative respectively so that /t/ → [ɾ], and /p/ → [β]

Another type of insertion is seen in connected speech. In connected speech, a vowel is sometimes inserted between a verb and a personal name or a proper noun. Example follows.

25. Verbs		personal names	
wòt	'kill'	Ñsè	'kill Nse'
dóm	'bite'	M̀kpá	'bite Mkpá'
kúm	'piercer'	M̀bòhó	'pierce Mboho'

The personal names begin with a syllabic nasal in (25). But in connected speech, a vowel is inserted before the nasal so that we have a structure such as presented in example (26).

26.	wòt (á) Ñsè	wòt	Ánsè
	dóm (á) M̀kpá	dóm	Ám̀kpá
	kúm (á) M̀bòhó	kúm	Ám̀bòhó

This is formalized as follows.

27.	wòt	á	nsè	→	wòtánsè	→	[wò-rá-ń- sè]
	dóm	á	m̀kpá	→	dómám̀kpá	→	[dó- má-m- kpá]

kúm á mbòhó → kúmám̀bòhó → [kú-má-m̀- b̀ò-ɓó]

The vowel /a/ is inserted before the noun to give the noun an initial vocalic element. This process occurs mainly in pronunciation but not in the written form. Speakers of the Anaang language can intuitively know when to insert a vowel in a string of speech. Based on this, personal names in strings of words are written the same way as they appear in isolation.

4.4 Parasitic Delinking

According to onset-rhyme theory (Ewen and Hulst 2001), onset on its own cannot constitute a syllable because it is not a syllabic segment. Onset can only be combined with the nucleus to constitute a syllable. Therefore, when a syllabic or nuclear segment is deleted or gets assimilated in some instances, especially where the affected syllable has just one nuclear segment, this process will affect the syllable. When a syllable is left with no overt nuclear segment, the affected syllable gets deleted from the syllable tier by stray erasure leaving a floating consonant behind. This is known as 'parasitic delinking' (Bickmore 1995). Let us consider the following example.

28.(i)	ké # i ɲ ^w á ɲ	→	[kî: ɲ ^w á ɲ]
	loc farm		in the farm
(ii)	èka # étó	→	[èkě: tò]
	big tree		big tree
(iii)	èka # ébót	→	[èkě :b̀òt]
	big goat		a big goat

This is formalized thus

29. Underlying form	parasitic delinking	parasitic relinking
(i) ké i ɲ ^w á ɲ CV-V-CVC	→ /k ɔ i ɲ ^w á ɲ/ CØ-V-CVC	→ [kî:- ɲ ^w á ɲ]
(ii) èkà étó V-CV-V-CV	→ /è k ɔ étó/ V-CØ-V-CVC	→ [è-kě:-tò]
(iii) èkà ébót V-CV-V-CVC	→ /è k ɔ ébót/ V-CØ-V-CV	→ [è-kě : -b̀òt]

The data in (29) shows the loss of V_1 element in a $V_1\#V_2$ sequence. If the preceding syllable has a CV structure, the loss of a V from a CV structure therefore results in a syllable with just a C structure. C on its own cannot constitute a well formed syllable. Therefore, the syllable that was initially associated with the CV element gets deleted as a result of the absence of an overt nuclear (V) element. The deletion of the syllable equally affects the consonant. The surviving consonant is regarded as extrasyllabic element (Hyman 1985), since it is left in a state of pendulum with no overt syllable to dock on. The outcome is that the delinked segment becomes subsequently relinked with an adjacent onsetless syllable to the right, 'tonal relinking'. (This is illustrated in example 30)

Observe that the phonemic material of the first syllable is deleted leaving the affected syllable with no overt vowel segment. This leads to the displacement of the initial syllable node thereby leaving consonant segment in a state of limbo as shown in (30c).

The unassociated CV elements on the melodic tier become relinked with the adjacent syllable node to the right.

4.5 Tonal Clustering

In tonal languages, tone is said to be a feature of the syllable in the sense that every syllable must have at least one tone. No syllable can exist without tone. Tonal clustering as a process is triggered by the deletion of a tone bearing unit usually a vowel. In most cases, the deletion of a vowel does not affect the tone since tone, according to Goldsmith (1990), is autonomous and independent of the segment. Rather, it leaves the tone in a state of limbo i.e. dangling without any segment to dock on. The delinked tone spreads and gets realigned to the adjacent vowel, which, according to Goldsmith (1990), is "the linguistic clue to stability of tone". This results in tonal clustering either high-low or low-high, as shown in the following example.

- | | | | |
|---------|---------------|---|------------------|
| 31. (i) | tʃíné # áfɔ́ŋ | → | [tʃíné:fɔ́ŋ] |
| | wear clothe | | wear ones clothe |
| (ii) | èté # àdʒít | → | [è tē: dʒít] |
| | father we | | our father |
| (iii) | tù dó# útɔ́k | → | [tùrú: tɔ́k] |
| | stop quarrel | | stop quarrelling |
| (iv) | dʒàrá # itám | → | [dʒà rî:t à m] |
| | wear hat | | put on a hat |
| (v) | èkà # áddʒén | → | [èkǎ:dʒèn] |
| | mother child | | mother |

(vi) èsà # ékò porch	→	[èsě:kò] lobby
(vii) ènǎ # énǎ gift	→	[ènǎ:nǎ] double gift
(vi) àkpò # úkùàk scale iron	→	[àkpǔ:kùàk] nail

The above representation simply illustrates the deletion of a tone-bearing unit which in turn results in tonal spreading to adjacent vowel to produce a kind of tonal cluster. Note however that this process is feasible only in the environment of $V_1\#V_2$ sequence with unlike tones. Details are presented below.

32.	underlying form	tone	syllable structure	surface form	tone	syllable structure
(i)	tʃínéàfǎŋ	HH L L	CV-CV-V-CVC	[tʃíné:fǎŋ]	H HL L	CV-CVV-CVC
(ii)	èté àdʒit	L H L L	V-CV-V-CVC	[è t é: dʒit]	H HL L	CV-CVV-CVC
(iii)	tùdóútǎk	L H L L	CV-CV-V-CVC	[tùrú:tǎk]	H HL L	CV-CVV-CVC
(iv)	dʒàrá itàm	L H L L	CV-CV-V-CVC	[dʒà rí:t à m]	H HL L	CV-CVV-CVC
(v)	èkà ádʒén	LL H H	V-CV-V-CVC	[èkà:dʒén]	L LH L	V CVV CVC
(vi)	èsà ékò	LL H L	V-CV-V-CV	[èsě:kò]	L LH L	V-CVV-CV
(vii)	ènǎ énǎ	LL H L	V-CV-V-CV	[ènǎ:nǎ]	L LH L	V-CVV-CV
(viii)	àkpòúkùàk	LL H L	V-CV-V-CVC	[àkpǔ:kùàk]	L LH L	V-CVV-CVC

Example (32i-iv) shows juxtaposition of HL tonal sequence at syllable internal position. Whereas (v-viii) presents the juxtaposition of LH tonal sequence. Observe that each item in the underlying representation has a level tone either high or low. Whereas the penultimate syllable at the surface level has a complex tonal structure, either low-high or high-low as illustrated in (33). Observe equally that tonal clusters in Anaang does not occur syllable initially or syllable finally, it occurs in syllable internal position only. Equally, this process does not occur at the lexical level it occurs only at phrasal level. Finally it occurs in V_1V_2 sequence at syllable boundary and not elsewhere.

33. t̩d̩òùt̩k̩ → [t̩r̩ù: t̩k̩] stop quarreling

4.6 Vowel Harmony

The concept of vowel harmony is widespread in the phonological literature on African languages (Clements and Railland 2008). Others include (Essien 1990,

Oyebade 1998, Cook 1985, Connell 1991, Urua 2007). Vowel harmony is known as non-contiguous or distant assimilation following Goldsmith (1993), Crystal (1997), Roca and Johnson (1999), since the vowels harmonize with a distant vowel in a particular domain, which of course is the syllable. Distant assimilation, following Bakovic (2007), obtains between segments that are not necessarily adjacent. Archangeli and Pulleyblank (2007:257) provide a list of harmonic features to include rounding, backness, nasality, Tongue Root Advancement (ATR) among others.

Proponents of binary feature system have indeed argued that there are vowel harmonic systems which involve [$\pm$ Back], [$\pm$ ATR]. In this case, vowel harmony is seen as a state in which segments agree with respect to some feature value within the relevant domain. Unlike the binary system proposed by Chomsky and Halle (1968), autosegmental phonology allows us to represent cases in which segments agree with respect to feature specification in terms of multiple associations or sharing.

Harmonic systems differ from language to language. Turkish has rounding vowel harmony system (Odden 2005:209). Tangale (spoken in Bauchi State), for instance, has a vowel harmony system based on the open-close distinction. This is called a "Cross-Height" harmonic system (Hulst & Weijer 1996), or a Tongue Root harmonic system. Tongue Root harmonic system may be analysed in different ways, viz: Advanced or Retracted Tongue Root, or in terms of binary equivalent [$\pm$ ATR], [$\pm$ High]. A language like Igbo has a typical Tongue Root harmonic system where all the vowels in a word must agree with either [$\pm$ ATR]. Languages that attest this process following Oyebade (1998), impose the constraint of allowing vowels from a particular group to co-occur in a well defined domain to the exclusion of members of other groups. Yoruba, for instance, has three groups of vowels: /e, o/ /e, ɔ/ and /i, u, a/ respectively. /e, o/ can co-occur with each other but cannot co-occur with the second group. Equally, /e, ɔ/ can co-occur with each other but cannot co-occur with /e, o/. Whereas /i, u, a/ can co-occur with each other and also with /e, o/ and /e, ɔ/. (See Oyebade 1998, for illustrations)

Anaang has seven phonemic vowels /a e i o ɔ u ʉ/. These vowels are grouped into two sets: A. /i u ʉ/

B. /a e o ɔ/.

The vowels in group 'B' are constrained from co-occurring with each other (i.e. within the group). A member of this group can only occur as a copy of itself. In other words, none of the members of the vowels of group 'B' can harmonize with any other member of this group unless as a copy of itself.

34a.

(i)	kɔ́ɔ́	'hang'	/kɔ́ɔ́/	'remove...from rope'
(ii)	tèm	'cook'	/tèmmé/	'bring down...from fire'
(iii)	kɔ́p	'lock'	/kɔ́ppɔ́/	'un-hang'
(iv)	bót	'mould'	/bóró/	'build up yourself'

On the other hand, vowels in group B can co-occur with vowels in group A. However, the vowels in group A cannot co-occur with each other. Where the vowels in group A & B interact, the vowels in group A must necessarily be restricted to the root only, while those in group B must be restricted to the suffix as seen in example (34b).

34b. (i)	dʒít	'lock'	/dʒítte/	'unlock'
(ii)	fúk	'cover'	/fúkɔ́/	'cover oneself'

These constraints on Anaang vowel harmony centers specifically on verb roots. The verb root with [+back] feature in group A takes on a harmonizing [+back] vowel from group B, whereas a verb root with [-back] vowel feature in group A harmonises with [-back] vowel feature from group B. This shows that the vowels in group A always occur at the verb root while the vowels in group B must necessarily occur at the suffix if they are to co-occur for harmonic purpose. However, such restrictions do not hold for vowels in group B. Where any of the vowels from group B occurs at the root verb, the vowel will spread its features rightward without any modification. In other words each of the vowels in group B occurs as a complete copy of itself at the suffix if such a vowel first occurs as the vowel of the verb root as formalized in (34).

35.

(i)	kɔŋ 'hang'	/kɔŋŋɔ́/	'remove...from rope'
(ii)	tèm 'cook'	/tèmmé/	'bring down...from fire'
(iii)	dʒ àt 'crown'	/dʒàrà/	'crown yourself'
(iv)	bùm 'roast'	/m'-bùmmó/	'...not roasting'
(v)	fúk cover	/fúkɔ́/	cover oneself (reflexive)
(vi)	dʒàt wear (on the head)	/dʒ àrà /	wear ...on ones head "
(vii)	g ^w èt write	/g ^w èré/	write... on ones body
(viii)	tɔ́ hit	/n- tɔ́:ɔ́/	...not hitting (negation)
(ix)	sé look	/n-sé:Ré/	...not looking "
(x)	bó say	/m'-bóóɔ́/	...not saying (negation)

Vowel harmony in Anaang is not harmony of Cross-Height or ATR type, but a process whereby the vowel of the affix harmonises with the vowel of the stem in terms of [± Back] feature or what Hulst and Weijer (1996:522) refers to as Labial harmonic system. Labial harmonic system, according to Hulst and Weijer is wide spread in Uralic languages like (Finish, Hungarian, Cheremis, Kirjiz & Tungusic). Other Lower Cross languages attest the same height and backness characteristics (Urua 2000). Harmonic system is predictable in Anaang. Let us consider the following data.

(36) Vowel harmony in monosyllabic verb root

(i)	dù be alive	/n'-dù:ɔ́/	...not living
(ii)	má love	/m'-má:ɔ́/	...not in love with
(iii)	dí come	/n'-dí:Ré/	...not coming
(v)	bùm roast	/m'-bùmmó/	...not roasting
(v)	fɔ́n be good	/m'-fɔ́nnɔ́/	... not good enough
(vi)	fúk cover	/fúkɔ́/	uncover (reversive)
(vii)	kɔŋ hang	/kɔŋŋɔ́/	remove...from rope

(viii)	tèm	cook	/tèmmé/	bring down...from fire
(x)	dʒít	lock	/dʒítté/	unlock
(x)	kɔ̀p	lock	/kɔ̀ppɔ̀/	un-hang

In the example above, the vowel at the suffix position harmonizes with all or some of the features of the vowel(s) as determined by the phonological environment. This is formalized in (37).

(37)	personal marker	syllable structure	- CVsuffix	output	syllable structure
(i)	kɔ̀p	CVC	pɔ̀	[kɔ̀p -pɔ̀]	CVC-CV
(ii)	kɔ̀ŋ	CVC	ŋɔ̀	[kɔ̀ŋ -ŋɔ̀]	CVC-CV
(iii)	tèm	CVC	mé	[tèm -mé]	CVC CV
(iv)	bùm	CVC	mó	[m̄-bùm -mó]	CVC-CV
(v)	fɛ́k	CVC	ɔ̀	[fɛ́ ɔ̀]	CV-CV
(vi)	dʒàt	CVC	á	[dʒà rá]	CV-CV
(vii)	g ^w èt	CVC	é	[g ^w è ré]	CV-CV
(viii)	ń	CV	ɛ́ é	[ń- sé: -Ré]	CVV-CV
(ix)	m̄	CV	ɛ́ ó	[m̄-bó: -ɛ́ ó]	CVV-CV
(x)	m̄	CVV	ɛ́ á	[m̄-má: -Rá]	CVV-CV
(xi)	ń	CV	Ré	[ń-dí: -Ré]	CVV-CV
(xii)	ń	CV	ɛ́ ɔ̀	[ń-dù: -ɛ́ ɔ̀]	CV-CV

A-CV suffix is affixed to the verb root to perform negative, reversive, and reflexive functions respectively. It can be observed that the feature specification of the suffix consonant is determined by the syllable structure of the verb root. -RV suffix is attached to monosyllabic roots with open syllable structure (37iv-viii) to produce the structure in (38a).

38a. personal marker		syllable structure	-RV suffix	output	syllable structure
(i)	ń sé	CV	Ré	[ń- sé: -Ré]	CVV-CV
	look			- not looking	
(ii)	ń bó	CV	ʙ ó	[ń- bó: -ʙó]	CVV-CV
	collect			- not collecting	
(iii)	ń má	CVV	ʙ á	[ń- má: -ʙá]	CVV-CV
	love			-not in love with	
(iv)	ń dí	CV	Ré	[ń- dí: -Ré]	CVV-CV
	come			-not coming	
(v)	ń dù	CV	ʙ ɔ́	[ń- dù: -ʙɔ́]	CV-CV
	be alive			- not alive	

In a CV verb root, the vowel of the verb is lengthened for vowel harmony to occur since vowel harmony in Anaang cannot occur in a light syllable root. Lengthening here is automatic without any previous segment deletion. The structure of the suffix is determined by the syllable structure of the root verb and by the grammatical function of the verb.

Close monosyllabic roots have a -CV suffix; where -C must copy all the feature specifications of the final consonant of the verb root thereby resulting in consonant gemination as presented in (38b).

38b. (i)	tèm	CVC	mé	[tèm-mé]	CVC-CV
	cook			bring down the cooking from fire	
(ii)	bùm	CVC	mó	[ń-bùm-mó]	CVC-CV
	roast			..not roasting	

This process occurs when the coda element of the root verb has [+Nasal] feature. Secondly,

a -CV suffix is affixed to verb roots to perform grammatical functions other than reflexive.

But in reflexive constructions (39), only a -V is affixed to the root even though the verb root has a CVC structure.

39.	root	syllable structure	-V suffix	output	syllable structure
(i)	fúk ver	CVC	ś	[fúks̄] cover oneself	CV-CV
(ii)	džát crown	CVC	á	[džárá] crown oneself	CV-CV
(iii)	g ^w èt write	CVC	é	[g ^w èré] write on oneself	CV-CV

If the verb root has a CV open syllable structure, the vowel of the root must be lengthened for vowel harmony to occur. This lengthening is not triggered by any previous loss of segment. The premise is that the initial syllable of the word must have a heavy structure in Anaang harmonic system.

It should however be noted that the structure of the syllable plays a vital role in Anaang harmonic system. Vowel harmony occurs in only monosyllabic roots. Disyllabic roots do not respond to harmonic system. In example (40), the - CV suffix /-ke/ is affixed to disyllabic root irrespective of the quality of the root vowel.

40.	verb root	syllable structure	-ke suffix	output	syllable structure
(i)	tjèémé lament	CVV-CV	/ké/	[ń-tjèéméké] ...not lamenting	N- CVV-CV-CV
(ii)	bénné carry	CVC-CV	/ké/	[m'-bénnéké] ...not carrying	N- CVC-CV-CV
(iii)	fèRé run	CV-CV	/ké/	[m'-fèRéké] ...not running	N- CV-CV-CV
(iv)	fidé forget	CV-CV	/ké/	[m'-fidéké] ...not forgetting	N- CV-C-CV

Other vowels have copying or what Essien (1990), Kiparsky (1987), Goldsmith (1990, 1993), Ewen and Hulst (2001) refer to as complete vowel harmony. This shows that we have two types of vowel harmony in Anaang. These are partial and complete vowel harmony.

4.6.1 Complete Vowel Harmony

In complete vowel harmony system, the vowel of the suffix copies all the feature specification of the root vowel. Example follows.

41.	Prefix	root	syllable structure	-CV suffix	output	syllable structure
(i)		kɔ̌p- lock	CVC	pɔ̌	[kɔ̌p-pɔ̌] unlock	CVC-CV
(ii)		kɔ̌ŋ hang	CVC	ŋɔ̌	[kɔ̌ŋ-ŋɔ̌] remove ...from hooks	CVC-CV
(iii)		tɛ̌m cook	CVC	mɛ̌	[tɛ̌m-mɛ̌] bring down ...from fire	CVC-CV
(iv)	ń-	sé look	CV	ʋé	[ń- sé: -Ré] ...not lookoing	CVV-CV
(v)	m̄-	bó say	CV	ʋó	[m̄-bó: -ʋó] ... saying	CVV-CV
(vi)	m̄-	má love	CV	ʋá	[m̄-má: -Rá] ...not loving	CVV-CV

In items (41 i – iv), the vowel of the suffix harmonises with all the features of the root vowel after an adjacent consonant. This process is a good example of complete harmonic system. In the above example, if the syllable of the root is a light syllable (i.e. monosyllabic verb), the vowel becomes lengthened when a suffix is added to the verb root as the in examples (iv) – (v). However, if the weight unit of the syllable of the root verb is heavy, no vowel lengthening is involved as in items (i) - (ii). As already stated, the vowels could equally harmonize with part of the vowel features of the root resulting in partial harmonic system.

4.6.2 Partial vowel harmony

Partial vowel harmony system in Anaang occurs in a context where the vowel of the verb root has a high vowel, either /i/ or /u/.

	Prefix	root		suffix	output	
42.						
(i)	ń	dí	CV	Ré	[ń-dí:-Ré]	CVV-CV
		come			...not coming	
(ii)	ń	dù	CV	ɛ́	[ń-dù:-ɛ́]	CVV-CV
		live			...not living	
(iii)	ḿ	bùm	CVC	mó	[ḿ-bùmmó]	CVC-CV
		roast			...not roasting	

In item (42 i), the root vowel /i/ harmonises with [e] at the suffix, while the root vowel /u/ harmonises with /ɔ/ at the suffix (42ii-iii). Observe that /i/ and /e/ are front vowels; as a result, the high vowel /i/ agrees in [-backness] with /e/. Whereas /u/ agrees in [+backness] with /ɔ/. In this case, the vowel at the suffix position harmonizes with some of the feature specifications of the root vowel being [±backness]. High vowels therefore agree mainly in [±backness] in Anaang. Certain suffixes in Anaang are therefore conditioned by vowel harmony. Note however that the vowel of the root is higher than the vowel of the suffix in partial vowel harmony.

The weight unit of the root verb is equally of utmost importance. For vowel harmonic process to occur in Anaang, the verb root must necessarily be heavy either CVV or CVC. The premise is that vowel harmony in Anaang does not occur in light syllables. As a result where the root is underlyingly light (i.e. CV structure); the vowel becomes automatically lengthened to increase the weight unit to a heavy structure (42 i-ii). Vowel lengthening here is not triggered by deletion of any type, rather it occurs in other to maintain uniformity on the weight unit of the base. In all these cases, vowel harmony does not occur with prefixes. We can therefore conclude that Anaang has progressive harmonic system only.

Generally, vowel harmony has the effect of making segments more like each other. In most cases, either the triggering or the targeted set of segments is a subset of the segment which are compatible with the harmonic feature in the language.

4.7 Nasalization

Nasalization occurs when an oral sound is produced through both oral and nasal cavities. In this case, the velum is lowered partially, so that the air from the lungs passes through both oral and nasal cavities (Clark and Yallop 1994). Let us consider the following examples:

43. Nasalization

underlying representation	surface form	syllable structure	affected segments	gloss
(i) /i!ném/	[i!nēm]	V-CVC	[e]	sweetness
(ii) /nék/	[něk]	CVC	[e]	dance
(iii) /tímmé/	[tĩmmě]	CVC-CV	[i.e]	stay back
(iv) /nǎ́: ŋ ǎ́/	[nǎ́: ŋ ǎ́]	CVV-CV	[ɔ:]	spoonfeed

The vowels in (46) are nasalized in the environment of an adjacent nasal segment. Observe that in (46i), the vowel in the first syllable is not nasalized owing to the absence of a nasal segment within the syllable.

Nasalization cannot occur across syllable boundary in Anaang. Syllable boundary therefore poses a constraint against nasalization. We therefore conclude that there must be an adjacent nasal segment within a syllable to trigger the nasalization of the vowel(s). Observe equally that all the vowels are nasalized in (ii-iv) owing to the influence of the presence of adjacent nasal segments in each of the syllables. It should, however, be emphasized here that nasalization is restricted to the vowels only. Consonants cannot be nasalized in Anaang. All the vowels within the syllable can be nasalized so long as there is an adjacent nasal segment as in item (ii) where [i] and [e] are nasalized. Nasalization of vowels here is possible because of the presence of nasal segment and there is no syllable boundary to block the spread of the influence of the nasal feature.

Nasalization can be anticipatory or preservative (Giegerich 1992). This shows that nasalization can spread to both left and right directions (bidirectional) as in examples (iii-iv). The word [tĩmmě] has two syllables; the vowel in the first syllable assimilates regressively to the nasal feature of a following segment. Whereas, the vowel of the second syllable becomes nasalized progressively to the nasal feature of a preceding segment. Nasalization is merely phonetic in Anaang since there is no

contrast between nasalized and oral vowels in Anaang. This type of process is regarded as a natural phonological process, because it is generally believed that it is easy in some instances to spread nasality to oral segment to give the vowel segment a secondary feature of [+nasality] in the environment of an adjacent nasal consonant.

4.8 Reduplication Processes in Anaang

The role of reduplication in word formation in Anaang has been exhaustively explored in sections (3.6.3.1, 3.6.4.1 and 3.5.1) respectively. In this section, we shall identify, classify and discuss the various phonological processes of reduplication in Anaang and analyse the effects of these processes on the internal structure of Anaang.

Reduplication cuts across both phonology and morphology (Spencer 1991, Steriade 1998).

From a morphological point of view, reduplication involves a kind of affixation, both in its morpho-syntactic contribution (it forms morphological category such as plural), and its linear position with respect to the stem (preceding it as prefix or following it as suffix). Phonologically, reduplication is a phenomenon involving phonological identity between the 'reduplicant' and the 'base' to which it adjoins. Generally, reduplication refers to a word formation process that copies all or part of a word or phrase (Urbanczyk 1999, 2007). It is a common feature of Bantu languages (Downing 1999), Lower Cross languages (Urua 1990), Nilotic languages (Dimmendaal 2000)

Two types of reduplication have been identified in the literature. These include complete and partial reduplication (Katamba 1993).

Complete reduplication involves copying of a complete word (Steriade 1992). There is both segmental and non-segmental resemblance between the base and the reduplicant. Example follows.

44. (i)/mǎ́ŋ/ → [mǎ́ŋ-mǎ́ŋ]

grace

gracefully

Partial reduplication on the other hand copies only part of the segment of the base as in example(45).

45. /fě̀Ré/ → [fě̀:fě̀Ré]

run

run continuously

Partial reduplication in (45) above copies only the first syllable of the base and prefixes it to the base form. Each of these processes shall be discussed separately for more clarification.

4.8.1 Partial Reduplication

Partial reduplication emerges first as total reduplication. The segmental and non-segmental structures of the base are first copied before the elimination and restructuring of the syllable including tone. In other words, partial reduplication is a subtype of stem elimination or simplification.

Earlier analysis viewed reduplication as segment copying and association (Urua 1990). In this case association of copied segments was treated as a segment driven process. This shows that affixation of a -CV suffix to a CVC base will yield line crossing line in autosegmental representation. This is illustrated with

/dép/ → [dèppè] 'not buying'

46.
$$\begin{array}{c} C & V & C & + & CV \\ | & | & | & & \\ d & e & p & & \end{array} \rightarrow \begin{array}{c} C & V & C & + & C & V \\ | & | & | & & | & | \\ d & e & p & & & \end{array} \rightarrow \begin{array}{c} C & V & C & \acute{C} & V \\ | & | & | & / & | \\ d & e & p & p & e \\ & & & & [dèppè] \end{array}$$

In our analysis, reduplication is not segment driven but syllable driven. Partial reduplication therefore copies the initial syllable of the base with some modifications

where necessary. This is illustrated with /fèRé/ → [fèːfèRé] 'run intensively'

[fèːfèRé]

In the illustration in (47), the second syllable is eliminated after complete copying of the base, leaving behind the first syllable so that the reduplicated form surfaces as three syllables. Note however that the structure of the syllable of the base is determinant in the modification processes in partial reduplication. Let us consider words with monosyllabic and disyllabic syllable structures in Anaang.

4.8.1.1 Partial Reduplication and Monosyllabic Structure in Anaang

48 stem		reduplicant	
(i) /nék/	'dance'	[né:nék]	'dance intensively'
(ii) /ním/	'dive'	[ní:ním]	'dive (not otherwise)'
(ii) /tóp/	'throw'	[to:tóp]	'throw continuously'
(iv) /mèn/	'swallow'	[mèːmèn]	'swallow not otherwise'
(v) /dòp/	'be quiet'	[dòːdòp]	'be very quiet'

(vi) /dʒip/ 'steal' [dʒiːdʒip] 'steal intensively'

The whole syllable is copied with the elimination of the coda element of the base such that the initial syllable of the reduplicant remains open as shown in (49) below.

- 49 (i) /néknék/ CVC CVC [né:nék] CVV CVC
 (ii) /nímním/ CVC CVC [ní:ním] CVV CVC
 (iii) /tóptóp/ CVC CVC [tó:tóp] CVV CVC
 (iv) /mènmèn / CVC CVC [me:mèn] CVV CVC
 (v) /dòpdòp/ CVC CVC [dò:dòp] CVV CVC
 (vi) /dʒipdʒip/ CVC CVC [dʒiːdʒip] CVV CVC

4.8.1.2 Partial Reduplication and Disyllabic Structure in Anaang

- 50 (i) /fèRé / 'run' [fè: fèkè] 'run intensively'
 (ii) /dʒùttò/ 'double' [dʒù:dʒùttò] 'double continuously'
 (iii) /kòónó/ 'pack' [kò:kónó] 'pack (emphatic)'
 (iv) /kpékké/ 'cut' [kpé:kpékké] 'cut intensively'
 (v) /kánná/ 'turn' [ká:kánná] 'turn intensively'
 (vi) /dʒídé/ 'pursue' [dʒiːdʒidé] 'pursue intensively'

In disyllabic base, it is only the initial syllable that is copied to the base with some modifications where necessary. Detailed analysis is as follows.

51. underlying form		surface form	
(i) /fèRé fèRé/	CV-CV CV-CV	[fè:- fè-ké]	CVV-CV-CV
(ii) /dʒídédʒídé/	CV-CV CV-CV	[dʒiː-dʒí-dé]	CVV-CV-CV
(iii) /dʒùttò dʒùttò/	CVC-CV CVC-CV	[dʒù:-dʒùttò]	CVV-CVC-CV

(iv)/kpékké kpékké/	CVC-CV CVC-CV	[kpé:-kpék-ké]	CVV-CV-CV
(v)/kánná kánná/	CVC-CV CVC-CV	[ká:-kán-ná]	CVV-CV-CV
(vi)/kòònó kòònó/	CVV-CV CVV-CV	[kò: -kò-nó]	CVV-CV-CV

In example (51) above, the initial syllable is copied to the base without any modification in (i, ii and vi). This is borne out of the fact that the initial syllable is underlyingly open. In (iii-v), the coda element of the initial syllable is eliminated thereby leaving the syllable with an open structure. Whatever process is adopted, the general principle is that the initial syllable of the reduplicant must have an open heavy syllable structure. Therefore, whether a segment is eliminated or not, the initial syllable must be lengthened to maintain the weight unit of the word.

4.8.2 Complete Reduplication in Anaang

As mentioned earlier, some word classes like adverbs and adjectives in Anaang are derived through a process of full reduplication of the base (cf3.5.1). Earlier analyses (Essien 1990, Urua 1990, Cook 1985), have shown that this process cuts across other Lower Cross languages like Ibibio and Efik. Example follows:

52.

(i) /m̀kpá/	'death'	[m̀kpá-m̀kpá]	'deathly'
(ii) /ímàm/	'laughter'	[ímàm-ímàm]	'joyfully'
(iii) /m̀bidé/	'play'	[m̀bidé-m̀bidé]	'playfully'
(iv) /ibà/	'two'	[ibáj-bà]	'two by two'
(v) /ḡḡ ^w èèn/	black (pl)	[ḡḡ ^w èèn-ḡḡ ^w èèn]	'very dark (pl)'
(vi) /ibàk/	'wickedness'	[ibàR-ibàk]	'wickedly'
(vii) /kèèt/	'one'	[kèèrè-kèèt]	'one by one'
(viii) /dùòp/	'ten'	[dùòβò-dùòp]	'ten by ten'

These word classes when duplicated sometimes lead to a modification of the structure of the syllable as will be seen later. There is a one to one correspondence between the base and the reduplicant in (52). However, there is an alteration at the syllable level. In (53i -iii) the syllable of the base is reduplicated without any alteration as shown below.

53	base	syllable structure	reduplicant	syllable structure
(i)	/m̀kpá/	N-CV	[m̀kpá-m̀kpá]	N-CV-N-CV
(ii)	/m̀bidé/	N-CV-CV	[m̀bi-dé-m̀bi-dé]	N-CV-CV-N-CV-CV
(iii)	/ɨ́ɨ́ẁèèn/	N-CVVC	[ɨ́ɨ́ẁèèn-ɨ́ɨ́ẁèèn]	N-CVVC-N-CVVC

In example (53), the base has two syllables while the reduplicant surfaces as four syllables, which by implication means that the syllables of the base double by two. In another instance however, there can be an alteration of the internal structure of the reduplicant. This is illustrated as follows.

54	base	syllable structure	reduplicant	syllable structure
(i)	/imàm/	V CVC	[í-mà-mí-màm]	V-CV-CV-CVC
(ii)	/ibàk/	V CVC	[í-bà-Rì-bàk]	V-CV-CV-CVC

The base has a V CVC structure, whereas there is a coda shift at the surface representation, where the second syllable of the reduplicant releases its coda to a following syllable.

Another situation involves desyllabification. Let us consider the following data.

55 V-CV + V-CV → V-CVG-CV

- | | | | |
|-------|----------|-------|------------------|
| (i) | /ibà/ | /ibà/ | [i-bà-i-bà] |
| | two | | two by two |
| (ii) | /idè/ | /idè/ | [-idèi-dè] |
| | courage | | courageous |
| (iii) | /ifù/ | /ifù/ | [i-fù-i-fù] |
| | laziness | | serious laziness |
| (iv) | /imô/ | /imô/ | [i-mô-i-mô] |
| | wealth | | very wealthy |

In example (55), there is no correspondence between the syllable of the base and its reduplicant. The base has two syllables whereas the reduplicant has three instead of four syllables. One of the syllables is eliminated by dual syllable head principle when reduplicated. The segment that was associated with the pruned syllable head becomes relinked to the adjacent syllable to the left. Observe that the relinked segment is a unrounded high vowel /i/. In another situation, the syllable of the base is completely reduplicated, but there is an alteration of the phonological feature of the base. This is demonstrated as follows.

56 base	syllable structure	reduplicant	syllable structure
(i)	/ibàk/	V CVC	[i-bà-Ri-bàk] V-CV-CV-CVC
(ii)	/kèèt /	CVVC	[kèè-rè-kèèt] CVV-CV-CVVC
(iii)	/dùòp/	CVVC	[dùò-βò-dùòp] CVV-CV-CVVC

Observe that the base have two syllables each. The reduplicant have four syllables each. Observe equally that the final consonant(s) of the base surface as an intervocalic

segment of the reduplicant. Based on this, the segments become weakened to their homorganic approximants respectively so that /k/ → [R]; /t/ → [r]; /p/ → [β].

Secondly, like in every intervocalic segment, the coda becomes resyllabified as the onset of a following syllable thereby leaving the preceding syllable open.

Thirdly, there is an insertion of a vowel to parse the consonant clusters of the reduplicant. Segmental insertion applies here to restructure the basic syllable structure of the base. The right-most rhyme segment of the base is released to the onset, this is illustrated with /keet/ - [keere keet]

The example in (57) involves two processes: reduplication of the initial syllable and vowel insertion. The insertion of the vowel leads to coda shift. The vowel is insertion to break unpreferred consonant clusters created by reduplication. The segment created by insertion generates a new syllable with the coda of the initial syllable so that the reduplicant has three syllables instead of two.

The analysis in (58) involves words with closed syllable structure. In what follows, we are going to consider reduplication with open syllabic structure of the base.

8.2.1 V CV Base

59.

- | | | | |
|-----------------------------|------------|-----------|------------------|
| (i) /ènᵛ ènᵛ / 'gift' | [ènᵛ: -nᵛ] | V-CVV-CV | 'real gift' |
| (ii) /èkà èkà/ 'mother' | [èké: -kà] | V-CVV-CV | 'motherly' |
| (iii) /ímé ímé/ 'patiencee' | [íméi -mé] | V-CVV-CV | 'patiently' |
| (iv) /ímá ímá/ 'love' | [ímái -má] | V- CVV-CV | 'very lovely' |
| (v) /ùtáùtá/ 'spirogyra' | [ùtàu -tà] | V-CVV-CV | 'spirogyra-like' |
| (vi) /atᵛ atᵛ/ 'porridge' | [átᵛ: -tᵛ] | V-CVV-CV | 'porridge-like' |

V CV structure has two syllables with light template. Complete reduplication will produce VCV VCV structure as follows.

60. underlying form	surface form
(i) /ènɔ̀ ènɔ̀ / V-CV-V- CV	[ènɔ̀: -nɔ̀] V-CVV-CV
(ii) /èkà èkà/ V-CV-V- CV	[èké: -kà] V-CVV-CV
(iii) /imé imé/ V-CV-V-CV	[iméi -mé] V-CVV-CV
(iv) /ímá ímá/ V-CV-V- CV	[ímá i -má] V- CVVV-CV
(v) /ùtáùtá/ V-CV-V- CV	[ùtàu -tà] V-CVV-CV
(vi) /àtɔ̀ àtɔ̀/ V-CV-V- CV	[àtɔ̀: -tɔ̀] V-CVV-CV

When the right-most syllable is light and is followed by another syllable with a vocalic segment, two processes of reduplication are attested.

The first pattern results in assimilation and vowel lengthening as presented in (60 i, ii, vi).

The second pattern involves resyllabification of the copied base (60 iii, iv, v).

Observe that the second syllable is lengthened in (60i, ii, vi) after the assimilation of an adjacent vocalic element at the surface level. The third syllable in (60iii - v) syllabifies to a preceding syllable. The structure of the reduplicant therefore reduces from four to three syllables. There is no tonal alteration in (60v and vi). The penultimate syllable does not have any additional high tone as was earlier generalized. This is borne out of the fact that reduplication here is not to intensify or repeat any action. In other words, no emphasis is created from the reduplicant in (v and vi).

The data in (60i-iv) involve focused items. The raising of tone in (i - iv) is therefore necessary since focused items in Anaang have an inherent high tone even if the items undergo a complete or partial reduplication process. The high tone occurs on the first syllable in partial reduplication and on the penultimate syllable in complete reduplication process.

The phenomenon of syllable structure processes is a concept adopted here for the analyses of segments and non-segments in connected speech as different from discrete form. These processes provide direct evidence for an autosegmental representation made up of various interconnected levels or tiers as different from the linear approach. Many phenomena relevant to the phonology of languages cannot be properly understood unless we enrich the representation within the syllable. Segments need to be members of the syllable if they are to be pronounced or get deleted by stray erasure.

We discussed syllable -based processes in Anaang. While certain processes occur within the syllable, others cut across the syllable boundaries. We have established that segments become modified according to context. Many of the processes occur to modify unpreferred syllable structure.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

5.1 Summary

In this research, the motivation of the syllable in Anaang has been explored. Anaang is said to have a simple syllable structure. However, there are constraints that spell out how segments are assigned to syllables and where. Syllabification in Anaang is therefore strictly guided by Anaang phonotactics. The combination of segments into words or morphemes are guided by the phonotactic statement of Anaang. All words can insightfully be syllabified into Anaang syllable. Therefore words that do not confirm to the phonotactics are regarded as ill-formed.

A number of theories which differ in their view of the internal structure of the syllable have been reviewed. Our interest is mainly on the onset-rhyme theory. The onset-rhyme theory was adopted to examine the way in which strings of segments can be organized into syllables. It has been established that syllable structure forms part of phonological constituents. Therefore, we proceeded to investigate the relation between the terminal position of the syllable structure and the featural structures that represent the content of segments, and showed that this relationship is autosegmental. The application of the multi-tiered representation of autosegmental theory shows that a particular set of features can be associated to more than one syllable position as in the representation of phonological length and tonal clusters. In another instance one level of tier is seen as being independent of the other in such a way that the alteration of the feature on a particular tier may not necessarily affect the other tiers as seen in tone and the deletion of a tone bearing segment.

It has equally been established that some word classes have a fixed syllable structure. In this case, it is possible for one to look at the syllable structure of a word and determine the word class of such a word. For instance, verbs in Anaang are said to have a non-syllabic initial segment.

At the same time, the syllable is seen to be determinant in language enrichment or word formation processes in Anaang just like in most African languages. In affixation process for instance, the type of affix to be affixed to a root word is determined by the syllable structure of the root. The same principles apply to grammatical constructions in Anaang.

Phonological processes are seen to apply to satisfy the well-formedness condition of a language. In Anaang, a new segment can be created to parse illicit clusters. An existing segment can be deleted to repair the word to a preferred syllable structure.

5.2 Conclusions

In standard generative phonology, the syllable was not regarded as an important entity, rather words were said to consist of sequences of consonants and vowels. In the non-linear framework, it has been established that the syllable is an important constituent in phonological study. Words can exhaustively be divided into a sequence of syllables.

The motivation for the syllable in phonological studies is embedded in its functions. For instance, the syllable of a language specifies what a well formed word is. Segments are combined together to form well formed words. But there are limitations or constraints on the distribution of these segments at syllable initial, medial and final positions. These constraints are specified by the phonotactic possibility combination of specific languages. In Anaang, for instance, the segments

/P r ʋ ŋ / can occur as the onset element of the syllable internally, but these segments are prohibited from word initial position by Anaang phonotactics. This shows that restrictions that hold for segment sequences for word at restricted positions may not necessarily hold for syllable in the same position in most instances. In other words, the need for a syllabic domain in phonological representation is motivated more firmly, in terms of restrictions on well-formedness and intuitively by appealing to the awareness that native speakers have on syllabification. The constraints are said to sometimes apply to the word, or to the level of the morpheme. But our investigation reveals that a great deal of constraints refer to the level of the syllable structure. A reference to the syllable structure helps us to understand why certain segments are constrained from certain positions of the word or morpheme.

The syllable defines the well-formedness condition with regards to the complexity of the association of melody levels with other tiers. It specifies the upper / lower limits of segments that may be associated to the skeletal unit. This of course gives rise to the different types of syllable structure in specific languages. It

has been established that Anaang cannot anchor complex structure as the onset or coda on the skeleton.

Syllabification is a process that encompasses both the feature content and the segments. This process is not significant in Anaang, therefore syllabification of lexical items cannot be successfully applied to underlying form since syllabification is not distinctive. Syllabification is to a word what punctuation is to sentences or a whole discourse. With proper punctuation, reading is made easy, fast and meaning clarified. Proper syllabification contributes to ease of production and analyses of words.

Phonological rules are insightfully understood when formulated within the syllable (Kenstowicz 1994). For instance, rules of nasalization in Anaang is blocked by syllable boundary, a vowel becomes nasalized only in an environment of an adjacent nasal segment within the syllable. The representation of the syllable on syllable tier makes this and other rules to become simpler and clearer. Rules cannot apply in a language if the output is to violate a phonotactic statement. Therefore rules apply in a language if and only if its effect is to enrich the well-formedness of their representations. Deletion or insertion rule for instance, applies in Anaang mainly to reduce the syllable to a preferred shape since Anaang does not permit consonant clusters.

It appears that different types of syllable structure violations are handled by different general strategies: segments which do not fit into the syllable of a language are labeled 'extrasyllabic'. Such segments get deleted, or resyllabified by epenthesis. Whereas segments which violate featural restrictions on positions within a syllable are subject to feature changing process. This can be seen in the repair strategy applied in the modification of loanwords.

The multi-tiered approach was equally adopted for the discussion of the aspects of syllabification and syllable based processes such as deletion, insertion, compensatory lengthening, and vowel harmony among others. The outcome is that syllable positions typically are interpreted on the basis of their relationship with segments. The creation of syllabic structure presupposes the existence of segment structure and that syllable plays an active role in characterizing constraints and processes. Most of the processes in chapter four are motivated by the need to respect constraints. For instance, the violation of dual syllable head constraint is generally

avoided by syllable head pruning which automatically leads to resyllabification/disyllabification as the outcome.

Models of structure internal to Anaang syllable show that consonant clustering is not permissible. We tried to build up the importance of the syllable in some phonological processes. We therefore conclude that segments need to be members of the syllable if they are to be pronounced.

This research studies the basic properties of Anaang syllables. Even though it has not been able to solve all the problems, it has explored and explained some of the irregularities in the structure of Anaang phonology to some extent. These irregularities had not been explored by past researchers on Anaang specifically, (Idem 1994, Michael 2000, Udoh 1998, Udondatta 1993, 2000). There are some reasons to assume that details on Anaang syllables were not of primary concern to these studies.

The structure of Anaang is very similar to that of other Lower Cross languages, but with slight variations in the sense that these languages share a lot of lexical similarities but there are also significant differences. On the other hand, there is no Lower Cross language which has exactly the same syllable structure as Anaang. The syllable structure of Efik and Ibibio are much closer, but they still differ in some aspects of phonological and morphological constituents. Anaang is unique in its own system.

The phonotactics of Anaang as they appear in the lexicon is considered here, while generalizations are made on the internal structure irrespective of the functions of these words in Anaang. This does not, of course, imply that phonetic investigations into the structures of Anaang are not desirable, since phonetics following Inkelas & Leben (1990), Kingston (2007) explains certain phonological patterns. There is therefore the need for future detailed phonetic research to be carried out on the sounds and the tonal structure of Anaang.

Tone is an indispensable feature of Anaang syllable even though it is autonomous. The features of tone cut across phonetics- phonology, morphology-syntax, semantics and even sociolinguistic description. In sociolinguistics, for instance tone is very remarkable in African drumbeats and proverbs in a way that proverb riddles are interpreted devoid the words and meaning but within the context of the syllable and tonal rhythm. Adequate data collection and actual experimental

analyses of Anaang tone is therefore required to unravel these diverse and interesting phenomena before generalizations could be reached.

Constraint on syllable shapes go a long way to capturing segment sequencing in linguistic forms including tones. Crucially, phonotactic constraints operate with syllable-based constraints. Restrictions that make reference to morphological constituents may affect the place of syllable boundaries. Restrictions on phonological constituents higher or lower than the syllable may affect syllable shapes or their weight properties. It is therefore left for future research to establish the range of such interfaces and the range of structural variation that arises from there. Several potential problem areas like glide formation, vowel clusters, and sonority value have not been discussed in detail in this research. These areas will serve to stimulate further research in Anaang.

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APPENDIX 1

700 ENGLISH WORD LIST

ENGLISH	ANAANG
Air	/áfùm/
Sun	/útún/
Mud	/mbát/
Rainbow	/álùkàwàsì/
Road	/úsún/
Fog	/ntùRùwè/
Mist	/ndedèp/
Sky	/àṅṅ /
Chalky	/ndòm/
Water	/ṅṅṅ /
Thunder	/àlùmà/
Creator (God)	/àbót/ /
Hill	/ábó t/
Land/ ground	/í sṅ/
Light	/íkáy/
Space	/ùfàn/
Lake	/ùlò/
Boundary	/álaná/
Moon	/áfíṅ/
World	/àdorobót/ /
Stream	/ílim/
Sea	/íṅà/

Darkness	/àkúm/
Country	/ílūŋ/
Stone	/itíát/
Pit	/àbè /
Hole	/álú /
Rain	/élim/
Dust	/ntɔŋ/
Season	/ini/
Dryseason	/nnádʒo /
Rainseason	/ edeep/
Valley	/ àbèlèŋ/
Wind	/áfùm/
Forest	/ ákà i/
Antelope	/ édòp/
Elephant	/ énin/
Hippopotamus	/ isantim/
Leopard	/ ùsimèkpè/
Lion	/ ékpè /
Monkey	/ ébɔk/
Squirrel	/ áduà /
Rat	/ è kpt /
Goat	/ ébó t/
Pig	/édi/
Sheep	/édɔŋ/
Cow	/énàŋ/
Cat	/àŋwà/

Dog	/éwá/
Toad	/ík ^w òt/
Frog	/mfòt/
Chameleon	/ákúwè/
Serpent	/údúRikòt/
Python	/àsáwò/
Tortoise	/ ikút/
Hen	/únèn/
Owl	/nkùríkù/
Bat	/mkpékpèm/
Cray fish	/àw [†] /
Snail	/ék ^w òŋ/
Small snail	/ŋkòrikò/
Maggot	/nnòŋ/
Cockroach	/mfém
Jigger	/nnòŋ/
Praying mantis	/àtikòŋkòŋ/
Fly	/nsùŋ/
Mosquito	/ábòŋ/
Wing	/mbá/
Beak	/ínùáúnén/
Horn	/nnùk/
Feather	/ŋg ^w á/
Egg	/ŋkuwà únèn/
Bark	/kpòí/

Crow of cock	/kpòk/
Bleat	/maí/
Pound	/tím/
To stir	/kámá/
Grind	/kɔk/
Cook	/tèm/
To shell	/fòt/
To skin	/dʒiàǵá/
To pick off leaves	/kò:/
To drain / filter	/lɛkɔ/
To squeeze	/ɲímmé/
To mix	/g ^w á:k/
To roast	/fɔp/
Beads / ring	/ɲk ^w uà/
Button	/mmáná/
Belt	/ikpáísìn/
Hat	/itám/
Cloth	/áfɔɲ/
Shirt	/áfɔɲídèm/
Trouser	/áfɔɲúkòt/
Shoe	/ikpáúkòt/
Crown	/àǵnà àǵnà/
Scarf	/áfɔɲíg ^w ò/
Skirt	/mkpíɲ/
Coat	/akòt/

Watch	/ɪkàniká úbòk/
Handkerchief	/àfòḡínuà/
Dress	/ àfòḡ ag ^w òùḡ ^w à:n/
Purse	/akpɔsí/
Sweater	/ àfòḡ átweḡ/
Pant	/ibá/
Box	/ àkèbé àfòḡ/
House	/úfòk/
Rope	/úluḡk/
Fence	/àk ɔ/
Ladder	/àbé:t/
Courtyard	/èdèmésà/
Kitchen	/é kò/
Door	/úsúḡ/
Window	/àwindò/
Padlock	/udzén úsuḡ/
Floor	/isòḡ/
Roof	/àkòḡm/
Key	/út ár úsúḡ/
clay	/mb át/
Cement	/àsimén/
Nail	/ḡkú:m/
To plaster	/dzíòḡɔ/
To dig	/tippé/
Latrine	/úfòR íkòt/
School	/úfòkḡwét/

Church	/úfɔ̃ʋáwàsi/
Hospital	/úfɔ̃R íbɔ̃k/
Place	/itié/
Prison	/úfɔ̃kɛkpɔ̃kɔ̃p/
House work	/ útómúfɔ̃k/
Raffia stick	/ákɔ:k/
Grave	/ uli/
Bamboo	/átíáúbóm/
Head	/íg ^w ùò/
Hair	/ídèl/
Face	/ísó/
Nose	/áluíg ^w ùò/
Eyes	/áɲèn/
Cheek / jaw	/mbáɲ/
Mandible	/ébèk/
Ears	/útɔ̃ɲ/
Neck	/itɔ̃ɲ/
Chest	/étʃit/
Hand	/úbɔ̃k/
Armpit	/úfáʋà/
Fingers	/nɲɛ:n úbɔ̃k/
Toes	/nɲɛ:n úkòt/
Waist	/ítʃin/
Stomach	/ekpa/
Back	/èdèm/

Buttock	/éftt/
Leg	/úkót/
Tongue	/édémè/
Teeth	/édét/
Beard	/ɲwàébék/
Anus	/ítúdáfít/
Artery	/ásìp/
Brain	/mfúlò/
Ankle / knee	/édɔɲ/
Scar	/ɲkárán/
Body	/idem/
Rib bone	/ákpɔ́ ésít
Bone	/ákpɔ́/
Navel	/ákóp/
Skull	/mkpɔ́kpɔ́ɔ́/
Intestine	/ns là/
Shoulders	/áfádá/
Stool	/áfít/
Forehead	/ákoisò/
Liver	/áf ú:t/
Gum of teeth	/nsìɲ/
Breath	/íɲ ^w é:k/
Shin	/ásián/
Tears	/ɲɲ ^w ɔ́:ɲ ádzét/
Right hand	/úbɔ́ɔ́ údóm/

Left hand	/úbɔɛ úfién/
Catarrh	/mkpɔ/
Toe nail	/mbàrá úkòt/
Palm	/éká úbɔk/
Skin	/ìkpáidém/
Penis	/éfét/
Vagina	/ítút/
Wrist	/ítɔŋ úbɔk/
Pus	/ímɛn/
Boil	/mbót/
Saliva	/étáp/
Blood	/ídʒì:p/
Breast	/ébá/
Sweat	/ìkpɔ/
Heal	/étìtìRè/
Back of head	/èkɔt/
Womb	/ilìp/
Voice	/údzò/
Squat	/sɔrɔ/
Sit	/tìé/
Stand	/dá/
Clap	/miá/
Eat	/diá/
Catch	/mɛm/
Swallow	/mèn/

Gulp	/wɔŋ/
Sip	/tɛm/
Stagger	/fũmmó/
Sing	/kwɔ/
Bend down	/nɛɔ/
Spit	/siák/
Pass	/fũrɔ/
Punch	/tũak/
Slap	/miá/
Grab	/mɛm/
Groan	/mim/
Stretch	/lé:bé/
Lick	/dái/
Beg	/kpédzé/
Bite	/dóm/
swim	/g ^w ɔk/
walk	/sàŋá/
run	/fèRé/
pinch	/ɔzibé/
cry	/tũá/
shout	/bɔŋ/
crawl	/piɔn/
look	/sé/
laugh	/sák/
blow	/fũt/

vomit	/kɔ̃k/
to call	/kót/
to swallow	/mèn/
to drink	/ŋ ^w ɔ̃ŋ/
to run	/fèʋé/
to say	/tàn/
to kick	/tiá/
to sleep	/dádʒá/
to hear	/kóp/
to excrete	/t ɔ̃ŋɔ̃/
to taste	/dái/
to grow	/kpón/
to be tall	/ŋiɔ̃ŋ/
to climb	/lɔk:/
to chew	/tá/
to eat	/diá/
to walk	/sànǎ/
to awaken	/démme/
to meander/dodge	/fèp/
to suck	/g ^w ɔ̃p/
to touch	/tɛ:k/
to cough	/kɔ̃ŋ/
to urinate	/tɔ̃k/
to see	/sé/
brush / dust	/k ^w uɔ̃kɔ̃

to cream	/fĩ ɔŋɔ/
to wash	/dʒét/
to comb	/sár á/
cream	/álàn/
chewing stick	/ákɔk/
wear	/siné/
to shave	/kpo:ŋo/
to iron	/k ^w uɔkɔ/
dirty	/mbát/
soap	/átɔŋ/
mirror	/ùm
Baby	/nséRádʒèn/
in-law	/úkòt/
husband	/èbé/
wife	/ŋ ^w á:n/
children	/umanafa/
family	/ekpɛk
village	ílɛŋ/
brother	/ádʒèn éká ág ^w òdè:n/
sister	/ádʒèn éká ág ^w òŋ ^w á:n/
father	/èté/
mother	èk à/
uncle	/édʒdʒáká èté/
aunt	/édʒáká èk à/
grandfather	/ètébòm/

grandmother	/ èk à ék à/
first son	/ákpán/
second son	/ùd ɔ/
third son	/ùdɔ ùd ɔ/
forth son	/ùd ɔfi à/
first daughter	/ àli àká/
second daughter	/ŋŋ ^w à/
third daughter	/àŋ ^w á àŋ ^w á /
forth daughter	/ úŋ ^w àkká/
grand child	/ádʒèdʒèn/
Adult	/èkámábá ^w ò/
Friend	/ùfàn/
Stranger	/èsèná ^w ò/
Woman	/ág ^w òŋ ^w à:n/
Man	/ ág ^w òdè:n/
Boy	/ètòk ág ^w òdèn/
Girl	/ ètòk ág ^w òŋ ^w à:n/
Twin	/àmànàmbà/